

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST *of* SCOTLAND

Formalising the Informal: Climate change and Health: An analysis of the impact of climate change on smallholder farmers' food security in the Department of Koung-khi in west Cameroon.

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A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy in collaboration with Hamburg University of Applied Sciences.

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DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis is entirely my own and has not been previously submitted for another PhD or comparable award.

Hubert Fudjumdjum

May 2024

ABSTRACT

Background

Global climate change significantly impairs developing nations since it jeopardises their progress in development. Its effects have made agriculture a predominantly vulnerable sector, resulting in yield reductions and food insecurity in sub-Saharan countries. This investigation shed light on the influence of climate variability on household food security, focusing on the perspective of smallholder farmers. Climate change affects smallholder farmers in Cameroon, but little literature exists on its effect on food security. Therefore, this doctoral study investigates climate change's impact on the country's most used subsistence crops (beans, maize, potatoes), specifically in the rural settings of the Koung-Khi department, located in the western part of the country. It also scrutinises the current change in weather patterns and its effect on the nutritional status of rural smallholder farmers, as well as adaptation strategies and challenges faced.

Methodology

The researcher applied concurrent mixed-method triangulation involving a quantitative approach with 252 smallholder farmers and a qualitative approach with 34 participants in the focus group discussion and 15 in key informant interviews. We collected and analysed climate data on precipitation and subsistence crop yield from 2005 to 2022 to establish a broader appreciation of the association between climate change and yield patterns. Additionally, we validated the findings through triangulation. Descriptive statistical methods were used to analyse food crop production quantities and meteorological trends. Through an econometric analysis, we estimated crop production depending on precipitation, rainy season length, and surface cultivated area. Specifically, we used a Cobb-Douglas production function model, a widely used economic model that measures the relationship between inputs and outputs in agricultural production. We used the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) based estimator for this analysis.

Findings

Findings showed annual rainfall decreased with a reduction in several rainy days' precipitation, soil erosion, and storms, the climate events most frequently witnessed. Farmers' experiences align with observed trends in climate variables, highlighting important perception-based surveys as a complement to climate research. A multilinear correlation with the Cobb-Douglas production function showed a correlation between climatic and non-climatic factors, emphasising the detrimental impact of climate change on staple food production, which worsens nutritional status.

Insights from group discussions and interviews underlined complaints about the decline in meal frequency and the inferior quality of grains, which resulted in less flavourful food. Significant challenges smallholder farmers face includes the high cost of farm inputs, such as unpredictable weather, limited subsidy access, lack of market access, and low soil fertility. Adaptation efforts comprise growing short-lived crops, intercropping, increasing irrigation, changing planting dates, and engaging in additional income-generating activities.

Conclusion

This doctoral study underscores the profound impact of climate change on food security among smallholder subsistence farmers in the Koung-Khi department of Cameroon. The findings reveal a significant decline in annual rainfall and an increase in extreme weather events, which detrimentally affect staple crop yields, exacerbating food insecurity and nutritional deficits. These findings are crucial, as they highlight the urgent need for action to mitigate the effects of climate change on agriculture. The research highlights the correlation between climate variability and reduced agricultural productivity through quantitative and qualitative methodologies. It also emphasises the importance of perception-based surveys in complementing empirical climate data. The challenges farmers face, including high input costs and unpredictable weather patterns, compound the struggle for food security.

Nevertheless, the adaptation strategies identified, such as growing short-lived crops, intercropping, and increasing irrigation, offer pathways to resilience. These insights contribute to a deeper understanding of smallholder farmers' vulnerabilities and adaptive capacities, informing policy interventions to enhance agricultural sustainability and food security in the face of climate change. Improving rural infrastructure through roads, storage facilities, and markets is fundamental to reducing food waste and enhancing access. These measures can strengthen food security in rural Africa and ensure sustainable food for future generations.

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

- ACMAD: Africa Centre of Meteorological Applications for Development
- AfDB: African Development Bank
- AFSA: Alliance for Food Sovereignty in Africa
- COP: Conference of Parties
- CH: Cadre Harmonisé
- COVID-19: Corona Virus diseases-2019
- CBOs: Community-based organisations
- CEMAC: Communauté Economique et Monétaire de l’Afrique Centrale/ Central African Economic and Monetary Community.
- DHS: Demographic and Health Survey
- FAO: Food and Agriculture Organisation
- FAOSTAT: Food and Agriculture Organisation Statistics
- FIES: Food Insecurity Experience Scale
- FGD: Focus Group Discussion
- FSIN: Food Security Information Network
- GHGs: Greenhouse Gas.
- GAR: Global Assessment Report
- GDP: Gross Domestic Product
- IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
- IRAD: Institute de Recherche Agricole pour le Development/Institute for Agriculture Research for Development
- IFPRI: International Food Policy Research Institute
- IFAD: International Fund for Agricultural Development
- INS: Institut National des Statistiques/ National Institute of Statistics
- IDPs: Internally Displaced Peoples
- KII: Key Informant Interview
- MINFI: Ministre des Finances / Ministry of Finances
- MINEPDEDM: Ministère de l’Environnement, de la Protection de la Nature et du Développement Durable/Ministry of Environment, Protection of the Nature and Sustainable Development
- MINADER: Ministre de L’Agriculture et Développement Rural/ Ministry of Agriculture and Rural development
- ENSAN: Enquête Nationale sur la sécurité Alimentaire et Nutritionnelle/ National Survey on Food and Nutrition Security
- NGOs: Non-governmental organisations

PNACC: Plan National d'Adaptation au Changement Climatique/ National Climate Change Adaptation Plan

RASIPEFIN: Rapport sur la Situation et les Perspectives Economiques, Sociales et Financières de la Nation

SDG: Sustainable Development Goals

UEC: Evangelical University of Cameroon

UNFCCC: United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

UNDRR: United Nations Office for Risk Reduction

UNFSS: United Nations Food Systems Summit

UNICEF: United Nations Children's Fund

UNDP: United Nations Development Programme

UNNPS: United Nations National Population Status

UNCDD: United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification

WHO-UN: World Health Organisation- United Nations

WMO: World Meteorological Organisation

WFP: World Food Programme.

W.B.: World Bank.

WHO: World Health Organisation

1. Chapter One. General Introduction and Research Framework

1.0. Introduction

This chapter introduces the topic by offering a comprehensive overview of its background. It clearly outlines the problem being investigated and the study's objectives. Moreover, the chapter outlines the reasoning behind the problem and emphasises the significance of its expected contribution to the current body of knowledge.

1.1 Background

Climate change remains a concern for the international scientific community and countries worldwide because of its potential and proven adverse effects on individuals and ecosystems (Baste and Watson, 2022). It has become a global political priority since the Rio Conference 1992 (Orsini and Kang, 2023). Consistent with the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), climate change is defined as weather variability that can be identified through statistical assessments by using changes in the mean or the range that have an extended length, typically many years or longer (IPCC, 2014 quoted in IPCC, 2022). Similarly, the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC, 2001) defines climate change as a hard and fast series of weather adjustments attributable to humans, both at once and not directly, that trade the composition of the global surroundings with the regular climate variability found over comparable durations. The term climate change then refers to variations in temperatures and precipitation because of greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) from deforestation, combustion of fossil fuels, industrialisation, and urbanisation (Ahmed et al., 2023). Besides abnormal trends in weather patterns and the regularity of seasons worldwide, scientists, researchers, and affected people are reporting changes beyond natural variations of inland and ocean temperatures (UNFCCC, 2022).

The FAO (2023) reports that over 29% of the sector's land locations experienced extreme drought for at least one month per year between 2012 and 2021, compared to 1951-1960. In terms of valuation, severe drought impacted 65.46% of the land in the African region (UNDRR, 2023). Scientists expect changes in weather patterns to triple the occurrence of drought. Cape Town, situated in the southwest of South Africa, is a notable example, enduring a three-year drought (2015 to 2017) caused by a prolonged lack of rainfall in the area (Wolski et al., 2021). Drought has far-reaching consequences, including compromised food and water security, sanitation, livelihoods, and increased risks of wildfires and infectious diseases (Adewoyin et al., 2023). According to the 2007 Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) report, scientists have reached a consensus that global warming is indisputable and has worldwide consequences (IPCC, 2007). In recent years, increases in greenhouse fuel concentrations (GHGs) and aerosols have modified the energy balance of the climate device (Patra and Khatri, 2022) and brought the global temperature to a growth of 0.89°C from 1901 to 2012 (Gavidia, 2023).

Figure 1: Temperature change measures over land by region.

Source: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Statistical yearbook 2022. Rome, Italy FAOSTAT. (2022) World food and agriculture. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/3/cc2211en/online/cc2211en.html> (Accessed: 03 March 2023).

According to Figure 1 above, on a global scale, 2021 has become the fourth warmest year, with 1.44°C more than the world reference measured over land, after 2020 (1.71°C), 2016 (1.66 °C), and 2019 (1.45°C) (FAOSTAT, 2022). With 1.60 °C in 2021 (significantly lower than 3.35 °C in 2020), Europe experienced the most widespread temperature alternate in 2021 (and for a maximum of the period 2000-2021) (FAOSTAT, 2022). Among the other areas, Asia (1.55°C), the Americas (1.45°C), Africa (1.43°C) and Oceania (0.63°C) had the most considerable temperature changes (FAOSTAT, 2022). The average temperature exchange within the 2010s was 1.24 °C, compared to 0.95 °C in the 2000s (FAOSTAT, 2022). Projections predict an increase in future temperatures of 1.8 to 4°C depending on emission scenarios and attribute 70% of the causes of this increase to human activity.

The occurrence is prevalent in tropical regions, hindering local progress (Anougue *et al.*, 2013). Conventions and legal guidelines aimed at stabilising the concentration of greenhouse gases (GHGs) have been adopted and ratified by international bodies around the world, such as the UNFCCC in 1992, the Rio Conference on Biodiversity Conservation in 1992, the Millennium Development Goals in 2000, the Doha Conference in 2012, that of Warsaw in 2013, the Sustainable Development Goals in 2015, in addition to the most current meetings of the events (COP 21 and 22) respectively, in Paris in 2015, and Marrakech in 2016.

According to the most recent IPCC Synthesis Report 2023, global warming is undeniable, marked by higher atmospheric and ocean temperatures. The estimated temperature variation in Africa between 1970 and 2004 was between 0.2 and 2°C, highlighting the continent's vulnerability. A joint WHO-UN report highlights that Africa experienced 622 natural disasters between 2010 and 2020.

The impact of these disasters in 2021 resulted in the deaths and disappearance of 11.1% (11133/100,000) of Africa's population. The mortality rate in highly vulnerable countries has risen 15 times more than in less vulnerable countries over the past decade (UNDRR, 2023). Droughts, primarily in Africa, instigated 34% of catastrophe-related incidents between 1970 and 2019, accounting for 7% of all disaster cases worldwide (Camazzola, 2023). Climate change contributes to health issues, which include vector-borne diseases, water-borne and foodborne sicknesses, mental and strain-related issues, malnutrition, zoonotic diseases, and persistent respiratory and non-communicable diseases (Neira *et al.*, 2023). In times of severe weather emergencies, such as heatwaves, storms, and floods, it is the most susceptible and marginalised populations that bear the brunt, namely women, children, impoverished communities, displaced persons, and individuals with underlying health conditions (Neira *et al.*, 2023).

Food security is an active concept that has advanced and been modified over the past 50 years (Clapp *et al.*, 2022). In 1943, at Hot Springs, Virginia, the United Nations conference on food and agriculture centred on food supply mentioned: "A secure, adequate, and suitable supply of food should be a gracious aim in every country" (UN, 1943 quoted in Clapp *et al.*, 2022).

In the Nineteen Seventies, the term "food protection" first appeared in policy circles (CFS, 2012), and during the 1974 World Food Conference, it became official for the first time in a policy context as "the availability of good international meals components of primary foodstuffs, mainly to prevent severe shortages of food in the occasion of sizable crop failure to preserve a regular expansion of food consumption in countries with low ranges of capita consumption and fluctuations in production costs" (UN, 1943; Shaw, 2007, quoted in Clapp *et al.*, 2022). According to the World Food Summit 1996, "Food security exists when every person, at all times, have physical and financial means to sufficiently secure nutritious food that meets their dietary desires and food preferences for an active and healthful life."

The definition was updated in 2001 to add the word "social," which generated a new meaning: "Food security exists when all people, at all times, have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life" (Clapp *et al.*, 2022). According to this definition, food security encompasses access to food, availability, utilisation, and supply. Besides the established four pillars of international policy guidance, Clapp *et al.* (2022) explained that agency and sustainability already go hand in hand with the right to food and are about to be adopted as a six-dimensional framework for food security. The agency is widely recognised as essential to addressing widening food inequities, including power imbalances among actors within those systems. It allows entities and clusters to exercise some rule over their circumstances and contribute meaningfully to governance processes. The High-Level Panel of Experts (HLPE) (2020) refers to sustainability as "practices within the food system that support long-term alteration of ordinary, public, and cost-effective systems, ensuring the present generation's food needs are met while safeguarding the future's food needs."

The UN Global Assessment Report on Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR, 2023) sheds light on building resilience to cope with and respond to shocks. Despite prioritising intervention over risk reduction, African countries have a low rate of implementing national disaster management strategies (UNDRR, 2023). The benefits of early warning systems are three times higher in vulnerable contexts due to their ability to reduce damage from disasters. The COVID-19 pandemic has raised doubts about the need for a multi-hazard and multi-sectoral strategy (Lageard and Bhattacharya-Mis, 2023).

1.1.1 Climate Change and Food Security: An Overview

Globally, thousands of scientists and organisations are continuously improving our comprehension of the reasons and results of changes in weather patterns (UNFCCC, 2022). The World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) and Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) offer significant available evidence to underpin the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) action (UNFCCC, 2022). The IPCC’s Sixth Assessment Report of 2022 confirms that changes in weather patterns are happening and that their effects adversely influence socioeconomic improvement and ecosystems. Because of global warming, precipitation patterns are changing, temperatures are rising, and extreme weather events are increasing (Abhilash, 2023; Muthoni, 2023). These changes significantly affect agricultural production, water resources, and livelihoods (Dovie and Pabi, 2023; Hindiye, Albatayneh and AlAmawi, 2023). It has been proven that changes in weather patterns influence crop growth (Hendriks et al., 2022), mainly crop respiratory and evapotranspiration (Malhi, Kaur and Kaushik, 2021, cited from Hendriks et al., 2022). Therefore, the capacity of the crop to grow, in addition to the time it takes from planting to harvest, is threatened (IAP, 2018; Malhi, Kaur and Kaushik, 2021; Hendriks et al., 2022).

Figure 2 Total agriculture losses as a share of Agricultural Gross Domestic Product by Subregion (1991-2021). Source: FAO. 2023. In Brief to The Impact of Disasters on Agriculture and Food Security 2023 – Avoiding and reducing losses through investment in resilience. Rome, FAO. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc8500en>. Accessed: 20 May 2024.

Regarding the total agriculture losses as a share of Agricultural Gross Domestic Product by Subregion, Asia needs more than 4 percent of the agricultural value added. In comparison, Africa accounts for about 8 percent of the increase in agricultural value, and the variation is more extensive in the small sector (Figure 2). Equally, losses are more significant in upper and middle-income countries but less than in Low-income countries, especially SIDS, which suffer the most from additional agricultural gains, as Figure 2 shows.

In September 2021, delegates from 183 countries at the United Nations Food Systems Summit (UNFSS) in New York discussed the “three Cs” (climate change, COVID-19 disease, and conflict) that threaten recent progress in fighting hunger, malnutrition, and undernutrition (Hendriks et al., 2022). Because of the summit, inclusive and consistent mechanisms that establish and implement global transition pathways for achieving the 2030 Agenda must be supported.

One of the most devastating floods in 2022 inundated a third of Pakistan from July to October, destroying half its crops at a cost estimated at \$2.3 billion (Patel, 2023). Egypt’s Nile Delta, the leading agricultural-producing region for the North African nation, suffered from high summer and low winter temperatures because of the elevated temperatures (Patel, 2023; Alleyne, 2023). Similarly, Patel (2023) emphasised that high temperatures and drought during the rainy season in the south threatened China’s domestic autumn crops. Considering rainfall shortages, most exporting countries, such as India and China, expect low crops in 2022-2023 (Patel, 2023). To guarantee domestic supply, India, the world’s largest rice exporter, restricted exports between September and November 2022 (Kumar, 2023). This decision affected sufficient regions, as rice is a vital food source for human consumption.

Europe experienced record temperatures in July 2022, with temperatures over 40 degrees Celsius in the UK, France, Italy, Spain, and Germany (Patel, 2022). It coincided with the flowering stage, reducing crop yields for several months. The European Commission announced that the yield outlook for summer crops in the EU has seen a substantial decrease (Patel, 2022). Figure 3 shows that maize, sunflower, and soybean yields were reduced by 8% to 9%, while the yield forecasts fell below the 5-year average.

Figure 3: Forecasted crop yields for summer crops were substantially reduced, driven by the heatwave. Source: European Commission – JRC MARS Bulletin (July 2022) Available at: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC127963>. (Accessed: 20 October 2023)

Climate change is a key driver behind these recent global environmental crises and one of the leading causes of severe food crises (Molotoks, Smith and Dawson, 2021). Climate variability could profoundly affect global food security because of changes in population growth and land use (Molotoks, Smith and Dawson, 2021). Food systems, however, face constant growth in requests and increasing ecological pressures (Myers *et al.*, 2017). Climate change may threaten the stability of global food systems because of short-term variability in the four dimensions of food security (Wheeler and Von Braun, 2013). Furthermore, the loss of water requirement has enlarged fivefold in the 21st century, despite an expansion in the length and severity of droughts in more than one-third of the Earth. (Neupane *et al.*, 2022). Because of climate and environmental alternates, country-wide self-sufficiency may shift away from the home supply, increasing the need to import extra food and increasing vulnerability to food scarcity (Hendriks *et al.*, 2022).

Since 1960, the annual suggested temperature in relevant Africa has elevated by 0.75°C to 1.2°C (Aloysius *et al.*, 2016;). Hu and Huang (2020) document that warm days and heatwaves increased between 1979 and 2016, while cold extremes decreased (Seneviratne *et al.*, 2021).

According to the Africa Centre of Meteorological Applications for Development (ACMAD) report for 2022, the seasonal precipitation forecast for Guinea-Gulf countries was below average from April to June 2022. Human-induced climate change has negatively affected several sectors, including water scarcity, abridged food production, and slow economic progress (IPCC, 2022). Global warming at 1.5°C can potentially damage African economies, agriculture, human health, and ecosystems (IPCC, 2022; Lucas, Guo and Guillén-Gosálbez, 2023).

The African Development Bank (AfDB) (2012) similarly stated that climate change's effects threaten several sectors: food security, scarcity of access to water resources, declining productivity of natural resources, loss of biodiversity, declining health, and further land degradation. Africa and, more particularly, developing countries are not on the side-lines of these disturbances since they are even the most susceptible to weather alteration (Amougou and Batha, 2014) because of the numerous stressors they encounter, including their low ability to expect extreme events and their geographical location in intertropical zones (Reid and Vogel 2006). Following the same line, Ronco *et al.* (2023) pointed out that the susceptibility to weather-related events is highest in developing countries, primarily attributed to changes in population.

With a universal temperature increase of 1.7°C, 1.2–70 million Africans could suffer from iron deficiency, 188 million from vitamin A insufficiencies, and 285 million from vitamin B12 deficiency (IPCC, 2022). Climate change has reduced African agriculture productivity by 34% since 1961 (IPCC, 2022). The change has caused a 5.8% decrease in maize and a 2.3% decline in wheat yields in sub-Saharan Africa (IPCC, 2022).

Following the line, Connolly-Boutin and Smit (2016) examined the relationship between weather patterns and extreme events associated with climate change, food security, and livelihood in sub-Saharan Africa. They highlighted that numerous smallholder farmers have observed shifts in rainfall patterns, an amplified occurrence of droughts or floods, and temperature changes. These perceived changes have a significant influence on agricultural practices, thereby affecting their livelihood and food security.

Moreover, smallholder farmers in sub-Saharan Africa understand their food security differently because of climate change. According to Tunde (2011), smallholder farmers in Nigeria understand weather change as a considerable risk to their livelihoods and meal protection. They mentioned that alterations in rainfall patterns, increased temperature, and more common droughts resulted in lower crop yields and a higher incidence of pests and illnesses. A similar point was raised by Subedi et al. (2023), Rezvi et al. (2023), Tazeem et al. (2023), Suresh et al. (2024) and Shinde et al. (2024). The farmers additionally point out a decline in soil fertility due to erosion and nutrient depletion, which further reduces their agricultural productivity. Juana et al. (2013) explored farmers' beliefs about the weather trade's impact on crop yields, farm animal manufacturing, and earnings within the location. They underlined that many smallholder farmers perceive adverse effects on their agricultural activities because of climate change. The investigation revealed reduced crop yields, increased pest infestations, reduced cattle productivity, and decreased profits because of changing climatic conditions, affecting their livelihood, and inflicting a lack of confidence. According to Bewket (2012), changes in weather patterns significantly affect the local livelihoods of smallholder farmers in Ethiopia, including a decline in seasons, increased pests, and excessive weed infestations. Some farmers also declared an increase in the prevalence of livestock diseases.

In its new Assessment Report 6, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change warns that if international greenhouse gasoline emissions are not cut through 1/2 by way of the end of the century, temperatures will exceed 1.5°C and a couple of 2°C above pre-industrial ranges at the beginning of the 21st century. Similarly, most of Africa will experience yield discounts for staple crops over the next two decades because of global warming above 2°C (IPCC, 2022). The forthcoming heating will adversely affect African food systems because of rapid emergent seasons and amplified water pressure (IPCC, 2022). Temperatures above certain limits impair the ability of crops to produce healthy seeds and fruits (Porter and Semenov, 2005). As the African Development Bank (AfDB) predicted in 2012, more than 20% of Africa's population could be at risk of famine by 2050. Climate change and intense weather occurrences will trigger infectious diseases in populations; crop profits could fall by 90% by 2100, with small farmers hit the hardest. According to Sonwa et al. (2019), this can have a vast and profound effect on the socioeconomic reputation of the population. Noort et al. (2022) introduced the idea that weather trade will reduce crop production, specifically for staple plants crucial for food safety in sub-Saharan Africa, together with maize, wheat, and rice.

In addition, weather variability will increase the demand for food insecurity, specifically among girls and kids. According to FAO (2018), women and children in sub-Saharan Africa are extra susceptible to famine and malnutrition due to the fact they do not have things like land, a credit score, or schooling. Climate change will exacerbate this pattern by decreasing agricultural production and increasing food expenses. Due to growing droughts and rising temperatures, 135 million humans globally are food insecure, and nearly half (73 million) are Africans (IPCC, 2022). The world has an enormous hunger and malnutrition crisis (WFP, 2023). According to the World Food Programme (WFP) estimates, over 345 million people will suffer from food insecurity in 2023 in the 79 countries where it operates and for which data is available (WFP, 2023). Compared with the pre-COVID-19 pandemic, this represents a surprising increase of 200 million people (WFP, 2023). The FAOSTAT (2022) showed that the global prevalence of undernourishment (PoU) has been on a downward trend for decades. However, under the shadow of the COVID-19 pandemic, PoU increased significantly between 2019 and 2020 and rose slowly from 2020 until 2021 (FAOSTAT, 2022) (see Figure 4).

PREVALENCE OF UNDERNOURISHMENT BY REGION

Figure 4: Prevalence of undernourishment by region

Source: FAOSTAT, 2022. A suite of Food Security Indicators. World food and agriculture. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/3/cc2211en/online/cc2211en.html> (Accessed: 03 March 2023).

Worldwide, approximately 10% of the population will suffer from hunger in 2021, compared to 9.3% in 2020 and 8% in 2019 (FAOSTAT, 2022). There is great concern about how the situation has developed in Africa, where poverty rates increased by 2.8% between 2019 and 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2022).

Compared with 2019, Africa’s undernutrition rate increased by 22%, or 51 million people, in 2021. In addition, this rate has increased by 42% since 2000.

Approximately 11.7% of the world’s population (924 million people) experienced severe food insecurity in 2021, according to the Food Insecurity Experience Scale 2021 (FIES). A measure of moderate or severe food insecurity, one of the official Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), provides additional information about people who do not have regular access to nutritious, sufficient food, regardless of whether they are hungry (FAO STAT, 2022). Africans experienced the highest food insecurity rate of any region in 2021, as shown in Figure 5 (FAO STAT, 2022).

Figure 5 : Levels of food insecurity based on the scale of food insecurity experienced in the region.

Source: FAOSTAT, (2022) World food and agriculture. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/3/cc2211en/online/cc2211en.html> (Accessed: 03 March 2023).

1.2 Problem Statement

The Millennium Development Goals adopted by the United Nations in September 2000 have significantly improved livelihoods worldwide (Gashu, Demment and Stoecker, 2019; Popkin and Ng, 2021; Aziz and Moniruzzaman, 2023). However, climate change has reversed that progress and caused developing countries to slow the pace of improving nutrition (Ingutia, 2021; Quibria, 2022). Because of the UN Sustainable Development Summit, which occurred in September 2015, the UN developed the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which includes 17 SDGs (Shulla and Leal, 2023). Its objectives include tackling poverty, disparity, global warming, ecological mortification, goodwill, and integrity. Following adopting the SDGs, early efforts produced positive results (Nishitani *et al.*, 2021; Agrawal *et al.*, 2022). The progress was fragile and too slow most times, as is observed now (Gulseven *et al.*, 2020). Over the past three years, numerous events, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, the ongoing insecurity in Ukraine, and the continuous impact of climate change, have negatively impacted the country’s progress (Gulseven *et al.*, 2020; Ingutia, 2021).

Globally, food prices remain higher than between 2015 and 2019, and hunger levels have returned to levels last seen in 2005 (Pawar, 2023). The United Nations Report 2023 stated that 589 million people suffered from hunger in 2015.

This number will rise to 768 million in 2021 because of the pandemic, conflict, climate change, and growing inequalities. According to the IPCC 2022 requirement for policy, global warming will undermine food safety and vitamins, particularly in developing regions. Moreover, the report revealed that an upward thrust in sea level and drought, heatwaves, and floods might pose a moderate to high danger to food security (high confidence) between 1.5°C and 2°C in international warming. The UN Report 2023 also sustained that, consistent with projections, about 670 million (8%) of the world's population will face malnutrition by 2030, and Sub-Saharan Africa could be the most concerned.

According to Ahmad et al. (2023), some studies have gaps on the influence of weather alteration on the farming sector in Africa because of a lack of comprehensive and lengthy-term information on past and present climate situations in Africa, which can serve as a stable foundation for research on agriculture. Furthermore, Ahmad et al. (2021) argues that researchers' potential to perform in-depth analyses and expect future effects is restrained. Most of the current research predominantly focuses on the direct effect of weather alternates on crops and their yields (Abdisa, Diga and Tolessa, 2022; Gul *et al.*, 2022; Anupong *et al.*, 2022; Cedric *et al.*, 2022; Alexandridis *et al.*, 2023; Farooq *et al.*, 2023; Abdi, Warsame and Sheik-Ali, 2023). Nonetheless, it is essential not to forget other interrelated elements holistically, together with socio-financial influences, irrigation structures, and agricultural practices. Africa experiences massive weather variability, contributing to its diversity (Mawren *et al.*, 2023). Studies on climate change's impact on African agriculture are limited due to their regional focus (Le Mouël *et al.*, 2023). Comparative studies across different regions are essential for a comprehensive understanding. Call et al. (2019) argue that future studies must predict the effects of weather trade on the agricultural area over the long term. The approach enables policymakers and farmers to proactively mitigate disruption and minimise potential losses through strategic adaptation. Farmers and stakeholders in agriculture need to be educated on climate change to make informed decisions. To increase knowledge, it is essential to communicate research findings in a way that is accessible and relevant. Regarding inequality, Azong et al. (2021) stated that different cultural and inheritance practices in communities enhance women's vulnerability.

Numerous sub-Saharan countries, like Cameroon, are highly exposed to the change in weather patterns. The main livelihood activity practised in Cameroon in a remote setting is agriculture, which is rain-fed (Molua, 2006; Bruckmann *et al.*, 2022; Ntali, Lyimo and Dakyaga, 2023), employs approximately 42.6 percent of the total population (World Bank, 2021) and contributes 16.98 percent to GDP (World Bank, 2022). Households that actively live from agriculture in Cameroon live in rural areas, and farming is their main activity, which helps for subsistence and commercial purposes (Muluh, Kimengsi and Azibo, 2019).

Determinants like agro-infrastructure, poverty, the weakness of social security, and land degradation expose agricultural practices to a considerable challenge (Nyantakyi-Frimpong, 2020). Seasonal food availability is also highly compromised because it heavily depends on rainfall distribution (Techoro, 2013).

The significant causes of food insecurity and malnutrition in Cameroon are highly attributed to the vulnerability of agriculture to climate change (Chabejong, 2016; Mbuli, Fonjong and Fletcher, 2021), although access to appropriate, safe, and wholesome food is fundamental for human health and well-being (Savoie-Roskos *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, adequate nutrition is essential for a robust immune system's growth and development (Trichet, 2010; Patil *et al.*, 2021; Munteanu and Schwartz, 2022). Mbuli, Fonjong and Fletcher (2021) argue that socioeconomic inequalities also contribute to food insecurity.

A significant reason for this is its disproportionate impact on vulnerable groups, including low-income families, marginalised communities, and farmers in rural areas (Munteanu and Schwartz, 2022). Several factors restrict smallholder farmers' ability to afford and access adequate food, including limited access to productive assets and economic disparities (Mbuli, Fonjong and Fletcher, 2021). The National Adaptation Plan for Climate Change (2015) emphasises that because of demography expansion, extensive dependence on agriculture, declining farm size in its five agro-ecological zones, a recurrent decrease in food crop production in climate-risk-prone areas, and frequent occurrences of hydrometeorological hazards, Cameroon urgently needs an immediate response.

Research on climate change impacts on subsistence staple crops in Cameroon still needs to be explored, while a little focus is on commercial crops like coffee and cacao (Techoro, 2013). Partially assessed climatic change impacts rarely provide insight into the local farmers' level of awareness and how they are coping with the change (Techoro, 2013). Given that limited resources for adaptation favour the vulnerability of farming to climate extremes in a rural area, attention needs to be more oriented to smallholder farmers. Raising awareness of the issue is also alarming because only one-third of teachers in 2021 could effectively explain climate change's impacts, despite 95% of teachers recognising the importance of this lesson. The United Nations Report 2023 mentioned that greenhouse gas emissions continue to rise according to real-time data from 2022. The level of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere increased between 2020 and 2021 at a rate that exceeded the average annual growth rate over the last decade and is already 149% higher than pre-industrial levels instead of decreasing as allowed by the target to limit global warming. A climate catastrophe is on the horizon, but current actions and plans to deal with it are insufficient (Baer *et al.*, 2023). Deficiencies and inaction result in heatwaves, droughts, floods, wildfires, sea-level rise, and famine (Agache *et al.*, 2022). To eradicate hunger by 2030, it is urgently and intensively necessary to invest in sustainable agricultural practices and ensure food security (Majedul, 2022; Agache *et al.*, 2022). Food security is alarming and needs to be addressed at all levels of society (Agache *et al.*, 2022).

There is a great need to utilise the best scientific approach to bring the issue from the vulnerable to the top so it will be better known, and the best action can be taken to solve the threat. Also, to reach zero hunger by 2030, food security needs to tackle the most vulnerable groups, such as farmers in rural areas in developing countries. Similarly, climate action needs to be addressed rationally in urban and rural areas, particularly for farmers who are more impacted by the threat.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

This study primarily examines and evaluates climate change's consequences on the food security of smallholder farmers in the Kong-Khi department of western Cameroon.

The specific objectives of the research were to:

- a) Investigate the occurrence of changes in weather patterns in the study area and their influence on staple foods.
- b) Assess the current state of the impact of climate change on food availability, accessibility, and utilisation among smallholder farmers.
- c) Explore smallholder farmers' adaptation strategies and the challenges they face.

1.4 Research Questions and Hypothesis

1.4.1 Research Questions

The overall research question is: How is climate change impacting smallholders' food security in the Department of Koung-Khi, and which responses are they deploying to improve their food security?

In addition, the thesis intends to explore the following research questions:

Q1 How are the changes in weather patterns occurring in the study area?

Q2 What is the impact of climate change on food availability, accessibility, and utilisation among smallholder farmers?

Q3 How are smallholder farmers responding to changes in climate conditions and which challenges do they currently face in their efforts to adapt?

1.4.2 Research Hypothesis

This study assesses the hypothesis that climate change negatively influences food production in the Koung-Khi department and reduces food availability among smallholder farmers.

1.5 Rationale of the Study: Why Does Food Security Matter?

Climate change has a cross-cutting effect on several SDGs and addressing its impact on food security contributes to achieving these broader sustainable development targets (Sindhu *et al.*, 2023; Dube and Shumba, 2023). According to IPCC (2022), the actual process of reducing greenhouse gases could mitigate climate change and limit the risks exposed. Climate change disproportionately affects vulnerable populations, worsening food insecurity and inequalities (Nyiwul, 2021).

The study of food security and climate change aligns with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) set by the United Nations (Egberi, 2023). Specifically, SDG 2 calls for ending hunger, improving food security, and promoting sustainable agriculture (Egberi, 2023).

Figure 6: Disaster profile in Cameroon

Source: Bang, H.N. A gap analysis of the legislative, policy, institutional and crises management framework for disaster risk management in Cameroon. *Prog. Disaster Sci.* 2021, 11, 100190. (Accessed: on 21 May 2024)

Figure 6 above, from Bang 2021, addressed hazards and disasters in Cameroon, focusing on geological hazards like volcanic eruptions, radiation emissions, and earthquakes and hydrometeorological hazards like floods, storms, mudslides, and landslides.

The susceptibility of the ten regions of Cameroon to climate risks and disasters is meaningful (Bang, 2021) because the region's sensitivity to climate is characterised by its overdependence on rain-fed agriculture (Techoro, 2013) and any decrease in yield because of unfavourable climate conditions can pose a threat to food security and hunger (Techoro, 2013; Lipper *et al.*, 2017).

The western region is among the country's most vulnerable to climate change, and concerns need to be more oriented because it is the "breadbasket" of the Central African sub-region and Cameroon (Yaouba and Dieudonné, 2022). Farmers in the western highlands rely heavily on subsistence farming for income and employment (Gur *et al.*, 2015). Awazi *et al.* (2021) argue that all dimensions of food security are affected by climate change in all five agro-ecological zones of Cameroon, and adaptation and mitigation measures to counter the threat are likely to differ across zones (Tangka, Merlain and Rudolph, 2022). As a matter of fact, Yaouba and Dieudonné (2022) noticed that smallholder farmers have lost their crops because of extreme climate change impacts, such as severe flash floods in the mono-modal rainfall agro-ecological zone and landslides in the hills and mountains of the Western Highlands, while drought and heatwave fluctuations have resulted in crop loss for farmers in the Sudano-Sahelien agro-ecological zone. It is imperative to regularly investigate the situation of food security in Cameroon (Chimi *et al.*, 2022).

Since maize, beans, and potatoes have been widely cultivated and consumed in the western region of Cameroon, the researcher chose these crops as a sample for the study. Smallholder farmers in the western highlands cannot master and cope with climate variability (Gur *et al.*, 2015). Consequently, this affects coping strategies, crop production, supply and demand, and the livelihoods of smallholder farmers within the locality (Gur *et al.*, 2015). Investigating the relationship between food security and climate change enables the development of effective acclimatisation approaches (Mutengwa, Mnkeni and Kondwakwenda, 2023). Modest literature has examined food security under climate change from the perspective of the local communities in the Western Highlands agro-ecological zones. For instance, Tume, Kimengsi and Fogwe (2019) evaluate indigenous farmers' ability to read weather signs to plan their daily and seasonal farming productivity. Moreover, Zama, Lan, and Zama (2021) examine the factors controlling farmers' decisions on climate change and their effects on farm production. Similarly, the impacts of weather alteration and response strategies of small-scale potato farmers were examined (Chiankam, 2022).

Nevertheless, there is a need for more attention towards the response and adaptation of subsistence farming populations to climate-related effects on staple crops in the department of Koung-Khi. A key goal of this study is to bridge this gap between scholarly literature and practical application. The state-of-the-art scientific knowledge on the impacts of environmental alteration on food security is increasing, and smallholder farmers' practical experiences in responding to its adaptation are needed. There is a need to exploit this knowledge gap. Enabling smallholder farmers to acclimate to the influences of weather change on staple crops requires giving them access to essential knowledge, information, and skills.

The strategies involve developing modest ways of sharing innovations, knowledge, and skills with smallholder farmers to get used to the technologies that enable adaptation and mitigation. This study will then cover this knowledge gap. The approach supports the Cameroon Vision 2035, stated by the government, which aims to tackle climate change as a critical regional strategy. Vision 2035 outlines Cameroon's development goals. Aim to minimise poverty.

It was prepared by the Ministry of Economy, Planning, and Regional Development. Vision 2035 recognizes climate change as a major challenge to Cameroon's economy. The document prioritizes reducing greenhouse gases as a key strategy for Cameroon to tackle climate change. Cameroon's government aims for high growth while achieving Millennium Development Goals. Phase one (2010-2019) of Vision 2035's schedule includes drafting and implementing major environmental policies to combat climate change. Phase two (2020-2027) includes climate change control as an objective. Actions include protecting forests, fighting desert encroachment, and promoting regional projects. Additionally, broadening knowledge and comprehension of the cultural dimension of adapting to climate change in diverse local contexts is essential. Therefore, it is beneficial and vital to cover this gap by first investigating and seeing how prepared smallholder farmers are to gain the new competency.

Moreover, further research gaps indicate the need to incorporate new insight into adaptation and mitigation processes and a new understanding of the need to incorporate present and future climate risks into policymaking. By combining their knowledge and perception of climate change, farmers can add to decision-making related to climate change management and economics (Lipper *et al.*, 2017; Singh, Anand, and Khan, 2018). Considering the crucial economic, social, and environmental threats plaguing the world, small-scale farmers must be empowered for their future livelihoods and well-being (Karki, 2020).

Value-added support for weather variability and adjustment concerns heightens farmers' ability to implement adaptation practices to combat climate change (Owen, 2020; Aryal *et al.*, 2020). Hence, agricultural practices in the subsistence sector could take advantage of the weather to gather, predict, and decide based on weather patterns. We expect the results to provide a stimulus for developing and implementing appropriate and effective policies and strategies for adaptation in developing countries (Ndaki, 2014). The updated status of food security in rural areas may guide the monitoring of the progress of the SDG to reach zero hunger in 2030. Also, this helps to evaluate challenges and opportunities regarding food security actions and policies aimed at reaching zero hunger in 2030. Food security and weather trade research are vital because of their profound implications for human health, environmental sustainability, socioeconomic fairness, international governance, and the Sustainable Development Goals.

This research uses surveys, focus group discussions, and key informant interviews to evaluate the effect of weather variability on the food security of smallholder farmers inside the Koung-Khi department.

Additionally, the researcher compared empirical information on crop yield variability and weather trade with the results.

Worldwide, millions of human beings are stricken by food security issues (UNICEF, 2021). Human survival and well-being rely on food protection (Goffe et al., 2021). A UN Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) 2020 file reported that over 690 million humans worldwide will be afflicted by starvation. In evaluation, billions of humans lack important micronutrients along with iron, vitamin A, and iodine.

Food insecurity results include malnutrition, stunted growth, and increased susceptibility to disease. Moreover, food insecurity has monetary implications. According to the World Bank (2021), food insecurity can lead to a decreased economic boom, increased healthcare costs, and reduced productivity. The observer estimates that malnutrition alone results in a lack of productivity of \$3.5 trillion annually and expanded healthcare fees. Food insecurity has a widespread effect on communities. According to the FAO (2018), food insecurity can cause social instability and insecurity as well as displacement. Additionally, poverty and inequality can be intensified by food insecurity, especially in rural regions, where people and families rely upon agriculture as their primary means of income.

Moreover, food insecurity will have long-term effects on a child's development. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO) (2021), malnutrition in the early years can result in stunted growth, cognitive impairment, and reduced capacity to gain knowledge. Millions of people in the sector are concerned about food security. Efforts to achieve food security require a multifaceted perspective that inscribes the rationale of poverty and inequality, promotes sustainable agricultural practices, and invests in social safety networks (Stretesky and Defeyter, 2022). It is crucial to continue studying and implementing strategies to ensure food security for all individuals and communities.

1.6 Expected Contribution of Research to Knowledge

Climate change and food security will present complex challenges at their intersection, but research can help address them. Agricultural and environmental research should address multifaceted food security and climate change challenges. Research could significantly contribute to policymakers empowering farmers and building more substantial and resilient food systems to ensure that the food system is sustainable and resilient for the present and future generations. Besides disseminating expertise, constructing potential, and transferring generation to farmers, the outcomes of this research contribute to farmers' variations in climate exchange, productivity, and food security. The findings may offer government organisations, personal institutions, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and community-based organisations (CBOs) the tools to map out strategies for addressing adverse impacts at the local level, where communities are most affected. This study expands knowledge and understanding of the current literature regarding climate risk responses to achieve resilience in food security in a rural setting. It may enhance smallholder farmers' perceptions of environmental hazards and guide the promotion of rural stability for sustainable practices in achieving food security. The methodology applied to conduct this study will give a state-of-the-art status or condition of food security in the study area.

This updated food security status could be a resource for the government and national and international organisations to establish new or change existing agendas to enhance food security issues. The findings could also support and complement ongoing or future research on food security in rural settings. The result could benefit from monitoring governmental and private action on rural adaptation and mitigation actions to cope with the threat.

Moreover, the research findings could refresh the adaptation and mitigation actions undertaken by rural farmers to counteract climate change impacts on their food security.

For the scientific community, the findings of this research could cover specific, significant gaps in the topic and provide a new orientation or focus of interest. To increase public awareness among smallholder farmers about food security status and climate change adaptation in rural settings, the scientific publications generated should inspire academic research communities. The study's outcomes will have a consequential impact by enriching the knowledge base of the scientific community and facilitating improved capacity building. The potential of the research findings lies in their ability to capture the attention of smallholder farmers, thereby raising awareness about the significance of climate adaptation policy.

In this study, the findings would assist policymakers in developing appropriate legislation relating to climate change adaptation for subsistence rural rain-fed agriculture. Innovation and technology transfer can create a resilient and sustainable food system. Due to climate change, continuous research is crucial to ensuring food security, implementing adaptive measures, and developing effective strategies. Implementing research outcomes could ensure the resiliency of food systems, minimise productivity losses, and secure access to nutritious food for all by creating a world free of hunger by 2030, which is the aim of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 2.

1.7 Structure of the Thesis

Chapter 1 provides a comprehensive introduction to the topic by offering a detailed overview of its background. It clearly outlines the problem under investigation and the study's objectives. Additionally, the chapter presents the rationale behind the problem and the expected contribution to the existing body of knowledge. Chapter 2 delves into the country of Cameroon, offering a thorough understanding of its climate zones and the corresponding weather patterns that are prevalent in each zone. Besides that, the report also provides comprehensive and in-depth data regarding the rainfall and temperature fluctuations across the country. Furthermore, it highlights the numerous difficulties climate change poses for vital aspects such as water resources, human health, and livelihood.

In conclusion, this chapter sheds light on the expected patterns of climate change that Cameroon is likely to encounter in the coming years. The main objective of Chapter 3 is to provide a thorough and complete overview of the agricultural practices currently being implemented in Cameroon and highlight the significant challenges that the farming sector is facing because of climate change.

The document explains the different agroecological zones found within the country while also delving into the current state of food security in Cameroon.

Additionally, this chapter goes beyond a surface-level analysis and provides a detailed investigation into the food security situation in Cameroon, highlighting the numerous factors that contribute to its complexity. Furthermore, readers will gain a broad understanding of the impact of weather variation on food security in Cameroon through this chapter.

Chapter 4 provides a detailed account of the method employed, from the initial application submission to the ethical committee at the University of the West of Scotland to the subsequent data collection in the field.

It outlines the established criteria for participant selection and elaborates comprehensively on the data collection process. It sheds light on the rationale behind the chosen method and its application within the study context. Finally, this section explains how the data was analysed and presented coherently and informally. Chapter 5 presents the results of the qualitative investigation. It gives the content of focus group discussions and key informant interviews. This chapter presents information on indigenous knowledge of weather variability.

It also includes stakeholders' perceptions about climate change and food security in the Koung-khi department. It also explored adaptation strategies and challenges at the national and local levels.

The main purpose of Chapter 6 is to provide an overview of the survey results. An important aspect brought to attention in this report is the socio-demographic profile and farming information. This chapter aims to comprehensively examine smallholder farmers' awareness and perception of climate change, offering detailed insights and a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Changes in weather patterns and food crop production in the study area are also addressed in this chapter. In conclusion, the chapter sheds light on the profound understanding of smallholders' adaptation strategies to climate change, providing readers with valuable insights into their practices and techniques. The purpose of Chapter 7 in the research is to provide the study's main findings in alignment with the research objectives. This chapter presents evidence from primary research and supplementary sources that collectively enhance the comprehension of the research objectives. Chapter 8 presents an extensive analysis, highlighting the significant conclusions drawn from previous chapters. This includes an exploration of smallholder farmers' perceptions of climate change's impact on staple crops, their adoption of adaptation strategies, and the challenges faced within the Koung-khi department.

Furthermore, the chapter elucidates the conclusion derived from the study, the policy choices available for adaptation, and the roles played by different stakeholders in implementing these choices. The chapter provides recommendations for adaptation strategies and outlines future research paths.

2. Chapter Two: Climate Change in Cameroon

2.0. Introduction

Chapter 2 delves into the country of Cameroon, offering a thorough understanding of its climate zones and the corresponding weather patterns that are prevalent in each zone. Besides that, the chapter also provides comprehensive and in-depth content regarding the rainfall and temperature fluctuations across the country. Furthermore, it highlights the numerous difficulties that climate change poses for vital aspects such as water resources, human health, and livelihood. In conclusion, this chapter sheds light on the expected patterns of climate change that Cameroon is expected to encounter in the coming years.

2.1 Some Facts About the Country

The country's name originated from the term Rio dos Camarões (“River of Shrimp”), which Portuguese explorers of the 15th and 16th centuries gave to the Wouri River estuary. In addition, Camarões referred to the mountains that bordered the river. The English use of “the Cameroons” was restricted to the mountains until the late 19th century, with the estuary being called the Cameroons River or simply the Bay in the local area. The German protectorate of the entire territory corresponded to the current state; thus, the term Kamerun was extended in 1884. (Benneh and Delancey, 2023). Cameroon lies in Central Africa, between the Gulf of Guinea and Lake Chad, and has latitudes between 2° and 13° north and longitudes between 8° 30' and 16° 10' east. There is a coastline of 402 km alongside a land area of 475,650 km², with a population of over 27,914,536 million and a life expectancy of 60 years (World Bank, 2022). The triangle's maximum width from east to west is about 800 km, and its length from north to south is 1,400 km. Cameroon has ten administrative regions, as shown in Figure 7, that cover various ecological zones. Its borders include Congo, Gabon, Equatorial Guinea, and the Atlantic Ocean on the south; Nigeria on the west; Lake Chad on the north; and Chad and the Central African Republic on the east (Ako, Eyong and Nkeng, 2010; Djongyang, 2022). The two major cities, Douala, and Yaoundé are economic and political capitals, respectively. Among African countries, Cameroon has the ninth-largest linguistic diversity after Nigeria. With over 200 ethnic groups and a historical ethnic crossroads, Cameroon has excellent cultural diversity. The country is one of the most linguistically diverse countries in the world, with over 250 local languages spoken. Because of its geographical and cultural diversity (Localazy Hub, 2023), Cameroon is often called “Africa in miniature”. It has the highest urbanisation rate in Africa's western and central regions because of its racially diverse population (Yenshu, 2011). French (80%) and English (20%) are the principal administrative spoken languages.

Figure 7: Map of Cameroon.

Source: Bang, H.N., 2022. A concise appraisal of Cameroon’s hazard risk profile: multi-hazard inventories, causes, consequences and implications for disaster management. *Geo hazards*, 3(1), pp.55-87

Figure 8: Hydrographic map of Cameroon

Source: (PNACC, 2015)

Despite Cameroon’s population growth rate of 2.6% (World Bank, 2022), the poverty reduction rate has remained behind, resulting in an increase of 12.5% to 8.1 million poor people between 2007 and 2014, with 56% living in the northern region (World Bank, 2022). A high rate of inflation has been experienced in Cameroon since November 2021, primarily because of shortages and increases in food prices (bread, wheat, vegetables, meat), attributed to disruptions in the global value chain caused by the COVID-19 pandemic and the ongoing Ukraine-Russia conflict (World Bank, 2022). The Ukraine war has exacerbated inflation pressures and domestic structural vulnerabilities (World Bank, 2021).

2.2. Climate zones in Cameroon

Cameroon’s climate is determined by two types: the equatorial type in the southern parts and the tropical type in the northern parts, making it one of the most ecologically diverse countries in central Africa (Molua, 2006). The two types of climates are subdivided into four sub-climatic or ecological zones, as shown in Figure 9.

The Equatorial climates are composed of Guinean and Cameroonian (Monsoon) types, each with different characteristics.

2.2.1. The Equatorial Guinea Types

The Equatorial Guinea type is in the southern part of Cameroon, as in Figure 9. It extends from Kribi to the south of the Plateau, covering nearly one-third of the country (Techoro, 2013).

Four seasons are observed throughout the year: two rainy and two dry, with approximately 1500 to 2000mm of rain falling yearly at under 25 degrees Celsius as the average temperature (Techoro, 2013; Antonio-Nkondjio *et al.*, 2019). Four regions are within the forest domain: the littoral, centre, southwest, east, and south. A succession of vegetation, including mangroves, deep equatorial evergreen forests, and humid savannah, covers this region from the Atlantic coast to the border with the Central African Republic (Antonio-Nkondjio *et al.*, 2019).

2.2.1.1. The Equatorial Cameroonian (Monsoon) Type

The Equatorial Cameroonian (monsoon) type, located along the southwestern coast, extends down the Sanaga River's mouth (Techoro, 2013). There is a low-lying wet period of roughly eight months, throughout which substantial rains are ample, and a short dry season within this climate type (Techoro, 2013). Techoro (2013) states that Pamo *et al.* (2008) divide the Equatorial Cameroon type into two categories: maritime Cameroon and mountain Cameroon. The maritime Cameroon type stretches along the coastal region to the mouth of the Nyong River (Techoro, 2013), which receives an annual average rainfall between 2000 and 10,000 mm with a mean yearly temperature of 26°C and is characterised as the second wettest place on earth (Molua and Lambi, 2006; Ngwa *et al.*, 2016). The mountain Cameroon type, Mount Fako, the high humidity, the highlands over 1000 m above sea level, and the grasslands contribute to the predominant vegetation type (Techoro, 2013; Antonio-Nkondjio *et al.*, 2019). It is found throughout the Western Highlands and continues northwards until the tropical Sudan type replaces it. The tropical climates are composed of tropical and Sudano-Sahelien types with different characteristics.

2.2.2. The Tropical Climate Type

The tropical climate type is composed of humid tropical and Sahel climates. The humid tropical climate includes one dry and rainy season extended from about latitude 6 to 10 degrees. With a landscape above 1000 m in the Adamaoua region, a humid savannah dominates a moderate climate with one rainy season lasting over six months, resulting in an annual precipitation of 900 to 1500 mm (Antonio-Nkondjio *et al.*, 2019). In contrast, the dry season lasts three to four months, with approximately 21 degrees Celsius of the average temperature (Techoro, 2013).

2.2.2.1. The Sudano-Sahelien Type

As part of the Sahelian type, the Far North region experiences hot, dry weather with an annual rainfall of approximately 400 to 700 mm (Antonio-Nkondjio *et al.*, 2019) and an annual mean temperature of 28°C (Ngwa *et al.*, 2016). Despite continuing to have a long dry season, the Mandara Mountains are colder and more humid because of their altitude and temperature ranges, and dryness increases with low atmospheric humidity (Techoro, 2013). In the country's north, the climate is warm desert and semiarid; in the central part, tropical savanna; and in the south and along the coast, monsoon, and equatorial (Omondi, 2019).

North Cameroon has a hot, semiarid climate with an annual rainfall of approximately 760 mm, most occurring between mid-May and September (MINADER, 2023; Omondi, 2019). Rainfall in August averages 235 mm, making it both the wettest and coolest month (MINADER, 2023; Omondi, 2019).

Figure 9: The Four climate subzones of Cameroon
 Source Adopted from Molua and Lambi, 2006. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0005105.g001>. (Accessed:06.07.2023)

Figure 10: Monthly climatology of Min-Temperature, Mean-Temperature, Max Temperature, and precipitation from 1991 to 2020 in Cameroon
 Source: Climate knowledge portal World Bank, Available at: <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/cameroon/climate-data-historical>.(Accessed: 06. July 2023)

2.3. Rainfall and Temperature Variation

Cameroon’s temperatures fluctuate between 20°C and 28°C throughout the year because of its geographical position in the intertropical zone (Techoro, 2013). From south to north, temperatures rise; this may explain why the south becomes humid and evergreen while the north becomes hot and desert-like (Techoro, 2013). Furthermore, the heat increases as one enters the hinterland, further away from the sea (Techoro, 2013). Investigation of the Tendencies and Interannual Irregularity of Tremendous Precipitation Indicators over Cameroon by Vondou *et al.* (2021) shows that precipitation decreases northward, with the highest values around the coast of the Atlantic Ocean. The humid monsoon moves through the Sahel zone in the northern part of Cameroon and induces a peak rainfall period in August–September (Molua and Lambi, 2006).

The rainy season occurs between March and October, and its peak occurs in August and September when the average temperature is at its lowest, as shown in Figure 10 above. From November to February is the dry season in Cameroon, characterised by the highest temperatures on average (World Bank, 2023).

Figure 11: Observed Average Annual Mean-Temperature of Cameroon from 1991 to 2020. Source: Climate Knowledge Portal World Bank, Available at: <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/cameroon/climate-data-historical>. (Accessed: 06. July 2023).

Similarly, Molua (2006) observed a positive temperature trend while investigating the actual temperature and precipitation series for 1960-2000, while under the Standardised Precipitation Index (SPI), Ntali, Lyimo and Dakyaga (2023) observed that a rise in temperature and a reduction in rainfall over time have occurred in significant amounts. Floods made up 32.1%, and droughts made up 7.5% of the overall natural risks in Cameroon between 1980 and 2020. Droughts have been recurrent in recent years; for instance, the severe drought of 2013-2016, brought about by a chronic loss of rain throughout the rainy season, precipitated critical electricity shortages across the country (Vondou *et al.*, 2021). A climate change with increasing temperatures would positively or negatively impact water resources in northern Cameroon, including Adamawa, the North, and the Far North regions close to the Sahel region of Africa (Cheo, Voigt and Mbua, 2013). Figure 11 shows that the period between 1971 and 1981 witnessed drought in the country. This observation aligns with the drop in precipitation between 1971 and 1985 shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Observed Average Annual precipitation of Cameroon from 1991 to 2020. Source: Climate knowledge portal World Bank, Available at: <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/cameroon/climate-data-historical>.(Accessed: 06. July 2023).

2.4. Challenges Posed by Climate Change in Various Sectors

2.4.1. Water Resources

Cameroon has the second-highest hydropower potential in Central Africa after the Democratic Republic of the Congo (Nonki *et al.*, 2019). It is one of the wealthiest African countries in terms of water resources (Hedayati *et al.*, 2023). However, although the hydrographic network is dense, as seen in Figure 8, it is unevenly distributed over the territory, where 72% of the resources are in the southern part of the country (PNACC, 2015). The hydrographic network of Cameroon has five significant groups, as shown in Figure 8 (PNACC, 2015). The first group comprises the Sanaga basin and river, with tributaries like Djerem, Noun, Mbam, Lom, and Pangar. The second large group of hydrographic networks includes the coastal river basin with the Cross River, Mungo, Wouri, Dibamba, Nyong, Lokoundjé, Kienke, Lobé, and Ntem Rivers. The third large group of the hydrographic network comprises the Congo basin with the Sangha, Dja, Boumba, and Ngoko rivers and Kadei. The Niger basin, with the Benue River and the Katsina-Ala, Donga, Faro, Kébbi, Menchum, and Gordi Rivers, composed the fourth hydrographic network of the country. The fifth hydrographic network comprises the Lake Chad basin with the Chari and Logone rivers (Djongyang, 2022). The adverse consequences of weather alteration have negatively affected the accessibility and availability of water and water resources, particularly for farmers worldwide (Zoyem and Nfor, 2021). Due to rainfed agriculture and the dependence on water resources for hydroelectricity production, which accounts for more than 95% of Cameroon's electricity, water is recognised as the primary impediment to socioeconomic development in Cameroon (Nonki *et al.*, 2019). To better understand how rainfall patterns have fluctuated with the variation in water supply, Zoyem and Nfor (2021) analysed rainfall data from 1963 to 2018 and water supply data from 2012 to 2018 to examine how rainfall patterns have changed over time. They found that rainfall events in Bamenda fluctuate over time and space. Rainy days also decreased, from 204 in 1963 to 155 in 2018.

As a result, rainfall volumes and the length of the rainy season both decreased. A study by Nounkeu and Dharod (2020) examined water access among rural households in Cameroon’s West Region and found that access to water was limited, requiring many trips and long walking distances. Regarding water insecurity problems caused by climate change, Awazi (2022) surveyed market gardeners engaged in various irrigation practices. According to the findings, extreme weather events induce water insecurity, including prolonged droughts, scant and irregular rainfall events, intense sunshine, and rising temperatures among smallholder farmers in rural settings.

Furthermore, surveyed market gardeners reported that they had experienced water insecurity, which in many cases contributed to crop failure, which caused them financial hardships and seriously impacted their livelihoods. The conclusion reached by Awazi (2022) is that climate change has led to water insecurity, with market gardeners forced to practice different irrigation practices throughout the year to improve crop productivity and reduce recurrent crop failures. An assessment of climate-induced water challenges in southwest Cameroon by Fonjong and Zama (2023) reveals that climate change has adversely affected the ability of women to perform their multiple roles. They discovered that several water sources have disappeared due to drought, and others have decreased in volume. As a result of unpredictable rainfall and temperatures, water sources in Cameroon are disappearing, declining, or becoming unreliable, resulting in an increase in the household workload of women and a reduction in their socioeconomic productivity (Fonjong and Zama, 2023). A study by Ebodé in 2022 examined the historical precipitation patterns in Cameroon. The study analysed rainfall’s spatial and temporal variations on different time scales, including seasonal and annual. The findings showed that there had been a significant decrease in annual rainfall across other regions of Cameroon, with Pettitt’s test indicating this trend starting around the 1970s. The northern region of Cameroon experienced a decline in precipitation ranging from -5.4% in Adamawa to -7.4% inside the Far North. The western region decreased, from -7.5% within the Southwest to -12.5% in the West (Abode, 2022). The southern location of Cameroon recorded a decline ranging from - 4.3% within the east to -5.9% in the centre (Abode, 2022). The study also revealed that after the 1970s, the northern, western, and southern regions of Cameroon experienced a decrease in precipitation towards the south, southwest, and west, respectively (Abode, 2022).

Figure 13: Annual Evolution of Irrigated Agricultural Land Area (hectare) in Cameroon
Source: MINADER, 2022

Figure 13 presents the evolution of irrigated agricultural land areas from 2017 to 2020 in Cameroon.

2.4.2. Human Health

The effects of climate change on health could increase in Cameroon in the future, particularly during the hot season, due to the lack of protective and adaptive measures (Dapi *et al.*, 2010). In a study conducted in Cameroon's cities of Yaoundé and Douala by Dapi *et al.* (2010), it was observed that schoolchildren experienced headaches, fatigue, and feeling very hot when exposed to high indoor air temperatures during school hours. Moreover, according to Djamouko-Djonkam *et al.* (2019), temperature was among the factors that affected the distribution of *Anopheles gambiae* larvae in Yaoundé. In addition, Fudjumdjum (2019) evaluated the possible health issues caused by climate fluctuations on the well-being of residents of Bafoussam City in the western part of Cameroon. The findings indicate a rise in climate change-related health issues in Cameroon's western region. In addition, the investigation showed a correlation between increased temperatures and pulmonary diseases related to air pollution. It also established an upward drive in mortality and morbidity costs inside the region. The study additionally demonstrated that climate change has exacerbated the adverse interplay between vector-borne and waterborne diseases. In the same vein, Fosah *et al.* (2022) found a positive correlation between temperature, rainfall, and malaria distribution in Cameroon, according to their investigation of the effects of climate variables on malaria distribution. Following the same line, Nyasa *et al.* (2022) found that humidity, temperature, and rainfall significantly impact malaria incidence both inland and along the coast, while higher temperatures and lower rainfall significantly increase malaria cases. Humidity was the principal climatic variable that negatively influenced malaria cases. A study by Wantim *et al.* (2022) attempted to establish the prevalence trend of malaria, typhoid, and diarrheal disease. According to these findings, flooding impacts malaria, typhoid, and diarrheal disease burdens. Because of heavy rainfall, flooding is a significant factor in the spread of these diseases.

Fudjumdjum's (2019) investigation on the potential health issues due to climate change in the well-being of the Bafoussam people of western Cameroon can be compared to similar studies in other developing countries a facing comparable climate challenge. For example, studies in other sub-Saharan African countries such as Nigeria, Ghana and Kenya have similarly investigated the health effects of climate change. Studies in Nigeria identified climate change, such as increased temperature and rainfall irregularities, tropical diseases, infectious diseases such as malaria and respiratory problems due to dust pollution are the main causes of many cases (Agboola *et al.*, 2024). Similarly, research in Ghana has shown that climate extremes and rainfall variability are associated with water-borne diseases and food insecurity, significantly affecting both rural and urban populations (Amenyedzi *et al.*, 2024).

In East Africa, Kenya faces parallel challenges, with climate change and drought and floods hampering agricultural production, causing food shortages and malnutrition alongside extreme weather an increasing health concerns related to water quality and sanitation (Mushitsi et al., 2023). Comparing Fudjumdjum's findings with these studies reveals a common thread: climate variability in developing countries continues to have negative health consequences. These include greater susceptibility to infectious diseases, food, and water shortages, and exacerbating health disparities.

The local focus on cities such as Bafoussam in Cameroon is consistent with extensive research showing that cities in developing countries are particularly vulnerable to weather-related health challenges due to factors such as due to population, infrastructure shocks and lack of health facilities. Thus, Fudjumjum's work contributes to a growing body of evidence that emphasises the urgent need for targeted public health interventions and climate adaptation strategies in similarly affected areas in countries that now emphasise the progress. It also highlights the importance of local research to create context-specific policies and actions that can mitigate the health impacts of climate change.

2.4.3. Livelihood

The concept of livelihood comprises a set of capabilities, assets (both material and social), and activities necessary for sustaining life (Hebinck and Bourdillon, 2001). Human livelihood systems are susceptible to the effects of climate change and its associated stressors, particularly those of poor and vulnerable people (UNDP, 2017). As Duru et al. (2022) note, rural livelihoods in developing countries increasingly depend on natural resources for survival, making them more susceptible to climate change. Awazi, Quandt and Kimengsi (2023) explore how endogenous livelihood assets affect smallholder farmers' resilience to weather variation in the western region of Cameroon. The number and size of farms, participation in social groups, livestock ownership, and household income were the three most significant livelihood assets that affected farmers' resilience. Ntali and Lyimo (2022) evaluated households' livelihood vulnerabilities in Northern Cameroon's drought-prone region. The study found that the most significant drivers of livelihood vulnerability were food insecurity, livelihood strategies, and social networks.

Some Sustainable Development Goals, for instance, zero hunger, water accessibility, and poverty alleviation, were limited because of rain-fed agriculture and poor early drought warning information. In a study conducted by Dube and Phiri (2013) to understand how climate change affects the livelihood of rural communities, they found that decreasing precipitation and rising temperatures are resulting in more significant difficulty in farming, causing food insecurity. In a cross-tabulation analysis, Duru, Aro and Oladipo (2022) examined how climate change affects rural women's livelihoods in Nigeria. The findings show that a temperature rise led to a decline in agricultural output and increased rainfall contributed to the disease vector increase. Unfavourable weather contributed to flood-related property losses.

The conclusion reached by Duru, Aro and Oladipo (2022) is that food production has become increasingly challenging because of climate change. This results in food prices rising and limited access to food, increasing the risk of hunger.

Similarly, Keshavarz, Maleksaeidi and Karami (2017) showed drought as a recurring climate-driven hazard that impacts natural systems and agriculture, especially in rural areas. Mekonen, Berlie and Ferede (2020) also note that the lack of precipitation results in a water shortage for agriculture, negatively impacting agricultural production. Cameroon's rural livelihood relies significantly on agricultural activity, which supplies food and income. Because of their dependence on the natural surroundings for their livelihood, smallholder farmers in west Cameroon are at significant risk of the perils of climate change. A hassle associated with weather change is that it influences smallholder farmers' capability to earn a living through agriculture. Therefore, this goal is to look at how climate change affects the meal protection of smallholder farmers in rural settings in the west of Cameroon.

Figure 14: Impact of climate change in various sectors
Source: Author's computation.

2.4.4. Floods

Floods in Cameroon have emerged due to weather changes (Mfondoum et al., 2023). Since 2005, the African Development Bank (AfDB) and the Cameroonian government have been working to limit flooding and its impact on socio-economic situations (AfDB, 2022). Water control projects were appointed to improve stormwater drainage and reduce flood risk. These efforts targeted the mitigation of the outcomes of excessive climate events. In the face of urbanisation and climate change, flooding is also irritated via rapid urbanisation in many parts of Cameroon (Nsangou et al., 2022).

The expansion of urban areas leads to soil sealing, which limits water absorption and will increase runoff (Jokam et al., 2022). Climate change is likewise intensifying precipitation, increasing the chance of flooding mostly in urban areas.

2.4.5. Impact of Climate Exchange on Agricultural Infrastructure

The fundamental agricultural infrastructure incorporates road networks, irrigation technology, and post-harvest storage technology (Munyanyi, 2013). The investigation by Ako and Wanie (2022) on the challenges in rural-urban avenue transportation and coping mechanisms for food security in Cameroon found that rural-city roads in Maroua are dilapidated and insufficient, making motion hard, particularly at some stage in the rainy season. These challenges negatively affect the four dimensions of food security in Maroua. The same finding was made by De Abreu et al. (2022) while reviewing the impacts of climate change on road infrastructure. The authors additionally stated that transportation communities in rural settings were the most impacted by the threat. The erratic rainfall distribution and prolonged dry spell disruptions influence irrigation structures as water sources become scarcer and less predictable (Mulla *et al.*, 2023).

Cameroon's agricultural infrastructure closely relies on seasonal rainfall patterns. The effect of weather change on irrigation technology in Cameroon has been substantial in recent years (Nya *et al.*, 2023). The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) suggested that by 2022, almost 75% of irrigation infrastructure in Cameroon will be degraded or poorly maintained. However, climate change causes irregular rainfall distribution and delayed rainfall (Chisale *et al.*, 2023). Irregular rainfall and prolonged droughts affect irrigation, as water resources are scarce and unpredictable (Mulla *et al.*, 2023). It has been observed that water scarcity threatens irrigation in the highlands of Cameroon (Fonjong and Zama, 2023). Increasing global temperatures have resulted in frequent and severe droughts in Cameroon, affecting agriculture and food security (Ntali, Lyimo and Dakyaga, 2023). This raises the need for crop support with irrigation technology to grow and mitigate climate change impacts (Ntali, Lyimo and Dakyaga, 2023). However, the implementation of irrigation technology in Cameroon has been difficult due to various reasons, such as lack of funds, lack of technical knowledge and skills, and inadequate infrastructure (Ngwa *et al.*, 2023).

Changing climatic conditions affected the storage of various crops such as rice, fruits, and vegetables (Travičić *et al.*, 2023). In this regard, Karanth *et al.* (2023) stated that increased temperature and humidity accelerated microbial growth, resulting in crop contamination. A theoretical study of pesticide uses against pests by vegetable producers in Cameroon by Nkuh *et al.* (2023) found that farmers rely on expensive chemicals to conserve production, which is ineffective. The findings also show that unpredictable rainfall also affected crop drying, resulting in high humidity, which is unsuitable for storage.

Furthermore, Chiankem (2022) claimed that in many of Cameroon's rural settings, extreme climate conditions consisting of floods and storms have destroyed storage facilities, leaving smallholder farmers with no alternative but store their crops outdoors. This exposes their produce to pests, rodents, and birds, which feed on the plants, leading to further losses. The impact of climate change on post-harvest storage technologies has been devastating for farmers in Cameroon, especially those in rural areas (Chiankem, 2022). They lack access to modern storage facilities and rely on traditional methods, which are inadequate for the changing climate (Chiankem, 2022). A changing climate, with rising temperatures, irregular rainfall, and increased intense weather activity, has reduced agricultural productivity in Cameroon (Chimi et al., 2022). Bomdzele et al. (2021) found that the yield potential of important crops like maize and sorghum is already reduced by 7 to 12 percent in some communities. The effects of climate change have significant impacts on agricultural systems in Cameroon, especially the degradation and disruption of food production systems (Bomdzele et al., 2021). Consistent with the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO, 2022), in 2020, Cameroon will lose about 50,000 hectares of land due to soil erosion every year.

2.4.6. Inland Migration

Due to climate change, inland migration has become common in Cameroon (Yhaya et al., 2022). At the national level, people move from rural to urban areas, or there is a shift to other areas (Yhaya et al., 2022). Various factors commonly trigger this migration, such as food insecurity, loss of livestock, floods, or drought damage to crops and households (Yhaya et al., 2022). Drought in the region has affected agricultural production and decreased it, leading to food insecurity and poverty (Isa and Ntede, 2023). As a result, many people migrated from rural to urban in the country or even crossed borders to neighbouring countries such as Nigeria (Sambo et al., 2023). According to Isa and Ntede (2023), the impact of climate change on internal migration in Cameroon is essential because it created social, economic, and environmental challenges that put pressure on it, resulting in overcrowding and infrastructure problems. Furthermore, Sambo et al. (2023) added that it disrupted traditional social and cultural practices, resulting in social instability and tension.

2.5. Future Trends of Climate Change

According to the IPCC 2023 Summary for policymakers, every place is anticipated to enjoy concurrent and more than one modification in climatic impact drivers as worldwide warming progresses. Additionally, there may be an excessive possibility that compound heatwaves and droughts will become more common, including simultaneous events throughout more than one place. Increasing greenhouse gas (GHG) concentrations in Cameroon may enhance the temperature by 1.9 to 3.8 degrees Celsius by 2080, as shown in Figure 15, and the intensity of heavy precipitation occasions, as shown in Figure 16. Tamoffo et al. (2023) studied how extreme rainfall and temperature events may impact Cameroon's socioeconomic sectors.

Their findings showed that global warming could lead to an increase in consecutive dry days and a decrease in consecutive wet days. However, yearly rainfall is expected to rise because of more intense rainfall on specific days. Temperature-based indices also reveal a rise in hot days and a reduction in cold days annually, which will intensify with more significant radiative forcing. The authors concluded that these changes could negatively impact food security, heat-related illness, poverty, price rises, and market instability. According to climate projections, the number of sweltering days per year (with daily maximum temperature above 35 °C) is expected to increase significantly because of rising mean annual temperatures (Tomalka et al., 2022). This increase is exceptionally high in northern Cameroon, where sweltering days are already frequent and by 2080, the region could experience up to 310 hot days annually (Tomalka et al., 2022).

Figure 15: Air temperature projections for Cameroon for different GHG emissions scenarios

Source: Available at https://www.pik-potsdam.de/en/institute/departments/climate-resilience/projects/project-pages/agrica/giz_climate-risk-profile_cameroon_en_final_2022_21_07 Accessed 07.July 2023.

Figure 16: Heavy precipitation over Cameroon for different GHG emissions scenarios relative to 2000.

Source: Available at https://www.pik-potsdam.de/en/institute/departments/climate-resilience/projects/project-pages/agrica/giz_climate-risk-profile_cameroon_en_final_2022_21_07 Accessed 07.July 2023.

Access to safe water remains low for the populations of the Sudano-Sahelian zone (North region: 35.4% and Far North region: 37.8%). People in rural localities often get up early or journey long distances to access water. The shortage of rain hampers agricultural development in the area, leading to drought, food security, famine, and poverty. The changes in climate at a worldwide level directly affect the local stage, affecting the livelihoods of groups that depend upon agriculture, forestry, and fisheries (Gandharba, 2023). Global policies and agreements on climate change, consisting of the Paris Agreement, have sizable implications for local groups, as they often require adjustments in neighbourhood regulatory frameworks and practices (Campbell-Lendrum *et al.*, 2023).

It is essential to notice that even though developed countries have historically been the largest emitters of CO₂, growing nations are also contributing to the problem as they attempt to modernise their economies (Balsalobre-Lorente *et al.*, 2023). We are presently experiencing a median heating of 1.14°C above the pre-industrial level, and regulations have placed the arena on track for almost three °C of heating (Friel, 2023). Mitigating climate change means lowering greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. CO₂ emissions from the energy sector should no longer grow as they did in 2022 (IEA, 2021, cited in Friel, 2023). By 2050, two-thirds of the global energy supply needs to come from wind, solar, bioenergy, geothermal, and hydropower, and the delivery of fossil fuels must reduce to around a fifth. (IEA, 2021, cited in Friel, 2023).

The worldwide response to climate change is critical, and the urgency of action cannot be overstated. The consequences of a warming planet, if no longer addressed together, are considerable and extreme. The interconnected nature of climate trade makes it a sincere global undertaking that calls for a united front. The critical components of a worldwide reaction may be reflected in the following questions:

Q1 Are we safeguarding vulnerable communities? Because vulnerable communities, often least responsible for emissions, endure the brunt of climate influences, a global reaction is essential to ensure that coping and adaptation measures are in place to protect those most in danger.

Q2 Are we fostering international cooperation? Because climate variability requires global cooperation on a supreme scale, an international response includes collaboration in sharing know-how, technology, and assets to deal with this shared venture.

Q3 Are we aligning policies with climate objectives? Because a worldwide response necessitates aligning regulations across sectors with climate objectives. This includes transitioning to renewable electricity, sustainable land use, and resilient infrastructure.

Q4 Are we prioritising long-term sustainability over short-term gains? Because decisions made these days will shape the future, an international response prioritises long-term sustainability over short-term economic profits. It recognises the benefits of a sustainable and resilient future.

Despite increasing research on the influence of climate change on food security, the literature still needs to be filled with significant gaps, especially for smallholder farmers in rural Cameroon.

Addressing these differences is essential to developing effective transition strategies and programs tailored to the unique challenges faced by this vulnerable group.

Lack of local weather data and forecasts

One notable gap is the need for local climate data and assumptions for specific rural areas in Cameroon. Most existing studies are based on broad climate models that fail to capture microclimate variations in different agroecological zones. This lack of detailed climate data hampers the ability to accurately predict and address local effects of climate change on smallholder agricultural systems trying to capture and regional climate models must be developed.

Inadequate preservation of Indigenous knowledge and practices. Another necessary approach is the limited attention paid to the role of indigenous knowledge and traditional agricultural practices in climate adaptation. Smallholder farmers in Cameroon often use time-tested, culturally rooted practices that make them more stable to climate change. However, these behaviours often need to be more examined and undervalued in the scientific literature. Combining indigenous knowledge with contemporary scientific methods can lead to comprehensive and culturally sensitive adaptive strategies.

3. Chapter Three: Agriculture and Climate Change in Cameroon

3.0. Introduction

This chapter aims to present a comprehensive overview of Cameroon's agricultural practices and the challenges the agricultural sector faces because of climate change. It explains the various agroecological zones in the country and offers insights into the current food security status in Cameroon. Furthermore, this chapter provides an in-depth analysis of the food security situation in Cameroon and examines the various factors that influence it. Moreover, this chapter considers the impact of climate change on food security in Cameroon.

3.1. Agriculture in Cameroon

Cameroon has 6.16 million hectares of arable land, and in 2018, it produced more than half of the CEMAC sub-region's agricultural output, making it the region's breadbasket (FAO, 2021). As a source of food, income, and jobs in developing countries, agriculture significantly reduces poverty and maintains food stability (Godom, 2022). It mainly provides direct employment for farmers and indirect jobs for street vendors, or "Buyam salam" (Godom, 2022). According to the United Nations National Population Status (UNNPS) report (2021), "Buyam-salam" refers to commercial activity in Cameroon where actors buy food products and resell them in the marketplace. Urbanisation and precarious living conditions contribute to these activities' growth because Cameroonians cannot find formal employment, especially since the 1980s economic crisis (UNNPS, 2021). Numerous people, especially women with low education, can self-employ through that activity with modest financial capital (UNNPS, 2021). Moreover, agriculture significantly contributes to household food, providing food directly to the household, providing rural households with an income, and improving the trade balance by reducing food imports (Godom, 2022). Among the main crops are sweet bananas, plantains, cassava, potatoes, yam, taro, and cereals (rice, millet, and maize), most of which are produced for domestic consumption (IRAD, 2008; PNACC, 2015; AFSA, 2023; Godom, 2022). Industries need raw materials from agriculture to maintain sustainable economic growth (Godom, 2022). Food production, marketing, and small processing units are integral to this sector, leading to beneficial outcomes (Rahmani et al., 2022). Because of its diverse geography, Cameroon has five major agroecological zones corresponding to its five natural zones (AFSA, 2023). Each agroecological zone has specific bio-physical and climatic characteristics that favour cultivating specific crop types (PNACC, 2015). The zones include Sudano-Sahelian, Guinea Savannah, Western Highland, Bimodal, and Monomodal Rainfall Zones (IRAD, 2008; PNACC, 2015; AFSA, 2023).

Agriculture employs nearly 60% of the population and remains the predominant sector of the national economy in terms of its contribution to GDP (23%) and the knock-on effects on other sectors of activity (PNACC, 2015). The main cash crops are cocoa, coffee, tobacco, cotton, bananas, and pepper.

Figure 17: Agroecological Zone of Cameroon.
 Source: Institute for Agriculture Research for Development (IRAD), 2008

Figure 18 below shows the annual change in the proportion (%) of the cultivated agricultural land in Cameroon. The surface area of the land cultivated in Cameroon is increasing each year.

Figure 18: Surface of land cultivated in Cameroon
 Source: MINADER, 2022 (Annual Performance Reports, 2022). Available at <https://www.minader.cm>. Retrieved on 20.11.2023.

3.1.1. The Sudano-Sahelian Agroecological Zone

The Sudano-Sahelian Zone in the north, Savannah, has a semi-arid climate lying between 8°36" at 12°54" N latitude and 12°30" at 15°42" E longitude with rainfall ranging from 400 mm to 1200 mm per year. The zone has an average temperature of 28° C; during April, the maximum temperatures range between 40 and 45° C. A variety of crops are grown, including sorghum, cowpea, millet, maize, rice, market gardening, watermelons, onions, sesame, soybeans, vegetables, cotton, as well as fish, cattle, and small ruminants (IRAD, 2008; PNACC, 2015; AFSA, 2023).

3.1.2. The High Guinean Savannahs Agroecological Zone

The High Guinean Savannah Agroecological Zone lies near 5°42' to 8°36' North latitude and 11°24' to 14°36' East longitude (Vatsou et al., 2023) with vast elevations of 900 to 1500 metres and peaks that reach 1800 m. The climate in the zone is Sudanian and humid, with rainfall averages of 1500 mm per year and average monthly temperatures ranging from 20 to 26 degrees Celsius because of altitude. Plants and animals present in this region include peanuts, rice, maize, cassava, sweet potatoes, yams, cocoyam, beans, vegetables, coffee, poultry, cattle, small ruminants, and fish (IRAD,2008; PNACC, 2015; AFSA,2023).

3.1.3. The Western Highlands Agroecological Zone

The Western Highlands Agroecological Zone has an equatorial climate and is the 2nd most watered area of the country. It is between latitudes 4°54" and 6°36" north and longitudes 9°18" to 11°24" east. The relief includes the Bamoun plateau, with an altitude of 1240m; the Bamiléké plateau, with a height of 2740m; and the volcanic plateaus of Bamenda, at an altitude of 1800m (AFSA, 2023). The zone has a dry season lasting from mid-November to mid-March and a rainy season lasting from mid-March to mid-November with a low average temperature of 19°C and a single mode of heavy rainfall (1500 - 2000 mm) (PNACC, 2015; AFSA, 2023). The region produces maize, rice, cocoyam tubers, cassava, and cocoyam for marketing. It also produces palm oil, citrus fruit, Indonesian and Arabic coffee, tea, cocoa, spices, bananas, sweet potatoes, vegetables, cattle, fish, and small ruminants (IRAD, 2008; PNACC, 2015; AFSA, 2023).

3.1.4. The Monomodal Rainforest Agroecological Zone

The Monomodal Rainforest Agroecological Zone is between 2°6" and 6°12" North latitude and 8°48" and 10°30" East longitude and includes the highest summits on Mount Cameroon, which reaches 4095 m (AFSA, 2023). It experiences a humid and warm climate, like the equatorial type, with temperatures around 22°C. The region is among the wettest places in the world, receiving 11,000 mm of rainfall annually (AFSA, 2023). Furthermore, large export farms are growing coffee, cocoa, tea, bananas (sweet bananas and plantains), palm oil, rubber, fish, and small ruminants (PNACC, 2015). There is a large palm oil production basin in Cameroon in this area (IRAD, 2008; PNACC, 2015; AFSA, 2023).

3.1.5. The Bimodal Rainforest Agroecological Zone

The Bimodal Rainforest Agroecological Zone, with about 45,659 km², lies between latitudes 2°6" and 4°54"/5°48" north and longitudes 10°30" to 16°12" east (AFSA, 2023).

It is located mainly between 500- and 1000 meters altitude with temperatures above 25°C and rainfall of 1500-2000mm per year. The climate is of the "Guinean" type, characterised by two distinct wet seasons and a long agricultural calendar with staggered growing and harvesting (AFSA, 2023). Crops grown here include perennials (cocoa, Robusta coffee, fruit trees) and annual and multi-annual crops (plantain, sugarcane, maize, tobacco, vegetables, tubers) (IRAD, 2008; PNACC, 2015; AFSA, 2023). The region also has fish and small ruminants (IRAD, 2008; PNACC, 2015; AFSA, 2023).

Indicators	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Trends in the volume of exports of goods and products	9.11	-5.9	1.3	1.6	-8.0
Agriculture (%)					
Trends in exports in volume of goods and products of the	121.8	10.4	6.1	-12.2	-3.3
Food & Beverage Industries					
Trends in the volume of imports of goods and products	2.9	12.3	4.3	7.6	-6.8
Agriculture (%)					
Trends in the volume of imports of goods and products of the	1.8	5.0	-2.8	8.4	-5.8
Food & Beverage Industries (%)					
Evolution of imports in volume of fertilizer goods (in thousands of	203.4	209.8
Tones)					
Evolution of imports in volume of insecticide goods. Fungicides; herbicides (in thousands of tonnes)	19.3	26.3
Trends in imports of agricultural products (%)	2.9	14.9	-5.4	15.6	...

Table 1: Some performance indicators
Sources: MINADER; MINFI (2021)

Table 1 presents a set of indicators relating to the evolution of production volumes and trade volumes of some of the leading industrial and export crops in Cameroon, as well as the volumes traded of some agricultural goods and agricultural inputs. Population growth and food demand are major factors in food security. Areas under cultivation of some crops increased significantly over time. Agriculture's vulnerability to climate change impacts is compounded by only 30% of agricultural land being irrigated.

Most of the farm production in Cameroon is either subsistence or low-cost (Yaouba and Dieudonné, 2022). Only 10% of its production is sold on the international market.

Cameroon's agriculture sector, particularly in rural areas, remains the primary means of livelihood for its population despite the country's economy diversifying (Yaouba and Dieudonné, 2022). Food products are exported, such as cocoa beans, coca products, and bananas (MINADER, 2023). The primary staple crops are maize, sorghum, groundnut, and cassava (MINADER, 2023). The IPCC (2023) report estimates that by 2050, the overall temperature in Cameroon will increase by 1.5°C, resulting in a 30% reduction in crop yields. The report notes that high temperatures can cause heat stress in flora, adversely affecting their growth and development.

Additionally, the report mentioned that modifications in rainfall patterns ought to lead to water shortages, which could affect crop increases and decrease yields. The Cameroon's Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development reviews that rural production in Cameroon has been declining, with a substantial decrease in crop yields because of weather exchange (MINADER, 2023). The Report from MINADER, 2023 also highlights that over 2 million households within the country face food insecurity due to the changing climate.

A study by the African Development Bank (AfDB) in 2023 observed that climate change is already affecting agriculture in Cameroon. The investigation revealed a decline in crop yields due to changes in rainfall, temperature, and pests. The observer also recognised that farmers adapt to those modifications by changing planting dates, using drought-resistant crops, and converting irrigation practices. The expansion of agricultural activity in Cameroon, as reported by MINEPPDED (2023), has been identified as a significant cause of deforestation. A study by Chia et al. (2013) found that climate change reduces crop production and encourages agricultural expansion.

Furthermore, the World Bank (2023) report suggested that the impact of climate change on agriculture in Cameroon extends past crop yield. The report observed that weather change also affects soil fertility, leading to a decline in the nutritional value of plants. Water scarcity also affects livestock manufacturing, which is an extensive source of income for many farmers in Cameroon.

According to a study by Mbah et al. (2023), rising temperatures and modifications in rainfall patterns have decreased crop yields and increased pest infestations within the country. The author claims that maize, a staple crop in Cameroon, is predisposed to the effects of weather variability. In addition, the study notes that climate change has brought about modifications to the timing of planting and harvesting seasons, which have affected the availability of food and earnings for farmers. This has additionally contributed to elevated food fees and food insecurity within the country.

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted food security in Cameroon, exacerbating existing vulnerabilities and challenges (Foka-Nkwenti et al., 2020).

The lockdown and travel restrictions implemented to prevent the spread of the coronavirus disrupted agricultural activities, including production, distribution, and access to markets, affecting the income and livelihoods of many smallholder farmers reduced, and increasing food insecurity in the sensitive population (Suh et al., 2023).

In addition, disruptions in the global supply chain have increased the scarcity and prices of essential staple food, exacerbating food insecurity and malnutrition in the country again (Laborde et al., 2020). Moreover, the economic consequences of the pandemic, including job losses and reduced incomes, have exacerbated the challenges of food insecurity in Cameroon (Suh et al., 2023). Vulnerable populations, including women, children, and rural communities in addition, have been disproportionately affected by the socioeconomic consequences of COVID-19 (Alevizos et al., 2023). The epidemic has highlighted the need to address structural inequalities and build resilience in the food system to reduce the impact of future crises on food security in Cameroon and other vulnerable areas (Suh et al., 2023).

Similarly, Chop *et al.* (2022) investigated the impact of climate change on maize production in the Northwest Region of Cameroon. Another investigation by the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI) in 2023 observed that climate change is affecting the manufacturing of food products in Cameroon, leading to a decline in maize yield. Moreover, Tchuete et al. (2023) highlight the effect of climate change on cassava production in Cameroon and discover that the changing weather patterns have brought about a decline in cassava yield by as much as 30% in some areas of the country. Similar observations were made by Ndjouenkeu *et al.* (2021) in an investigation in Cameroon and Nigeria, the neighbouring countries. The authors recommended adopting climate-clever agricultural practices to mitigate the effect of weather exchange on cassava production.

3.2. Food Security Status in Cameroon

The progress towards reaching Sustainable Development Goal 2 will be compromised due to the accelerated frequency of conflicts, climate extremes, economic slowdowns, downturns, and increasing unaffordability of dietary food (FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO, 2023). According to facts from the National Survey on Food and Nutrition Security in Cameroon (ENSAN), the food insecurity situation in Cameroon has deteriorated from 12.8% in 2019 to 20.4% in 2020. It also results in approximately 2.7 million humans (or 10% of the entire population) being acutely food insecure (ENSAN, 2021). The value added to the agricultural sector, which accounted for 44% of GDP in 2004, declined considerably to 17% in 2021 (World Bank, 2022). Apart from climate change, the instability of food security status in Cameroon is also attributed to ongoing conflicts and socio-political insecurity, resulting in high food prices and flooding that has led to population displacement and crop damage. The situation in the western part of the country is further exacerbated by the non-state armed groups' attacks, which have resulted in over 2,300 internally displaced people (IDPs).

It is consequently vital that measures are taken to cope with the underlying causes of the battle and socio-political instability to ensure long-term answers to the food security issues. The World Food Programme Report 2022 stated that 15.1% of families nationwide have insignificant food consumption scores.

Additionally, 53 percent of households had an acceptable food consumption score as opposed to 37 percent with borderline and 10 percent with poor consumption, making them vulnerable to negative coping strategies such as reductions in number, portion size, and quality of meals (WFP, 2023). As shown in the February 2021 Smart survey, chronic malnutrition continues to be a problem among children under five (WFP, 2023), with 29 percent of children classified as stunted (DHS, 2018). In this context, intelligent surveys are digital surveys that can be administered through computers, such as email or web-based platforms, designed to ensure the accuracy of survey findings. Stunting affects 42 percent of the poorest quintile and 38 percent of the rural population (WFP, 2023). Cameroon continues to suffer micronutrient deficiencies, particularly among children under five and pregnant women (WFP, 2023). There is an increase in procurement costs associated with commodities such as imported rice, cooking oil, fish, and milk, which result in high prices for these products (WFP, 2022).

The causes of malnutrition in Cameroon include general food insecurity, limited dietary diversity, and gender-related issues (WFP, 2022). In addition, climate change contributed to decreased agricultural production, which threatens food security (Epule et al., 2021). Tume et al. (2020) propose evaluating sound policy alternatives to address food security concerns in response to declining crop production and rainfall patterns. Based on the analysis conducted by Cadre Harmonisé (CH) in March 2023, a significant proportion of the population, estimated at 2.4 million, is currently experiencing severe food insecurity, categorised as CH Phase 3 (Crisis) or higher, between March and May 2023. That represents 11 percent of the population facing acute food insecurity. In assumption, the CH evaluation shows that the present-day situation requires instant interest and action from all stakeholders to mitigate the disaster's effects and ensure that the affected population is provided with assistance. Figures 19 and 20 depict the food security classification in Africa, Cameroon, and the Koung-Khi department. Figure 20 illustrates that much of Cameroon's population faces stressful food security conditions because of economic, security, and environmental hardships. The food and nutrition status in the Western region and the Koung-Khi department is stressed, as shown in Figure 20 below. Given the severity of the food security crisis in Africa, it's of extreme significance that each stakeholder is collectively involved in it. Immediate action is necessary to ensure the affected population receives the needed assistance. By operating collectively, we will mitigate the effects of the disaster and ensure that food security is restored for all.

Figure 19: Classification of food and nutrition status in Africa and Cameroon
 Source: The Cadre Harmonisé (CH)-Integrated Food Security Phase Classification (IPC)
 Available at <https://www.ipcinfo.org/ch/>. (Accessed in July.2023).

Figure 20: Classification of food and nutrition status in the department of Koung-Khi
 Source: The Cadre Harmonisé (CH)-Integrated Food Security Phase Classification (IPC)
 Available at <https://www.ipcinfo.org/ch/>. (Accessed in July.2023).

3.3. Climate Change on Food Security in Cameroon

The world is increasingly involved in climate change, which has substantial implications for food safety (Molotoks, Smith and Dawson, 2020). Several sub-Saharan African countries, including Cameroon, are vulnerable to the consequences of climate change for the safety of their food (Yaouba and Dieudonné, 2022). Fonjong and Zama (2023) report that climate change negatively impacts food security and nutritional status in Cameroon by reducing agricultural production and decreasing revenues for smallholder farmers. Agriculture production should not be endangered to maintain good food security in Cameroon since various staple crops depend highly on rainfall (Chimi *et al.*, 2022, p.699). To be food secure, one must ensure the production and consumption of food from farms and fluctuations in market prices (Mbuli *et al.*, 2021). The investigation by Mbuli, Fonjong and Fletcher (2021) assessed the vulnerability of small-scale farmers in North-West Cameroon to a changing climate and its implications for food security. According to their findings, agricultural losses increase the risk of food insecurity. The changing climate impacts household nutrition in Cameroon (Molua and Ayuk, 2021). Mbuli, Fonjong and Fletcher (2021) reported that some farmers in Cameroon have abandoned certain crops, including potatoes, cabbage, and green vegetables, which have been highly affected by variations in rainfall. As a result, Njouenwet, *et al.* (2021) demonstrated decreased maize and sorghum production in the Adamaoua region because of reduced rainfall. In the previous years, the average temperature in Cameroon has accelerated by approximately one degree Celsius, resulting in decreased harvests of vegetation, which include maize and rice, that are heat sensitive (Fonjong and Zama, 2023).

There has been an increase in drought in Cameroon, resulting from the development of certain pests that attack staple vegetation together with cassava, yams, beans, maize, groundnuts, and potatoes (Sheehan, Elias, and Nevins, 2019; Nyanchi *et al.*, 2021). According to Mbongsi (2022), the scarcity of these staple crops on the market results in high food prices, which results in hunger and malnutrition in the affected region and its neighbours. A similar finding was made by Wossen and Berger (2015), who noted that Ghana's climate change correlates with food price increases, resulting in higher food prices for poor households. In examining how climate variability has affected food security in Bamenda, Tume *et al.* (2020) found that rain-fed agriculture systems have resulted in declining basic foodstuffs on which people rely. In particular, cassava, cocoyam, rice, and soybean production have decreased because of their intense predisposition to climate change and variability. According to Tume *et al.* (2020), some food species, like cocoyam, a staple food in some regions, are silently disappearing because of extreme climate, land degradation, and deforestation. The heavy rains also damage roads and prevent the transportation of crops from the point of production to the place of distribution and consumption. As a result, food prices will likely increase in areas of excessive demand because of insufficient food supplies. According to Chimi *et al.* (2022), the youth's lack of interest in agriculture has also resulted in inadequate labour to meet food needs.

Chimi *et al.* (2022) showed that youth migrate from rural to urban areas to search for better and new opportunities. Financial capacity, loans, and credit are also leading factors affecting food security in Cameroon, according to Tambi and Bime (2019) and Wenda, Engwali and Ofeh (2020). Therefore, in a straight line, increasing the productivity of smallholder farms contributes to ensuring their food security and enhancing their livelihoods (Karki, 2020). Food security must be addressed in every region of Cameroon, given the country's commitment to end hunger (SDG 2) and achieve the 2035 emergency.

3.4. Main Crop Types Investigated

3.4.1. Maize

The global yield of maize is around 81 million metric tonnes per hectare, and it grows on roughly 40 million hectares, mostly on smallholder farms (Mbah *et al.*, 2023). In Cameroon, maize is essential for food security since it is one of sub-Saharan Africa's most widely consumed staple foods (Wenda, Engwali and Ofeh, 2020). It produces over 2.1 million metric tonnes in Cameroon (FAOSTAT, 2022). Cameroon is ranked 44th globally, with a share of 0.18%; it also ranks 13th in Africa, with a share of 0.36% (FAO, 2022). Mbah *et al.* (2023) note that maize is the primary staple of over 15 million people in the country. It is also a significant raw material for food processing, brewing, livestock feeding, and agro-based industries. Cameroon cultivates yellow, red, and white varieties of maize, with yellow and white varieties being the most popular (Meyo and Egoh, 2020). A region's eating habits, and food preparation processes determine whether the white or yellow types are preferred (Meyo and Egoh, 2020).

Besides vitamins A, C, and E, carbohydrates, and essential minerals, maize grains contain 9% protein. It is an efficient energy source because of its high dietary fibre and calorie content (FAO, 2022). A fertile, deep, loose, fresh, well-drained soil rich in organic matter is the best for maize cultivation. Maize requires a specific soil, water, and temperature environment to grow. A wet or acidic soil is not conducive to increasing maize. A lack of water can ruin the yield when the ear develops (flowering). According to Mbah *et al.* (2023), the rainy season is the best time for seeding and flowering and temperatures below 10°C are not conducive to germination. If planted in tropical zones between 0 and 1000 m, maize may reach maturity 90 to 130 days after emergence. The maturity period can vary from 200 to 300 days, depending on the altitude. There is no recommendation to cultivate maize above 1800 metres or outside of a temperature range between 10 and 19 degrees Celsius (Hoopen and Maïga, 2012). Picture 1 shows a maize plantation, while 2 show maize corn.

Picture 1: Maize Plantation
Source: Picture take by the researcher during the Fieldwork

Picture 2: Maize Corns
Source Picture take by the researcher during the Fieldwork

3.4.2. Potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum* L)

It was during the German colonial period (1884-1914) that Cameroon introduced potatoes (Goodridge, 1996). Nevertheless, new varieties were introduced by the British and Dutch governments in the 1940s, leading to widespread cultivation (Foncho, 1982). The high plateaus of Western Cameroon were well suited to this crop (Mengui, Oh and Lee, 2019). Regarding food production, potatoes are the world's fourth-largest crop after maize, wheat, and rice, and planting occurs at the beginning of the rainy season, usually in March. Harvest occurs in June, just before flooding (Mengui, Oh and Lee, 2019). Cameroon has over 200,000 smallholder farmers, primarily women, who cultivate potatoes (Tambi and Bobuin, 2023). Mengui, Oh and Lee (2019) report that 80% of the national production (435,354 tons) is from the West and North-West regions. Located in the country's west at altitudes between 900 and 3000 metres above sea level, these regions feature cool temperatures and high rainfall of at least 800mm per year (Mengui et al., 2019). There were 220,000 tonnes of potato production in Cameroon in 2020, representing 0.1% of all potatoes produced worldwide and 0.8% in Africa (FAO, 2020). Various methods of preparing and serving potatoes provide a variety of ways to consume carbohydrate-rich food.

Potatoes and cereals both contain similar protein levels when measured dry. This root's content is very high compared to other roots and tubers. Additionally, the potato has numerous micronutrients and is low in fat (Tambi and Bobuin, 2023). Pictures 3 and 4 show potatoes harvested from smallholder farms.

Picture 3: Harvest of potato on the plantation
Source: Picture from Participants

Picture 4: Potato spuds showing bad quality
Source: Picture from participant

3.4.3. Red Beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*)

As a protein-rich and nutrient-dense food legume, beans fall third place behind soybeans and peanuts as the most nutrient-dense foods worldwide (Maingi *et al.*, 2001). With 6.3 million hectares of land planted annually, 37 million African farmers cultivate beans, with Cameroon producing more beans in West and Central Africa and being the sixth biggest bean producer after Tanzania, Uganda, Kenya, Burundi, Ethiopia, and Rwanda (Ngoh and Nchanji, 2022). According to Broughton *et al.* (2003), the amount of beans consumed per person in Cameroon reached 13.5 kg in 2018, making it the second most crucial grain crop after maize (Broughton *et al.*, 2003). A growing population and the urbanisation of significant towns like Doula and Yaoundé handle the increased bean production in the country (Ngoh and Nchanji, 2022). In Africa, beans contribute to food and nutritional security, income generation, crop improvement, and enhanced production systems as essential food legumes and a high-value source of protein, minerals, and micronutrients (Ngoh and Nchanji, 2022). Fresh or dehydrated mature pods can be frozen, canned, or dried to preserve them. Without sufficient land, intercropping is one of the most prevalent farming systems among smallholders. Intercropping is recommended to reduce crop failure risk (Giller, 2001). Growing beans at the best temperature with sufficient water to provide exceptional yields is essential. Groth, et al. (2020) found that 25 to 30°C is the ideal temperature for bean cultivation. Mung bean growth and productivity can be adversely affected by summer temperatures above 40 degrees Celsius (Chaudhary *et al.*, 2022).

A mixture of beans and maize is often grown in Cameroon's Western Highlands and humid rainforest during the first and second plantings (March and August/September). Besides growing well with corn and other vegetables (Kisito *et al.*, 2019), beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) prefer warm temperatures to develop. Common beans have significant social and economic importance in Cameroon (Mananga *et al.*, 2022). Depending on their shape, colour, and size, they are available in different varieties. Figure 5 below shows the plantation of maize and beans in an intercropping practice.

Picture 5 : Plantation of maize and beans: an intercropping practice (family farming)

Source: Picture taken in data collection area by research participant (June 2023)

3.5. Trends in Staple Food Production

Figure 21 below gives an overview of the production of maize, beans, and potatoes in the department of Koung Khi. It shows the trend of staple crop production in the department of Koung-khi between 2006 and 2022. The indications reveal that 2013 was the year in which the highest production of maize and beans was recorded, which paradoxically was not the case for potatoes

Figure 21: Trend of staple food production in Koung Khi between 2006 and 2022
Source: Author's computation with data from regional representation of the MINADER.

Figure 22: Trend of staple food production in West Cameroon between 2006 and 2022.
Source: Author's computation with data from regional representation of the MINADER.

In the West Cameroon region, maize production seems to be increasing in a context where climate change imposes more extended periods of drought, which shows that this crop is more favourable to the dry season. Both beans and potatoes show the same trends. Still, beans generally offer deficient production, which is not necessarily the case for potatoes, which shows that 2012 and 2019 were favourable. This change in staple food production can also significantly impact the overall supply of agricultural products in future years. Thus, climate change will substantially affect agriculture in the West Cameroon region. Figure 23 below shows the area of land used to produce staple foods in the Western Region between 2006 and 2022.

Figure 23: Cultivated areas of staple crops in the Western Region between 2006 and 2022. Source: Author's computation with data from regional representation of the MINADER.

Land use is crucial for economic development and the environment (Karimov et al., 2023). Thus, land dedicated to agriculture will allow for regular production that will benefit the food needs of the surrounding populations and, potentially, the economy (Zachariou and Burgess, 2023). Land can be used in different ways to meet different objectives, and it can be challenging to meet all these objectives at once, giving rise to difficult choices when designing policies that impact their use (Karimov et al., 2023). The areas under cultivation of maize, beans, and potatoes in the Western Region show that while the areas allocated to maize production are increasing over the years, the areas of beans are tending to decrease, which can sufficiently demonstrate that the agroecological context is less and less favourable to this crop. Overall, potato production remains low.

Figure 24: Evolution of areas according to crop between 2006 and 2022.

Source: Author's computation with data from regional representation of the MINADER.

Figure 24 above shows the evolution of areas by speculation in Koung Khi between 2012 and 2022. In the department of Koung Khi, the surface cultivated between 2012 and 2022 shows that the production of potatoes remains very low overall, which is somewhat in line with the observations made at the regional level. On the other hand, in the case of maize and beans, there is a trend of more peaks and valleys with more pronounced adverse effects for beans. Agricultural yields are not increasing rapidly in West Cameroon; the pressure on forests due to population growth is likely amplified by increased demand (Zébazé et al., 2023). Part of the REDD+ investments are expected to support efforts to increase agricultural productivity while ensuring minimal impacts of agricultural production on forests (Enow, 2023). For example, support for urban elites increasingly interested in investing in agriculture in Cameroon could increase agricultural yields in the coming years (Enow, 2023).

Figure 25 below shows the evolution of average prices by speculation between 2012 and 2022. Producer prices of agricultural products and physical quantities at production have a decisive effect on farmers' incomes. Therefore, indicators that show how farm receipts and expenditures are influenced by their price components are essential. The agricultural price indices, designed and calculated, provide information on the evolution of producer prices for agricultural products. For producers, up-to-date information on prices and other market factors allows them to negotiate with traders with peace of mind. It facilitates the spatial distribution of products from rural areas to cities and between different markets. Governments are working to provide farmers with better information services on agricultural markets in developing countries.

Figure 25: Evolution of average prices by speculation between 2012 and 2022
 Source: Author's computation with data from regional representation of the MINADER.

The information available on prices is for the West Cameroon region. This analysis is based on average prices to show that bean prices increased between 2012 and 2022, partly justified by decreasing production. maize and potato prices are relatively stable, despite a peak in 2015.

Some different meals derived from Maize, Beans, and Potatoes

Primary Stage

Complements

Final meal

Table 2: Different Meals Derived from maize, Beans, and Potatoes
Source: Author's computation

Table 2 above shows the different meals that are made from the combination of maize, beans, and potatoes. They are the common meal consumed by the rural farmer.

We observe that the food needs to be cooked with some other supplements, which are not mainly cultivated by the farmers. Most of those supplements need to be bought from the market.

3.6. Climate and Agriculture in the Western Region

Among the ten regions of Cameroon, the western one is the smallest in terms of area (14,000 km²), but it has the highest population density (2,401,749 Inhabitants) (MINADER, 2021). The western region provides most of the food consumed in Cameroon, and approximately 80% of the population in the western region are smallholder farmers who use traditional farming tools (MINADER, 2021). Agricultural products are smallholder farmers' means of supporting life (MINADER, 2021). Maize, beans, and potatoes are among the main staple crops cultivated in that region, which smallholder farmers grow in rows with peanuts, cassava, and yams. The west region has eight departments (Bamboutos, Haut-Nkam, Hauts-Plateaux, Koung-Khi, Menoua, Mifi, Ndé and Noun) as shown in Figure 26 below. Farming practices and purposes for smallholder farmers are the same in all eight (8) departments in the western region. Farming for smallholder farmers is mainly for household needs, and part of the harvest is sold on the market to cover other needs like finance, health care, education, and well-being.

The western region is purposefully selected because three-quarters of the West's smallholder farmers depend on agriculture, and there is a need for more scholarly evidence about climate change's impact on food security in the selected area.

Figure 26: Division of Eight Department of the Western of Cameroon.

Source: Available at Cameroon/Media/File: Regions of Cameroon EN.svg. Retrieved on 01.10.2023.

Because of its higher elevations and moderate humidity, the West has one of Cameroon's more pleasant climates. The dry season is a significant season in the West, followed by the rainy season.

The year begins with a dry length until March, accompanied by rains starting in April or May and lasting till October or November, as shown in Table 3. In the mountains, temperatures are slight, with a mean yearly rainfall of 1,000 to 2,000 millimetres.

In the western part of Cameroon, climate plays a crucial role in agricultural practices. It affects soil moisture content, fertility, and vegetation positively or negatively. Crop yields are adversely affected by rain irregularities because the rain may not arrive during the crop's growth cycle. A decrease in agricultural production is caused by decreasing annual rainfall combined with seasonal variations in the timing of the rains (Molua, 2014). A rising temperature decreases surface runoff, increases evapotranspiration, and reduces soil moisture stores (Sonwa et al., 2014). High temperatures may cause soil moisture deficits, challenging the cultivation of water-loving plants like corn, groundnuts, potatoes, and yams. It is essential to know when the rains are beginning and ending for the final state of some crops. These factors include the soil, moisture content, and sensitivity of the plants. For both rain-fed and irrigated farms, it is essential to understand the spatial and temporal distribution of rain (Molua, 2021). Farmers practised field rotation previously, allowing their land to lie fallow for two or three years.

However, because of the increasing population density, they now utilise their land almost continuously (Ngondjeb, 2013). This permanent land use for agricultural purposes induces soil degradation and erosion caused by heavy rain. Regular use of chemical fertilisers by 60% of farmers has resulted in declining soil fertility (Ngondjeb, 2013). Maize is the primary staple, and farmers surround their rows with cocoyam, beans, groundnuts, and yams (Ngaiwi et al., 2023). Potatoes are another mainstay, and the West is one of the few places in Cameroon where they grow well because of the high elevation in the region (Ngaiwi et al., 2023). Farmers plant crops in fields comprising alternating ridges and furrows after the first rains. Most crops, such as maize, groundnut, and potatoes, begin to grow after the first rainfall between March and April, and can be harvested after five months, which is still within the rainy season (MINADER, 2023). However, other crops, such as beans, which require less rainfall and have a shorter growing season, are planted underground in September, when the rainy season is about to end, and harvested in December, in the middle of the dry season (MINADER, 2023). Farmers in the Western Region of Cameroon rely on climate seasons to guide their agricultural practices (Mbuli et al., 2021). Their calendar system considers the area's unique climatic characteristics, with the rainy and dry seasons dictating the timing of various farming activities (Mbuli et al., 2021). For instance, farmers typically clear their plantations during the dry season to facilitate successful slash-and-burn farming, while sowing and planting are best done during the rainy season (MINADER, 2023). Given the joint ownership of these two seasons, farmers know the changes that can impact their operations. Sometimes, the dry season extends into the rainy season, leading to a shortened cycle that does not allow the ground to soak sufficiently for successful crops (MINADER, 2023).

Alternatively, the rainy season may start earlier than predicted, while agricultural activities inside the dry season are still underway (Fonjong and Zama, 2023).

In such cases, farmers fear the outcomes of excessive or too little rainfall that could cause flooding or a shortened dry season (Fonjong and Zama, 2023). Finally, the frequency of runoff during rains can wash away more land (primarily litter) in rivers and backwaters downstream (MINADER, 2023).

The devastating force of the winds during different seasons (dry and rainy) is also a growing concern for farmers (MINADER, 2023).

Jan	Feb	Mar	April	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
Dry period	Ending of Dry period	Starting to rain	Rain Season in the West Region								
			Period Of Heavy Rainfall in the West Region						Ending of rain		Dry Period

Table 3: Variation between dry and rainy seasons in the western region of Cameroon

Source: Author's computation with data from regional representation of the MINADER

Crops	Technical Itinerary	Long Dry season									Short Rainy Season								
		January			February			March			April			May			June		
		01	02	03	01	02	03	01	02	03	01	02	03	01	02	03	01	02	03
Groundnut	Field Preparation	[Bar]																	
Maize	Planting										[Bar]								
Soybeans											[Bar]								
Okra	Cleaning (weeding)										[Bar]								
Cucumber											[Bar]								
Beans	Phyto treatment										[Bar]								
Tomato											[Bar]								
Cabbage	Fertilization										[Bar]								
Pepper											[Bar]								
Wheat	Harvesting										[Bar]								
Squash											[Bar]								
Lettuce	Setting up the nursery	[Bar]																	
Watermelon		[Bar]																	
Carrot	Field preparation	[Bar]																	
Cowpea/white beans		[Bar]																	
Palm trees (young Plantation)	Planting										[Bar]								
	Fertilisation										[Bar]								
	Cleaning (weeding)										[Bar]								
	Harvesting										[Bar]								
Palm trees (old Plantation)	Fertilisation										[Bar]								
	Maintenance (weeding, pruning)										[Bar]								
	Harvesting										[Bar]								
Banana, plantain	Field preparation	[Bar]																	
	Planting	[Bar]																	

Figure 27: Program of agricultural activities in the Highlands Zone

Source: MINADER, 2023

The cropping calendar proposes a chronogram of agricultural activities (see figure 27) to facilitate farmers to better plan of farming activities to adjust to climate disruptions and optimise crop yields. This calendar includes agricultural operations (AP). AP1: Soil preparation happens before the crop is planted (sown).

AP2: Clearing and cleaning: This is clearing and cleaning an area. It involves removing plants from a wooded area, forest, or "wasteland" to cultivate or convert the soil to pasture.

AP3: Labour involves any activity associated with cultivating agricultural land, including using hoes and spades and packing animals.

AP4: Sowing: Farmers plant seeds after being ploughed or ridged in this activity. Farmers can sow the seeds in two ways: direct sowing and when farmers should sow seeds in seedbeds.

AP5: Maintenance includes weeding and fertiliser application.

AP6: Phytosanitary treatment: protection from/fight against various diseases by applying phytosanitary products.

AP7: Harvesting: Harvesting involves the collecting of plant parts that farmers can use for human consumption (fruits, seeds, stems, roots, bulbs, etc.) (MINADER, 2023).

The research on the impact of weather change on food security is justified by the urgency of the issue, the interdisciplinary nature of the challenge, and its implications for global sustainability.

By delving into the complexities of this intersection, researchers make contributions not only to the clinical knowledge of weather trade but also to the development of strategies that safeguard food security in a changing climate. This research holds vast implications for the prosperity of current and forthcoming generations and forms a pivotal aspect of the worldwide reaction to climate change.

Despite an emergent body of literature examining climate change impacts on food security among rural smallholder farmers, many important gaps remain. One notable gap is the lack of attention to climate change impacts on between regions and agricultural systems (Molua et al., 2023). Vulnerabilities have been highlighted, but no research examines how these vulnerabilities vary across geographical and socioeconomic contexts (Molua et al., 2023). Furthermore, the existing literature tends to overlook the complex interactions between climate change and other drivers of food insecurity, such as poverty, inequality, and land use policy (Ahmad et al., 2023). Smallholder farmers are embedded in socioeconomic and political systems that determine their adaptability to climate change impacts. However, few studies have comprehensively investigated these policy factors and their impact on food security in rural communities (Cedric *et al.*, 2022; Alexandridis *et al.*, 2023; Farooq *et al.*, 2023). Another gap in the literature relates to limited attention to gender empowerment in climate change adaptation and food security (Mawren *et al.*, 2023). Women play an imperative role in agricultural production and rural food supply, but their experiences and perspectives are often marginalised in research and policy debates (Le Mouël et al., 2023). More exploration is required to apprehend the nature of gender inequality and the convergence of climate change impacts. In conclusion, it is important to address this gap in the literature to advance our understanding of the dynamics that determine smallholder farmers' susceptibility and resilience in the face of weather variation. Future exploration efforts should seek to adopt interdisciplinary approaches, engage with community members, and incorporate multiple perspectives to gain contextual insights that can inform intervention policies and practices if they are to be developed it is effective.

4. Chapter Four Methodology

4.0. Introduction

This chapter provides a detailed account of the methods and procedures employed, from the initial application submission to the ethical committee at the University of the West of Scotland to the subsequent collection of data in the field. It outlines the established criteria used for participant selection and comprehensively elaborates on the data collection process. It sheds light on the rationale behind the chosen method and its application within the context of the study. Finally, this section explains the process by which the data was analysed and presented in a coherent and informative manner.

4.1. Justification of a Mixed-Methods Approach

The concept of mixing different methods originated in 1959 when Campbell and Fiske used a multimethod to study the validity of psychological traits (Campbell and Fiske, 1959). Two paradigms, positivism and interpretivism or constructivism, influence the research approaches for each study (Creswell, 2013). Positivism presents a comprehensive approach to the various disciplines within the natural and social sciences (Coolen, 2012). To better understand the context, it is interesting to note that positivism originally meant collecting and validating factual knowledge scientifically, aiming to discover proper knowledge obscured by the traditional powers (Coolen, 2012). A significant feature of positivism is the widespread use of quantitative procedures and tools for collecting and analysing data over questionnaire surveys, which have reasonable reliability in enlightening evident phenomena (Collins, 2010). Conversely, interpretivism or constructivism emphasises subjective, humanistic perceptions of reality and the use of qualitative interviews, observations, and focus groups as methods and tools of data collection (Collins, 2010).

Guodaar (2021) contends that adopting either a pragmatist or soft constructivist paradigm permits the integration of the epistemological concepts of positivism and interpretivism. According to pragmatics, a single perspective cannot offer the most accurate comprehension of reality. Therefore, the practical integration of positivist and interpretive research methods is often necessary to understand a research problem within one study (Guodaar, 2021). In this approach, various investigation procedures and tools, such as surveys, interviews, focus groups, and participant observations, can be employed in a single study (Creswell, 2013) and deliver applied assistance for each other, triangulating the understanding engendered to solve the problem (Guodaar, 2021).

Within the confines of this research, an interpretive approach relies on critical inquiry and observation to develop or extract a detailed and profound comprehension of the investigated phenomenon. This refers to a qualitative approach, which includes a focus group discussion composed of community leaders and lead farmers and key informant interviews with stockholders.

In contrast, a positivist approach refers to a social science that considers observable phenomena as the foundation for knowledge where measurable analysis is the most considered. The application includes questionnaire surveys, which enable the analysis of local meteorological information to determine climate change trends in the Koung-Khi department. Further, the survey questionnaire explores how smallholders perceive challenges posed by climate change, how it affects their food security, and how they adapt to the threat. It has been possible to enhance food security by leveraging farmers' expertise and experience (Okori *et al.*, 2022). A supplement of focus group discussions and key informant interviews helped to complement and corroborate the results from quantitative and qualitative sources.

4.1.1. Quantitative Approach

The strategy of inquiry applied in this study is a survey methodology that provides quantitative or numeric descriptions of trends or attitudes of the smallholder farmer community by studying a sample of smallholder farmers in the Koung-Khi department. A survey was carried out to collect information about the influence of climate change on smallholder farming and its relationship to food security status, as well as prevailing knowledge systems that were combined and employed to facilitate acclimatisation. Surveys are widely used in social investigation since they are efficient and rapid in collecting data and can measure study characteristics accurately for generalisations (Guodaar, 2021). The approach used in this study for the survey included structured questionnaires.

A survey is an excellent tool for researchers to estimate study characteristics for further details to be analysed (Creswell, 2013). It has the advantage of gathering large amounts of information, having validated models, and having a large sample size and, therefore, greater statistical power (Jones, Bartsch and Sharifi, 2013). Primary data on smallholder farmers' experiences with climate change were obtained through a survey to gain insight into understanding the threat. The survey helped assess food availability, accessibility, and utilisation among smallholder farmers in rural settings. The survey was designed to be easily understood by all smallholder farmers, with sections focused on smallholder farmers' socio-demographics information and experience in the understanding of climate change, climate change and food availability, accessibility, and utilisation among smallholder farmers, and smallholder farmers' adaptation strategies and challenges. The first phase of the survey aimed to collect socio-demographic data on smallholder farmers, such as age, gender, household size and education level. These data will provide insights into the demographic characteristics of population the number of subjects to help researchers understand the socio-economic context in which they operate.

Subsequent sections of the study focused on smallholder farmers' experiences and perceptions of climate change. This included questions about their understanding of climate change and its impact on food security, availability and use in their communities. The aim of this section is to collect data on how climate change affects smallholder farmers' agricultural practices and livelihoods, as well as their food availability and consumption. Finally, the study addressed smallholder farmers' adaptation strategies and challenges in responding to climate change impacts. This section aims to identify resilience strategies and capacity building programs adopted by smallholder farmers to mitigate the negative impacts of climate change on their agricultural activities and food security along with barrier identification efforts and barriers that hinder their ability to adapt effectively to changing environmental conditions.

Overall, the research design demonstrates a comprehensive approach to understanding the complexities of climate change and food issues among smallholder farming communities, with the aim of mitigating them develop evidence-based interventions and policy recommendations to support their coping and adaptation efforts. Question types in the survey included closed ended (Likert scale) and open-ended questions. However, respondents could also give their answers under options. By requesting opinions on statements, it is easy to derive trends of views from many smallholder farmers on specific issues and get a picture that is more complex than a trend consisting simply of "yes" and "no" answers (Shee et al., 2019). The open-ended questions allow respondents to include more information involving knowledge, attitudes, and understanding of the subject. Open-ended questions dispatch two types of response errors. First, respondents are not likely to forget the answers they must choose from if they are required to respond freely. Second, open-ended questions do not allow respondents to disregard reading the questions and "fill in" the survey with the same answers (Shee et al., 2019). Only the trained research team members interacted with the participants throughout the survey process. The researcher could intervene only when the trained team member could not solve the situation.

4.1.2. Qualitative Approach

The strategy of inquiry applied is a qualitative descriptive approach in which the researcher explored in-depth activities like focus group discussion, interviews, and personal observation over a sustained period (Stake, 1995). This study used focus group discussion as a participatory approach. Participatory approaches are frequently used in local studies to gather evidence from rural residents and better understand their environmental circumstances (Hofmeijer et al., 2013; Walter and Andersen, 2013). The process involves a collaborative knowledge exchange between scientists and non-scientists (local people) (Ballard and Belsky, 2013). As part of this study, focus group discussions were conducted with lead farmers and the head of the community to obtain detailed information to support what was gathered during the surveys and cover the missing gaps that emerged at the session.

This study involved a focus group discussion with twenty-four lead smallholder farmers and ten community leaders with unique characteristics to benefit from a deeper understanding of a topic of interest.

Rich and comprehensive data is collected through conversations among community leaders and lead farmers. The discussion allows the participants to express their ideas and thoughts on the issues. Although focus groups are often considered more reliable, they are still vulnerable to criticism in social science research. Based on these discussions, Guest, Namey and McKenna (2017) mentioned that results could not be generalisable since one individual could dominate a focus group discussion. In this study, the researcher attempted to overcome the bias by applying the Mawere and Mubaya (2014) approach, which considers detached focus group discussions based on gender and indigenous diversity. Adding to the Mawere and Mubaya (2014) solution, the researcher also considers gender representation with equal representation for each gender. This approach eliminates environmental bias if one gender is more representative. Besides other methods, the researcher used interviews with key informants in the study area to collect qualitative data. The interview process describes a qualitative research technique involving spending time in depth with a few respondents to understand their perspectives regarding an idea, programme, or issue (Boyce and Neale, 2006). Interviews are beneficial for gathering in-depth information about research questions (Boyce and Neale, 2006).

In addition, Boyce, and Neale (2006) argue that the researcher is directly in charge of the data collection process and can clarify specific issues during the process if necessary. Conversely, disadvantages involve a more significant time commitment and the challenge of scheduling interviews with members of the target sample group at a suitable time (Boyce and Neale, 2006). The persons interviewed for this study were government representatives and representatives of non-government organisations.

Government representatives were composed of regional and departmental delegates of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. A non-government organisation representative comprised five project managers from Caritas and six church leaders from the research locality. The researcher employed a semi-structured interview format, combining elements from structured and unstructured interviews throughout the study. In a semi-structured interview, interviewers ask all interviewees the same questions but can also request additional questions to clarify or explore specific topics further (Boyce and Neale, 2006). An open-ended interview allows respondents to respond more flexibly regarding content and scope (Creswell, 2016). The researcher achieved the study's qualitative validity through different methods to build a credible narrative account of the issues. Credibility in research is a critical detail that refers to the extent of the accuracy and authenticity of the findings. Establishing credibility in qualitative studies is imperative to ensure that the outcomes are reliable and valid. To obtain the credibility of this study, the researcher employed triangulation techniques, which incorporate using more than one asset of records to corroborate the findings.

4.1.3. Researcher Reflexivity and Research Biases

In mixed-method research, the expression of reflexivity by the researcher is a foundation for maintaining the integrity and transparency of the study.

In this context, reflexivity refers to the researcher's conscious examination of their assumptions, biases, and influence on the research process, particularly while combining quantitative and qualitative methods. The researcher transparently outlines how research design preference aligns with the research goals and enriches the general understanding of the phenomena under investigation. In integrating quantitative and qualitative methods, the researcher articulates their method for triangulation. They transparently discuss how divergent or convergent findings are handled, emphasising the complementary nature of the two methods.

From establishing this mixed-method research, the researcher embraced the fundamental of addressing bias as an essential issue of maintaining research integrity. Recognising that bias can emerge in various forms, from choice bias in participant recruitment to confirmation bias in data analysis Rieger et al. (2023), the researcher designed the study meticulously to minimise and address this potential bias. The preference for the mixed method was not arbitrary; instead, it was grounded to mitigate bias. The researcher triangulated quantitative and qualitative methods to offset the constraints inherent in every approach, fostering an extra-comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the study question. Each method was selected with extreme attention to its biases, and their integration became carefully organised to supplement and validate one another. Biases in participant selection were addressed through purposeful and diverse sampling. Ensuring diversity in participant selection helped the researcher capture a broader range of perspectives and experiences, minimising the risk of sampling bias (Rana et al.,2023). Also, a diverse research team with individuals from various academic backgrounds helped to challenge biases. During data collection, the researcher remained vigilant for signs of bias.

In the assessment phase, the researcher adopted rigorous and apparent approaches. Coding procedures were established, and any ability for interpretation bias was meticulously considered. Triangulation emerged as an effective strategy to address bias. The researcher identified convergences and divergences by cross-verifying results from different methods, strengthening the study's credibility. This systematic triangulation helped counteract biases that might have been found in each approach.

4.1.4. Concurrent Triangulation Strategy

Analysing the research problem based on concurrent mixed methods involves combining quantitative and qualitative data (Schoonenboom and Johnson, 2017). This approach involves simultaneously collecting both kinds of data, integrating them, and interpreting the overall findings (Creswell, 2013). A researcher can also embed data forms within each other in this design to analyse various questions (Harrison and Reilly, 2011). Multiple types of data can provide better insight into a particular research question. The mixed-methods strategy adopted for this study was concurrent triangulation.

Concurrent triangulation involves collecting qualitative and quantitative data concurrently, comparing them, and then determining whether there is convergence, difference, or more than one (Creswell, 2009).

As a result, this model offsets the strengths of one method with the weaknesses of the other to balance out each method's weaknesses (or vice versa) (Creswell, 2009). Under the objectives of this study, the researcher concurrently collected both quantitative and qualitative data. Creswell (2009) stated that during the mixing process in an interpretation or discussion section, a data synthesis occurs to ensure that the data are easily comparable (i.e., transformed into another type of data) or used to compare two databases in a discussion. The mixed-methods concurrent triangulation strategy is helpful because it is familiar to most researchers and can produce well-validated and substantiated findings (Dewasiri et al., 2018). Figure 28 below shows the mixed-methods concurrent triangulation strategy.

Figure 28: Diagram of the Mixed-Methods Concurrent Triangulation Strategy

Source: Authors' computation. Adopted from: Atif, A., Richards, D. and Bilgin, A., 2013. A student retention model: empirical, theoretical, and pragmatic considerations.

4.2. The Study Area

4.2.1. Department of Koung-Khi

The researcher selected the department of Koung-Khi for this research through a simple random sample, where every department in the Western Region had an equal chance of being selected. The department of Mifi was not included in the sampling procedure because it was the primary area of study, and the ethical committee did not validate the method applied in that area. The Department of Koung-Khi in the West Region of Cameroon has a territory of about 353 km² with a population of approximately 70,600 (National Institute of Statistics, 2019), which includes ethnic groups such as the Bamileke. A division of the Mifi department resulted in the establishment of this department in 1995.

The department is divided administratively into four districts: Bayangam, Bandjoun, Poumougne, and Demdeng (National Institute of Statistics, 2019). Each district has villages with rural areas where the research occurred. In this study, a rural area is a geographical region outside urban centres, typically characterised by low population density and natural scenic beauty.

The term implies a distinct spatial and demographic orientation dominated by the rural landscape, agricultural activities, natural environments, and traditional lifestyles (Barbosa et al., 2022). The significance of rural areas is increasingly recognised in academic and policy circles, as they play a vital role in promoting sustainable development, preserving cultural heritage, and providing essential ecosystem services (Brandão and Santos, 2022). Despite their distinct advantages, rural areas face several challenges, including poor infrastructure, limited access to services, and declining economic opportunities (Chen and Liu, 2023). Significant efforts are needed to support rural development, enhance the livelihood of rural residents, and promote sustainable land use practices to strengthen food security. Picture 6 shows the highlands of the west region of Cameroon with agriculture.

Picture 6 : The highlands of the western region of Cameroon with agriculture
Source: Picture taken in the fieldwork (June 2023)

The department of Koung-Khi has an equatorial microclimate of Guinean (MINADER, 2015). Rainfall is abundant, ranging from 2,300 to 4,500 mm per year, with an annual average of 3,000 mm. There is a short dry season (November - February). The dominant wind during this period was the harmattan. The wet season lasts eight months (March - October). August is the rainiest month, while February is the hottest. The average annual temperature is 26°C, with a temperature difference of 10°C (MINADER, 2015). The hottest period is from December to February, and during that period, farming activities are at their peak, such as harvesting staple crops like beans and potatoes (Yengoh, 2010).

August and September receive abundant rainfall, the period to harvest maize, yams, and groundnuts (Yengoh, 2010). Figure 29 below shows the area where the study was conducted.

LOCATION OF THE STUDY AREA

Figure 29: Location of the study area
Source: Author computation

4.3. Data Collection Procedure

4.3.1. Sample Size

For a study to be compelling, the researcher should determine an appropriate sample size to represent the general population under consideration (Saunders et al., 2009). The rural setting of the Koug-Khi department encompasses twelve agricultural operational areas, each representing a community of farmers. The department takes great care to ensure that these areas fully comply with all relevant regulations and guidelines, with a particular emphasis on sustainability and environmental responsibility. The Ministry has appointed an agronomic engineer with expertise in agricultural management as the leading authority in the locality. For this study, the researcher randomly selected the following ten villages: Badrefam, Batoufam, Bayangam, Famla II, Djebem, Fomayum, Kamgo, Cheferie Dja, Bandjoun, and Nkeng. Each town represents an agricultural operational area in the three districts of Koug-Khi.

Smallholder farmers who participated in the study were producers of staple crops and relied only on family labour. The principal staple crops under investigation were beans, maize, and potatoes because they are the most cultivated and consumed in the western region of Cameroun.

The present study obtained a comprehensive sampling frame of smallholder farmers from the selected operational areas through the departmental delegate of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. Based on the ten active rural regions, the evaluated size of the sampling frame was 1000. The departmental delegate brought this information to provide a comprehensive and representative sample of the population under investigation to ensure the study's findings are genuine, reliable, and valid. Based on Yamane's formula (1967), the researcher calculated a sample size of three hundred and one (301) for this study. A total of 301 respondents comprised two hundred and fifty-two during the survey, thirty-four during the focus group discussion, and six during the critical informant interview. The researcher chooses a specific number of smallholder farmers from ten different agricultural operational areas to ensure a representative sample. The researcher selected these areas because they share similar population sizes and strong farming communities. Up to eighty smallholder farmers were selected from each district. Determining the appropriate sample size for a research study requires careful consideration of two key factors: precision and confidence level (Althubaiti, 2023). Precision refers to the error the researcher will accept, while confidence level is the assurance that the actual value of the variable in question falls within the standard error. By carefully balancing these two factors, researchers can ensure their findings are accurate and reliable. It is important to note that the choice of sample size can significantly impact a study's overall quality and validity, making it a critical consideration in any research endeavour (Althubaiti, 2023). The study's sample size was determined using the equation (Q1) below, with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. This approach guarantees reliable results and enables us to draw accurate conclusions.

Equation (Q1) of sample size calculation: (Q1)

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Were,

n = the sample size of the study.

N = the Total population size of smallholder farmers' farmers in the rural setting of the department of Koung-Khi.

e = the sampling error.

4.3.2. Reliability and Validity

The techniques employed in the research process establish the degree and rationale for producing reliable, precise, and accurate outcomes, thereby ensuring credibility (Cohen et al., 2000).

Babbie (2010) argued that research instruments must yield expected results to answer research questions accurately. According to Cohren et al. (2007), it is essential to employ a stable and consistent measurement style to ensure reproducible results.

Cohen et al. (2007) noted that validity involves accurate research findings and conclusions. As shown by Babbie (2010), Kothari (2004), and Ndaki (2014), validity refers to a measure that accurately represents the intended object of measurement. Bans-Akutey and Tiimub (2021) propose that validity can be internal, external, or constructed. Establishing internal validity is fundamental to eliminating biases hindering research findings (Onwuegbuzie, 2000). Population validity and ecological validity are types of external validity. Population validity ensures that the sample represents the population being studied. In contrast, environmental validity ensures that findings apply across different contexts and times (Onwuegbuzie and Johnson, 2006). By providing construct validity, the researcher ensures that the concepts or characteristics to be studied are appropriately measured by the methods of measurement used (Middleton, 2019)

According to Babbie (2010), reliability is an attribute of the technique or tool that facilitates reproducibility of the results when applied to the same phenomenon at different times. Consequently, a result's reliability depends on its repeatability. Babbie (2010) identified three ways to ensure the reliability of research. For example, a test-retest or split-half method could be employed, as well as testing questions derived from standardised schedules or previous research. In this study, the authenticity and consistency of the results were accomplished by pre-testing the gears, using experts, and triangulation.

4.3.2.1. Use of Experts

The review experts commented to the researcher on how to improve the instrument. For this research, the researcher submitted the questionnaire to six climate change, environmental, adult health, and agronomic experts for review. The experts involved were two from the University of the West of Scotland, one from the Hamburg University of Applied Sciences, Germany, and three from the Department of Agronomy and Environmental Science of the Evangelic University of Cameroon. The reviewer commented on shaping the instrument before it was used in the field. Another comment was about the accuracy of the language and understanding of smallholder farmers who live in rural areas and are subject to low literacy. Additional comments were about breaking the scientific language style, as smallholder farmers could easily understand it. Another comment was about the questions and if they mirrored all the essential concerns projected to be measured.

4.3.2.2. Pre-Testing the Instruments

The researcher also tested questionnaires in this study to strengthen validity and reliability further. The pre-testing approach was also used as a pilot study to test the survey and improve the study's validity. A few questions in Section 1 of the questionnaire concerning socio-demographics, climate knowledge, and perceptions of climate change were found in the literature. The researcher changed the questions to suit the study context and needs. Thus, previous studies validated and used the questions, ensuring validity and reliability.

Along with providing the validity and reliability of results, pre-testing research instruments allow for the refinement of data collection instruments and predict whether the study will yield meaningful results and reflect the real-world context of the study (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003).

Regarding this research, pre-testing of the questionnaire was done in the district of Bandjoun in February 2023, just before the fieldwork. The questionnaires used during the survey, interview, and focus group discussion were written in English. Questionnaires were then translated into French using Microsoft Word 365. The researcher then checked the spelling and grammar errors in the translated version in French. The researcher is bilingual and has significant language skills in English and French. A French version of the questionnaire was also submitted to two university professors for proofreading and correction of spelling and grammar errors. Ten smallholder farmers, in alliance with village leadership, were randomly selected. Then, an informing on the pre-test training was delivered before they were intreated to join the pre-test exercise. Throughout the pre-testing exercise, the researcher carefully examined several aspects. Firstly, the researcher focused on identifying unclear words from the questionnaire tailored explicitly to smallholder farmers. Secondly, the researcher thoroughly scrutinised the questions or items that had the potential to elicit inappropriate answers.

Additionally, the researcher identified any missing or misplaced items in the list to ensure its completeness. Lastly, we emphasised ensuring the clarity and comprehensibility of the instructions provided. The pre-test result allows the researcher to adjust additional information on food accessibility, availability, and adaptation strategies. Certain unclear scientific words and contexts were deleted and rewritten until they became understandable by smallholder farmers. Information on the challenges smallholder farmers face in covering food security was added. Some policy interventions and adaptation strategies items were deleted and rearranged. After the pre-test results, a final questionnaire was undertaken, and many other enhancements were made well before printing the final form of the data collection.

4.3.2.3. Triangulation

Researcher has been increasingly focused on generating and testing theories using triangulation as they have become more sophisticated over the years (Bans-Akutey and Tiimub, 2021). Various research methods are used to ensure that the data obtained from research accurately reflects the reality of the phenomena being investigated (Moon, 2019).

The researcher used triangulation to improve the findings' reliability and legitimacy, encompassing credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability (Varpio et al., 2017; Renz et al., 2018; Moon, 2019). Research triangulation refers to the process by which the researcher uses qualitative and quantitative methods to extract the information and critically evaluate findings to determine their legitimacy and credibility (Bans-Akutey and Tiimub, 2021). Through triangulation, researchers can achieve validity and reliability in their research. Researchers can achieve triangulation in their study using the six methods outlined in (Bans-Akutey and Tiimub (2021).

Mixed methods research describes methodological triangulation in more detail (Bekhet and Zauszniewski, 2012). It incorporates multiple research methods into the study and uses various approaches. It is possible to conduct research "across method" or "within method" (Risjord et al., 2001; Casey and Murphy, 2009; Bans-Akutey and Tiimub, 2021). Several data sources are accessed in a study involving the triangulation of data. An investigator triangulation study uses researchers, interviewers, investigators, data analysts, or observers. A theoretical triangulation describes a phenomenon from the perspective of several theories (Hales et al., 2010; Bans-Akutey & Tiimub, 2021). In environmental triangulation, researchers validate their findings across a variety of environments. Multiple triangulations use two or more triangulation types (Bans-Akutey and Tiimub, 2021). In this research, the researcher applied practical and data triangulation. In the qualitative procedural line, the researcher used semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions to collect and scrutinise data. The researcher also observed and took photos of some field and staple crop types. The researcher used a survey questionnaire, a quantitative approach. In addition, 18 years of daily precipitation and staple crop data for the study areas were obtained from the regional delegation of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and the Regional Office of Meteorology and analysed. The results from all these approaches and databases were triangulated to corroborate and draw assumptions.

4.3.3. Data Collection

Approval to conduct the research activities was requested at the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development in Yaoundé. Yaoundé is Cameroon's capital and home to its central administration offices. The researcher submitted the following documents for the request:

- 1-A request letter for research written by the PhD student and addressed to the agriculture and rural development minister to seek permission and allowance for the study.
- 2-Research proposal, which summarises the project, why it is essential, and the outcome.
- 3-Questionnaire for the survey.
- 4-A letter of research approval on official university letterhead, signed by the research supervisor.
- 5-An ethical clearance to show the study's approval from the ethics committee at the UWS.

The minister of agriculture and rural development in Yaoundé issued a letter of authorisation to conduct research in the western region. The letter of research authorisation, signed by the minister, attests that an individual has the authority to perform requested activities on Cameroon's territory at the mentioned locality. Table 4 below shows the steps followed during data collection.

<p>Step 1: Academic Institution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ethical approval (UWS) <p>The procedure started at the academic institution level, where the researcher obtained ethical approval from the Ethics committee of the University of the West of Scotland.</p>
<p>Step 2: State Government</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Governmental Authorisation <p>The researcher applied for authorisation from the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. The aim was to have a ministerial or state authorisation to go into the field and conduct the research.</p>
<p>Step 3: Regional Government representative</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Regional Governmental Authorisation <p>The researcher collects climate and crop data at the regional Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development delegation.</p>
<p>Step 4: Arrondissement Government representative</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Arrondissement Governmental Authorisation (Rural) <p>The researcher arranged and organised fieldwork at the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development departmental delegation and pilot study.</p>
<p>Step 5: Rural Government representative</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Head Agricultural post (Rural) <p>Communicate with smallholder farmers and arrange the meeting point.</p>
<p>Step 6: Smallholders' farmers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Survey, group discussion, and interview.

Table 4: Steps of Data Collection

Source: Authors' computation

4.3.3.1. Crops Food Data Collection

After being granted confirmation of the requested approval to conduct research activities, the researcher travelled to the western region where the research would occur. In the west of the area, the researcher went to a regional delegation of the minister of agriculture and rural development to present confirmation of the requested approval to conduct research activities in Yaoundé.

At the regional delegation, the researcher used the proof of the requested authorisation to conduct research activities to collect staple food data needed for the study. At the regional service of surveys and agricultural statistics, the researcher collected staple food data (maize, potatoes, and beans) produced from 2005 to 2022 by the targeted smallholder farmers in the rural setting of the department of Koung-Khi.

4.3.3.2. Climate Data Collection

To collect climate data for the study areas, the researcher used the confirmation of the requested approval to conduct research activities. The researcher collected monthly precipitation data of the study area for eighteen years (2005-2022) to analyse patterns and trends, which provided valuable insights into the region's hydrological dynamics. This comprehensive dataset contributed to a deeper understanding of how precipitation fluctuates throughout the years, offering a foundation for assessing the potential impacts of climate change on local water resources.

4.3.4. Fieldwork and Survey

4.3.4.1. The Agricultural Posts

According to Decree No. 96/229 of 1 October 1996 on the Organisation of the Ministry of Agriculture, the Ministry of Agriculture is under the authority of a Minister. External services of the Ministry of Agriculture include:

- 1 Regional Delegations of Agriculture, under the authority of Regional Delegates, are responsible for supervising and coordinating the activities under the Ministry at the regional level.
- 2 The Departmental Delegations of Agriculture are under the authority of the Departmental Delegates, whose mission is to supervise and coordinate all activities under the Ministry at the Departmental level.
- 3 The District Delegations of Agriculture are under the authority of the District Delegates, whose tasks are to implement the programmes defined by the central and regional services.

Agriculture District Delegations include Agricultural Posts, Plant Material Testing, and Propagation Farms. Agricultural posts are under the authority of the Head of Post, who follows:

- 1 The animation of farmers' organisations.
- 2 The dissemination of technical topics and new methods of cultivation and treatment; the popularisation of seeds and plant material.
- 3 Research and collection of information relevant to agricultural surveys and statistics.
- 4 The distribution of fertilisers and plant protection products to growers should be done in liaison with the administrations concerned.
- 5 Proposal to the competent bodies of farmers deserving of an award or an honorary distinction (MINADER, 1996).

Climate and crop data were collected at the regional delegation. The regional delegate allowed the researcher to conduct research and then directed him to the department delegate in Koung-Khi.

The data collection procedure was organised in the rural setting of Koung-Khi with the support of the departmental delegate, district delegate, and agricultural post agent. Before starting the data collection procedure in the western region, three research assistants and one lecturer were selected at the Faculty of Agronomy and Environmental Sciences of the Cameroon Evangelic University in Bandjoun. The Evangelical University of Cameroon (UEC) is an institution of higher education founded by the Evangelical Church of Cameroon that aims to contribute to the training of future generations in the imperatives of social transformation and the construction of a new Africa (UEC, 2023). Selected research assistants were master's students in the end stage of their academic journey. Excellent communication skills, outstanding critical thinking and decision-making abilities, excellent technical knowledge in data collection, planning, and scheduling skills, and the ability to maintain quality and safety during the survey procedure were the primary selection criteria for research assistants.

It was ensured that at least one or two research assistants knew the local community's culture and beliefs. Engaging a research assistant with whom the community is knowledgeable helped to facilitate communication between the research team and smallholder farmers. This approach also helped to reduce data collection bias. The researcher also had cultural similarities with the target community because he is from Cameroon and originally from the Western region; this social proximity with the target community was an asset for the research team to facilitate comprehension with smallholder farmers during the fieldwork. The cultural similarity between smallholder farmers and the research team would create a convincing power dynamic and strengthen confidentiality. After recruiting research assistants, the researcher conducted two training and preparation sessions centred on ethical research and engagement.

In this study, research assistants assisted in collecting data through surveys. They were responsible for administering questionnaires, conducting question reviews with study participants, or recording observational data in the field. Also, a specific training session was held on the questionnaire, going through each question to ensure a common understanding of what each question was asking.

Picture 7: The research Team
Source: Picture taken during the fieldwork

The departmental delegate joined hands with the district delegate to organise meetings with the Head of the Agricultural Post. The aim was to arrange the best approach to meeting smallholder farmers in a rural setting and collect relevant information for the research via surveys and focus group discussions. This approach was the best because the head of the agricultural post is closer to the smallholder farmers, and this familiarity gives the farmers trust regarding the information they receive. Also, a call from the head of the post-agricultural department regarding collecting information relevant to agricultural surveys will be more welcome. The Head of the Agricultural Post facilitated contact with smallholder farmers in all the ten localities surveyed. The Head of the Agricultural Post communicated with smallholder farmers and agreed on a meeting day, time, and location. The Head of the Agricultural Post then informs the research team, and they meet at the agreed location to conduct the survey. Each of the ten agricultural posts hosted a meeting where the research team ensured the attendance of significant participants. At the meeting, the Head of Agricultural Post presented the research team with the purpose and expected benefits of the research. The researcher showed the signed research authorisation and then read and explained the information sheet and the consent form. Farmers agreed to participate and then received a questionnaire. At the end of each meeting, the researcher chooses one or two farmers for further group discussion sessions.

Meeting with Departmental Delegate

Meeting with Departmental Delegate

Picture 8: Meeting with Departmental delegate to arrange the fieldwork
Source: Picture taken by the researcher during fieldwork

Picture 9: Survey sessions during fieldwork

Source: Pictures taken with participant consent during Fieldwork

4.3.4.2. Focus Group Discussions

The selection criteria were the farmers who understood the topic well and did not participate in the survey session. The researcher completed three focus group discussions. Two occurred during fieldwork, with twelve smallholder farmers and elders in each session. After completing all survey sessions, the last session was with ten community leaders. One session with smallholder farmers comprised six female and six male farmers. The second session of smallholder farmers included six female and six male elders. The researcher chooses an equal number of genders to value gender equality during the discussion and allows each gender to freely express personal experiences and perceptions. This approach helps research eliminate some bias. The group discussion participants with the community leader were seven males and three females. The main discussion issues during the focus group discussion were food availability, utilisation, and accessibility. Also, the researcher addressed adaptation strategies developed at the community level in response to climate change).

Picture 10: Focus Group Discussion 01
Source: Picture taken with participants' consent during the Focus Group Discussion

4.3.4.3. Key Informant Interview

Key informant interviews usually aim to interview a specialist with extensive knowledge of an area of interest (Boon et al., 2009). The method involves engaging in an extensive interview with an expert and using open-ended and closed-ended questions to gather information. As part of this study, the researcher performed a key informant interview at the regional, departmental, and rural levels. The researcher identifies participants for key informant interviews from the regional and departmental delegations. For this study, the researcher interviewed a sample of 15 participants, as detailed below.

The time required for each interview in this study is around 30-40 minutes. The researcher visited private organisations working on climate change management, and five officials were consulted and interrogated. The participants also included four officials from the government: the Regional Delegate, the Regional Director of Communication and Agricultural Promotion, the Departmental Delegate, and the Departmental Director of Food Production and Food Safety. Various churches emphasise environmental stewardship. Six church leaders in the research areas were visited and interviewed. Interviewing a church leader about climate change and food security can help highlight the value and role of religious institutions in addressing that critical issue.

Church leaders may have unique perspectives on climate change and food security, drawing on their experiences working with vulnerable populations, promoting sustainable agriculture, or advocating for policy change.

An interview can help capture these perspectives and inform public discourse on these issues. Table 5 below shows the data collection tools and approaches used. It details information collected during the survey, focus group discussion and key informant interview.

Picture 11: Interview with NGO Representative
Source: Picture taken with participants consent during the Interview

Execution status	Information
Secondary data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Climate and food crop data at the regional and departmental delegate
Survey	<p>Smallholder farmers' survey via a structured questionnaire on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Farmers' demographic characteristics. ➤ Climate change manifestation in study areas and on food production. ➤ Climate change impact on food availability, accessibility, and utilisation ➤ Adaptation strategies used by farmers and challenges faced.
Focus group discussion	<p>Group discussion with village heads and smallholder farmers who have a broader knowledge of climate change effects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Change in food consumption. ➤ Changes in temperature and rainfall influenced the main food crops grown and consumed in their area. ➤ Impact of extreme weather on the availability, accessibility, and utilisation of food in their area and family feeding.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Measures applied in rural areas to address and overcome the impacts of climate change on food security. ➤ Adaptation strategies and challenges that limit the application and what farmers are doing to overcome the threat.
Key Informant interview	<p>Key Informant Interviews with religious and agricultural experts at the regional and district level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Climate change affecting smallholders' food security in the western region. ➤ State support of smallholder farmers on adaptation and mitigation strategies of the impact of climate change on food security in Cameroon and at the rural level. ➤ Policies implemented at the rural level to support smallholder farmers on adaptation and mitigation to the impact of climate change on food security. ➤ Challenges that limit the application of adaptation and mitigation policies and what is done to overcome the threat.

Table 5: Data collection tools and approach

Source: Authors' computation

4.4. Confidentiality and Ethical Considerations

The University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee approved this study with application number 19521. The Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development also approved the study at the national and regional levels under authorisation numbers 301 and 08, respectively (See appendix). All participants were provided with a clear understanding of the study objectives, emphasising the voluntary and anonymous nature of their involvement. All participants were required to submit written informed consent before the interviews. A link to the PIS and consent form is in the appendix. The audio files and transcripts were safely stored and could only be accessed by the researcher. The information collected in this study was kept on a password-protection spreadsheet and used for academic purposes only. The survey results should have presented participant information. In addition, the respondents' identities were not mentioned in publications related to the study. After completing the survey, all data collected for data analysis was destroyed. The data collected during the survey was accessed only by the research team.

4.5. Data Processing and Analysis

This study aimed to identify and analyse the impact of climate change on smallholder farmers' food security in western Cameroon, particularly in the department of Kong-Khi. To achieve this aim, the researcher applied descriptive statistics and econometric analytical models to analyse the time-series panel data. Descriptive statistical methods, such as line graphs, percentages, frequencies, mean values, and standard deviations, are used to analyse food crop production quantities and meteorological trends.

An econometric analysis, a Cobb-Douglas production function model, using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) based estimator, was applied to estimate crop production (maize, beans, potatoes) depending on precipitation, rainy season length, and surface cultivated area. Most researchers have focused on this function. Among the possible algebraic forms of production functions, Cobb-Douglas has been the most popular model in most empirical studies of agricultural production analysis (Gebrie and Mada, 2018). The researcher chose Cobb-Douglas production functions because they are relatively simple and convenient to specify and interpret. The model could handle multiple inputs in its generalised form. In most empirical estimations of frontier models, the Cobb-Douglas functional form is commonly used because of its effectiveness and simplicity.

Moreover, Cobb-Douglas functional forms are very parsimonious regarding degrees of freedom and convenient for interpreting production elasticity. However, Coelli et al. (2005) showed that this simplicity is linked to restrictive assumptions, including constant elasticity, constant return to scale, and equal substitution elasticity. The Cobb-Douglas production function has been determined to be applied in a study like this one.

For instance, Elahi et al. (2022) estimated the production risk of wheat farms to weather shocks and the effectiveness of physical, non-physical, and innovative management strategies for reducing crop damages based on a Cobb-Douglas production function and ordinary least squares estimation technique. The results revealed that the adverse effects of extreme weather events on wheat crop damage were more significant with the rise of severe weather. Daproza et al. (2023) used a Cobb-Douglas production function and ordinary least squares estimation technique to investigate the influences and determinants on national rice production and realise that labour, credit to agriculture, irrigated areas, and fertiliser significantly affect the volume of rice production. Kimtai and Mutiso (2022) apply a Cobb-Douglas production function and ordinary least squares estimation technique to examine the effects of climate change on maize yield in Kenya by analysing annual time series data for 1961-2020. The study shows that precipitation is one of the country's most critical factors influencing maize production. Water deficit, combined with high temperature, a proxy for climate change, has a negative and significant effect on maize production, while high precipitation is positively associated with maize yield. This study's results align with Kimtai and Mutiso's (2022) findings.

4.5.1. Econometric Analytical Model

This study is based on the theory (model) of the Cobb-Douglas production function. The theory (model) describes the relationship between production output (crop food production) and production inputs (precipitation, length of rainy season, and area of surface cultivated).

The production function equation can be simplified as:

$$X = A \cdot L^{\alpha_1} \cdot K^{\alpha_2} \cdot M^{\alpha_3} \tag{1}$$

The Log-log model uses natural logs on both sides of the equation. This model proves helpful where the relationship between parameters is nonlinear. A log transformation can convert a nonlinear model into a linear model. All log transformations generate similar results. Interpretation of regression coefficients becomes a breeze, with the natural log's practical advantage.

The stochastic form of the double log model can be expressed as:

$$\rightarrow \ln X = \ln A \cdot \alpha_1 \ln L \cdot \alpha_2 \ln K \cdot \alpha_3 \ln M + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

where;

- A = production constant
- X = crop product
- L = rainfall amounts
- K = length of rainy season
- M = area of surface cultivated
- ϵ = stochastic term

While

$$\frac{\partial(\ln x)}{\partial(\ln L)} = \alpha_1 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\ln x)}{\partial(\ln k)} = \alpha_2. \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\ln X)}{\partial(\ln M)} = \alpha_3. \quad (5)$$

α_1 = coefficient of precipitation

α_2 = coefficient of the length of the rainy season

α_3 = coefficient of surface cultivated

The stochastic form of the double-log model, commonly used in econometrics, is a standard regression model in which the logarithms of the dependent and independent variables are taken. This model is advantageous when correlations between variables are multiplicative and can help stabilise the variance of the residuals. Here is an explanation of the stochastic form of the double-log model.

Food Availability, Accessibility, and Utilisation

The researcher measured food availability, accessibility, and utilisation through perceived impact (very low, low, moderate, high) (Shrestha and Nepal, 2016).

Researchers calculated the Food Availability Index:

$$\text{Food Availability Index (FAvI)} = FAvI = \frac{4fH+3fM+2fL+fVL}{N}$$

were,

FAvI = Climate change impact on food availability index.

fH = number of smallholder farmers showing the high impact of climate change on food availability.

fM = number of smallholder farmers showing the medium effects of climate change on food availability.

fL = number of smallholder farmers showing the low effects of climate change on food availability.

fVL = number of smallholder farmers showing a very low impact of climate change on food availability.

N = Total response

The researcher calculated the Food Accessibility Index:

$$\text{Food Accessibility Index (FAcI)} = FAcI = \frac{4fH+3fM+2fL+fVL}{N}$$

were,

FAvI = Climate change impact on food accessibility index.

fH = number of smallholder farmers showing the high impact of climate change on food accessibility.

fM = number of smallholder farmers showing the medium impact of climate change on food accessibility.

fL = number of smallholder farmers showing the low impact of climate change on food accessibility.

fVL = number of smallholder farmers showing a very low impact of climate change on food accessibility.

N = Total response.

Researchers calculated the Food Utilisation Index:

$$\text{Food Utilisation Index (FUI)} = FUI = \frac{4fH+3fM+2fL+fVL}{N}$$

were,

FUI = Climate change impact on food utilisation index.

fH = number of smallholder farmers showing the high impact of climate change on food utilisation.

fM = number of smallholder farmers showing the medium impact of climate change on food utilisation.

fL = number of smallholder farmers showing the low impact of climate change on food utilisation.

fVL = number of smallholder farmers showing the very low impact of climate change on food utilisation.

N = Total response.

The interpretation of the results was as follows, based on the scores of the indicators:

A score of four for an indicator implies a high impact. A score of three shows a medium impact. A score of two means a low impact, and a score of one indicates no change (Shrestha and Nepal, 2016).

4.5.2. Adaptation Strategy

The adaptation strategy used by smallholder farmers in the study area was assessed using the adaptation strategy index (ASI). Researchers asked farmers to assess different adaptation strategies to cope with the threat through a four-point rating scale. The following formula from Uddin et al. (2014) was applied to calculate the adaptation strategy index (ASI).

$$ASI = AS_n \times 0 + AS_l \times 1 + AS_m \times 2 + AS_h \times 3$$

were,

ASI = Adaptation Strategy Index

AS_n = frequency of smallholder farmers that rate adaptation strategy as having no application.

AS_l = frequency of smallholder farmers that rate adaptation strategy as having a low application.

AS_m = frequency of smallholder farmers that rate adaptation strategy as having a moderate application.

AS_h = frequency of smallholder farmers that rate adaptation strategy as having a high application.

4.5.3. Challenges Faced by Farmers to Apply Adaptation Strategies

The researcher assessed the problems that constrain the application of the adaptation strategies through a ranking by using the problem confrontation index (PCI) (Ndamani and Watanabe, 2015).

The researcher asked farmers to grade their perceptions of each challenge on a four-point Likert scale ranging from "no problem" to "low," "moderate," and "high."

The researcher calculated the problem confrontation index (PCI) by using the following formula from (Ndamani and Watanabe, 2015):

$$PCI = P_n \times 0 + P_l \times 1 + P_m \times 2 + P_h \times 3$$

were,

PCI = Problem Confrontation Index.

P_n = number of smallholder farmers who graded the constraint as no problem.

P_l = number of smallholder farmers who graded the constraint as low.

P_m = number of smallholder farmers who graded the constraint as moderate.

P_h = number of smallholder farmers who graded the constraint as high.

4.5.4. Focus Group Discussion and Key Interview Analysis

The researcher analysed focus group discussions and key informant interviews through a thematic approach. Using thematic analysis significantly amplifies the comprehension of local dietary practices and associated customs among respondents by offering a flexible and grounded perspective in research (Braun and Clarke, 2014). This analytical technique confers several advantages by facilitating a comprehensive and systematic examination of qualitative data that identifies key themes, patterns, and trends. Using thematic analysis in this study enables researchers to gain a deeper understanding of the climatic factors that underlie the food security situation in rural settings, providing valuable insights into the complexities of local reality and their social significance. Ultimately, applying this analytical approach enhances the quality and rigour of research in food security studies and related weather variability. The researcher used focus group discussions and key informant interviews to clarify outstanding issues and provide an efficient way to understand the problems from different perspectives. Recorded interviews and group discussions were listened to multiple times and transcribed into Word to benefit transparency and clarity in the data.

The manuscript analysis was done with the Vivo Software programme (QSR International, Doncaster, Australia) (NVivo, version 14.23.0; Doncaster, Australia: Sage Publications Software, 2021) to assist with coding and analysing the data. It was necessary to change the codes and themes several times to achieve the desired outcomes. Data was transcribed using secondary sources, and then broad themes were defined using the primary codes. The researcher adopted Reyes-Garcia et al., 2021, and generated the following keywords: (1) weather instability, OR environmental change, OR gendered values, OR indigenous ecological knowledge; AND (2) food choice, OR food security, OR dietary habits, OR eating patterns, OR customary food, OR vulnerable groups; OR water access; OR climate change; OR indigenous communities; (3) local culture; OR indigenous knowledge; OR agriculture policy; OR forestry policy; OR national strategy adaptation; OR community-level initiatives; and (4) challenges; OR barriers.

The themes relevant to the impact of climate change on food security were recognised through an inductive approach.

Finally, four broad themes for the current study are proposed, which are: (1) Gender and Indigenous knowledge on weather variability, (2) Nutritional status of Indigenous communities under climate change, (3) National and Community-level initiatives for strategy adaptation; and (4) Barriers to coping strategies.

The following steps were utilised:

- Step 1- Getting familiar with the data

Taking notes, transcribing data (if necessary), and reading and rereading the data.

- Step 2- Generating initial codes

Identifying interesting data features and systematically coding them across the entire data set

- Step 3- Searching for themes

Sorting codes into potential themes and gathering all relevant information.

- Step 4- Reviewing themes

Ensure the themes apply to the coded extracts (Level 1) and the entire dataset (Level 2) to generate a thematic analysis map.

- Step 5- Defining and naming themes

Developing a clear definition and name for each theme is based on an ongoing analysis of specifics about each theme.

- Step 6- Producing the report

The data analysis was the last opportunity step.

The researcher triangulated qualitative and quantitative results to understand better how climate change impacts smallholders' food security and local opportunities for adaptation. In addition, triangulating the results from all sources increased the credibility and validity of the research findings. Figure 30 gives a summary of the method and data collection procedure.

Figure 30 Summary of Method and Data Collection Procedure
 Source: Authors' computation

4.6. Challenges and Limitations of the Methodology

The principal challenge encountered with this approach was during the execution of the fieldwork. The research team faced numerous obstacles when contacting smallholder farmers in rural settings. The barrier resided in gathering them all together at one specific point. Certain individuals have expressed their inability to allocate time for the scheduled meeting. The research team faced further obstacles concerning logistics, financial resources, and remote rural settings. The research team had to utilise vehicles adequately suited to rural road conditions. Researchers constrained financial means prevented them from obtaining suitable logistical resources, limiting their reach to the far-flung rural sector in the study area. Research has limitations, as no study is entirely free from external or internal influences. This is especially true for social research conducted in natural and social environments. In this study, some limitations were identified. The experiences of smallholder farmers in a rural setting may have been influenced by their literacy levels, which could have affected their responses.

Despite its potential benefits, the concurrent mixed-method triangulation method has its limitations. One of its primary areas for improvement is the potential for prioritising one form of data over the other. This is because both quantitative and qualitative data are collected simultaneously during the same stage. Studying a phenomenon using two methods requires much expertise and effort. In addition, comparing two analyses that use different data sources can be challenging. In dealing with those challenges, the researcher trained a team of assistants composed of one university professor and three students in the end stage of the master's study. Also, during the analysis phase, time consumption and analysis strategies were considered to overcome the challenges.

5. Chapter Five: Results of Focus Group Discussion and Key Informant Interview

5.0. Introduction

This chapter presents the results of the qualitative investigation. It gives the content of focus group discussions and key informant interviews. In this chapter, indigenous knowledge and weather variability are presented. Also, content about staple food production and the nutritional status of the smallholder farmer in the Koung-khi department is presented. Adaptation strategies and challenges at the national and local levels are also explored in this chapter. The contents of this section were obtained via fieldwork, which comprised focus group discussions and key informant interviews with diverse stakeholders with a wide range of knowledge and backgrounds. It is worth noting that the fieldwork phase involved collecting data from diverse stakeholders, including individuals from different professions and social classes. This approach provided a comprehensive and reliable assessment based on a range of perspectives and experiences of the participants. Four primary themes were identified in the data analysis: (1) Indigenous knowledge of weather variability; (2) Nutritional status and well-being of Indigenous communities under climate change; (3) National and community-level initiatives for strategy adaptation; and (4) Barriers to coping strategies. The results are presented according to themes.

5.1. Demographics of Participants

Table 6 below shows the demographics and characteristics of the participants involved in the study.

Demographic of participants		Participants (N= 49)
Gender		
Males		29 (59,2%)
Females		20 (40,8%)
Education level		
Church Leader (ChL) n=1	Doctorate	1 (2%)
Church Leader (ChL) n=5	Master	14 (28,5%)
Government representative (GR) n= 4		
Non-Government Representative (NGR) n= 5		
Lead farmers (LF) n=1	Bachelor	1(2%)
Lead farmers (LF) n= 1	Diploma	1(2%)
Lead farmers (LF) n= 19	College	25(51%)
Community leader (CL) n= 6		
Community leader (CL) n= 4	No education	7(14,2%)
Lead farmers (LF) n= 3		

Table 6: Characteristics of respondents

Source: Authors' computation

5.2. Summary of Themes and Keywords

Table 7 below shows the key keywords and themes in the study.

Codes	Themes	outcome
weather instability, OR environmental change, OR gendered values, OR indigenous ecological knowledge, OR perception	(1) Gender and indigenous knowledge of weather variability	-Increase the number of hot days -Decrease rainy days -Soil erosion - Drought - Heavy wins
food choice, OR food security, OR dietary habits, OR eating patterns, OR customary food, OR Vulnerable group, OR Water access, OR Climate change, OR indigenous communities, OR Health status	(2) Nutritional status and well-being of Indigenous communities under climate change	- Decrease crop food production -Poor food quality and quantity -Poor nutritional status for pregnant women and newborns -Loose of traditional food
local culture, OR, indigenous knowledge, OR Agriculture Policy, OR Forestry Policy, OR National strategy adaptation, OR Community-level initiatives,	(3) National and Community-level initiatives for strategy adaptation	Adaptation -Change the planting date -Intercropping - Agroforestry -Irrigation -Supplement income (Churches and NGOs) -Traditional food storage and tree conservation
Challenges, OR barriers coping OR difficulties adapting OR mitigation	(4) Barriers to coping strategies	Challenges -Poor market access -poor resources -lack of policy implementation in a rural setting

Table 7a: Summary of themes and Keywords
Source: Author's computation

5.3. Indigenous Knowledge of Weather Variability

All participants in the lead farmers (LF) group and community leaders (CL) observed and witnessed long-term changes in the local climate. Church leaders (ChL) and government and non-government representatives (GR) also share the same view. The standard justification argument was that, over the past decade, a decrease in the annual count of days with rainfall has been observed. Concurrently, there has been an increase in the number and duration of dry periods and the frequency of hot days. These observations reveal that participants have a good understanding of the manifestations of climate change.

Also, in Ghana, Appiah and Guodaar (2022), in their conclusion on examining smallholder farmers' perceptions and knowledge of climate variability in rural communities, mentioned an excellent level of expertise in their perception of climate variability and change. The participants' responses agree with the previous investigation by Fonjong et al. (2023), where they reported a change in precipitation pattern in the southwest of Cameroon while investigating how climate-induced water challenges adversely affect women's ability to perform farming. The authors additionally claimed that local water availability compromises women's productivity and increases the burden on women's triple roles as farmers, caregivers, and home managers. Through the investigation of the trends, impacts, and local responses to drought stress in the Diamare Division, Northern Cameroon, Ntali et al. (2023) added that farming activity in Cameroon, in general, will continue to suffer from water scarcity if adaptation strategies are not applied efficiently.

Regarding the prolonged dry season that caused the small streams in the village to run dry, two lead farmers added:

“This phenomenon is happening in their locality, too, and they do not have clean drinking water and are the ones to irrigate the farm. (LF, in FGD, 2023)

In rural settings, streams are the most common source of water for households and farming needs (Daba and You, 2022; Nya et al., 2023; Mkuna and Wale, 2023). Ayanlade et al. (2022) argue that drinking water in rural communities is mainly from the river, and one stream of water can sometimes distribute water to many communities. This argument aligns with Anik et al. (2023), who investigated the impact of climate change on water resources and associated health risks in Bangladesh. The results revealed that more than four communities in rural settings lack water for household needs and farming practices because the increased temperature has dried the streams that distribute water throughout the villages. After the rain, the second water source for farming is stream water (von Haefen et al., 2023). However, stream water is used through irrigation or pumping. These practices require materials, which are, most of the time, expensive for rural farmers.

Hansen et al. (2023) pointed out that pumping in a river seems harmless to aquatic environments. During periods of low water or in a more pronounced situation such as a drought, accumulating these samples from the same river can harm the marine ecosystem (Muruganandam et al., 2023). A female community leader claimed that the prolonged dry season had caused the three small streams in the village to run dry, which was unprecedented. Three LFs argued that:

“Even in the house, the temperature has increased a lot and is causing diseases to newborns and children” (LF, FGD, 2023).

This observation shows that climate change impacts the health status of the farmer community in the department of Koung-Khi.

It also raises the issue of indoor temperatures in rural settings under climate change. Ganesh *et al.* (2021) claimed that indoor temperature increases the demand for the body's fluid. The increase in human body temperature is medically equal to fever, which is usually a signal of underlying contamination (Mkangara, 2023). The weather variability in the study area induced an increase in indoor temperature, which threatened the health of the inhabitants, especially newborns, as they have susceptible health. Indoor air quality is also often threatened by high temperatures, as Onwudiwe (2023) mentioned while reviewing climate change impacts on air quality in Nigeria. Generally, when the house is not built smartly, it does not keep the indoor temperature stable (Simon and Sánta, 2023).

“We observe that when the rain comes, it is too heavy, and it rains a lot, causing soil erosion. Because the roots of the crops are not deep in the ground because of the heat, the rain then takes all the plants away. This usually happens to the culture on the top hill, like maize” (LC, in FGD, 2023).

The crops most affected by climate variability are those cultivated in the highlands (Demem, 2023; Paerregaard, 2023; Schröder *et al.*, 2023). The dying of crops on the highlands is the most common observed impact of climate change in affected areas in Ethiopia (Wolka, Uma and Tofu, 2023). This is primarily due to geographical positioning at the highest level relative to the sea level. Mabhuye (2023) claims the vulnerability of staple crops like beans, which are commonly cultivated in the highlands, because they need water at the growing stage. When they are mature, they need warm weather to dry and get ready to be harvested. That is also the reason why staple crops like beans are suitable for the climate in the highland region of western Cameroon.

Four community leaders added that it happened to them and all their neighbours last year; they lost many of their plants on the mountain and had a landslide and flooding in the valley.

“Last year, a strong wind came and went through more than half of the mountain in many places. Those cultivated on the top of the mountain were more affected” (CL in FGD, 2023).

All six church leaders (ChL) interviewed mentioned this weather event. On that topic, two church leaders argued that the farmers in their locality should ask God what they have done wrong so that God punishes them in that way and plead with him to pray for the village.

“When I was a child in the 1960s, all these changes that are happening now were not there; we had normal life here in the village and were having rain normally; many things are changing, and we are also part of the cause” (LF in FGD, 2023).

“Our grandparents taught us that man and nature are one and that we must take care of nature” (CL, in FGD, 2023)

Considering the key informant interviews and the focus group discussions, the participants believe that the current climatic conditions in the local settings have become increasingly challenging over the last few years.

This acknowledgement is a testament to the ongoing impact of climate change on our environment. The participants' views highlight the importance of initiating and implementing measures that will alleviate the effects of climate change and create long-term sustainability practices.

5.4. Food Crop Production and Nutritional Status of Indigenous Communities under Climate Change

During the focus group discussion and the critical informant interview, all participants concurred that the production of food crops has declined because of climate change. The primary factor that caused crop failure and resulted in significant losses for farmers in the area was the insufficient water supply, given the reliance on rain-fed agriculture. According to all farmers, the main reasons for the long-term decrease in maize, bean, and potato productivity are the changing climate patterns and the loss of soil fertility.

“Generally, maize or bean seeds are planted after the third or fourth rain. However, in recent years, things have changed so much. For example, last year, it was worse. Because after three rains, the soil was too wet to grow the seeds. As we planted, things grew very well.

However, as soon as the maize reached five leaves, the rain stopped for nearly four weeks. Some plants dried up, and others resisted. We were forced to sow again. Moreover, sometimes people do not have any more seed to plant again” (CL, FDG, 2023).

A Lead farmer agreed to this comment and added that:

“It is often the crops in the mountains that are the most affected because those in the plains and valleys are more victims of flooding when we often have heavy rains with very, very violent winds.”

All government representatives and church leaders also mentioned this issue raised by community leaders during the focus group discussion. The government representative argued that when it is like that, the fertiliser farmers put in the fields does not play a role anymore because of the heat.

“Add to this, especially for the beans, it often happens that when the blooms are to form the pods, heavy rains and wind cause the flowers to fall. And that makes the production null.” (LF, in FGD, 2023).

In addition, pests and diseases were found to considerably impact crop production.

“When it is sweltering, locusts eat the bean leaves and corn” (CL, in FGD, 2023).

This observation has lined up numerous investigations on the pests and diseases induced by climate change on crop production. (Tofu, Woldeamanuel and Haile, 2022; Harvey *et al.*, 2023; Ahmad *et al.*, 2023)

Changes in weather, especially prolonged droughts, create favourable conditions for the growth of certain pests like locusts. This observation has been made in many countries, for instance, in South Africa by Price (2023), in Nigeria by Prince *et al.* (2023), in Malawi by Phalira *et al.* (2023), and in Burkina Faso by Yaméogo and Yanogo (2023).

These pests cause damage to crop by eating the leaves of staple foods during the growing stage (Yaméogo and Yanogo, 2023; Price *et al.*, 2023). Similarly, Sharma and Pradhan (2023) found that at the mature-like growing stage, maize is commonly affected by certain pests that destroy crop quality.

An elderly community leader shared that in the past, their community could produce a higher yield of crops on a relatively small plot of land, and they could do so promptly. However, the situation has changed over time, and land productivity has decreased due to fluctuations in rainfall.

“All of this affects the quality and quantity of the seeds of the corn and bean because it gets even smaller, and then when you prepare, the taste is not like the bean I ate when I was young” (LF, in FGD, 2023).

Most farmers participating in the focus group discussion shared the same view on this argument. During the group discussion with community leaders, a female participant said:

“Before, we even used to eat four times a day, and there was always something to eat at home, especially banana-like. Before, when we came home from school, our parents had already prepared something for us to eat, but nowadays, we cannot do that for our children just because there is not enough for them. We barely eat twice daily; the worst is during the dry season and the summer holidays. In the dry season, food is scarce, and during the holidays, there are children all the time at home, and they must be fed morning, noon and night.”

The decrease in the number of meals a day has also been observed in Ethiopia by Woleba *et al.* (2023) while looking at household food security, determinants, and coping strategies among small-scale farmers. Also, the same results were found in South Africa by Bahta and Myeki (2022), who used empirical evidence to explore the impact of agricultural drought on smallholder livestock farmers. One female in the group of farmer leaders additionally argued that:

“Concerning food, especially certain supplements such as oil, salt, and condiments, you have to go far into the city to buy and carry on your head or on the motorcycle to return to the village. At home, I spent two weeks without having the oil and salt to prepare because the heavy rain had spoiled the road, and neither the motorcycle nor the car could pass; some of my neighbours had the same problem. To solve this, we had to contribute the money and send a kid from the neighbourhood to the city to shop for us.”

Climate change has adversely affected the productivity of crops grown in the rural locality of Koung-Khi. As a result, the significance of local traditions has increased.

The variability in climate has had a severe impact on some of the traditional practices related to crop production in the area. To illustrate, a community leader mentioned that:

“The farm festival, which has traditionally marked the beginning of a new crop cycle, has long been celebrated by local communities through social gatherings at a commonplace.”

However, in recent times, the festival has transformed due to the scarcity of crop varieties and options available for offering on this auspicious day. The festival is no longer celebrated in the same way as before.”

“On this day, multiple varieties of crops are typically sown on a plate and worshipped for the community's prosperity. This shift in how the festival is celebrated has been caused by a lack of crop diversity, a problem that has been prevalent in the region for some time. This has brought about a need for new strategies to address the issue and ensure the continued celebration of the festival.

“To this end, efforts are being made to introduce new crop varieties that can be grown in the village and provide the necessary options for the festival. These efforts are aimed at restoring the traditional celebrations of the festival and maintaining its significance in the community as a marker of the beginning of a new crop cycle”.

In addition to the impacts of climate change on crop productivity and traditional practices, the lead farmer has further supported these arguments. According to them, some traditional foods have disappeared because of the excess heat that no longer favours the farmers who store them. Moreover, the cultivation of those crops has also become non-existent because of climate change. A community leader lined up this idea and mentioned that:

“When there are often traditional ceremonies in the chieftom and the family, during marriage ceremonies, we no longer see some traditional food, like taro, because for this to grow, it requires a lot of water. I remember back in the day, the city people used to come here with the Dyna car to buy taro and go to the city and sell it again, but now it is not happening anymore.”

“Also, there was a specific crop of people offering to marry a girl before she goes to their in-laws as blessings for their promising future. However, now, due to lack of crop production and changes in eating practices, the customary norms have also been shifted” (CL, FGD, 2023).

The topic of nutrition for pregnant women and new-borns in the locality was also discussed. A respected community leader, known for their experience and knowledge, contributed to the discussion by expressing their concerns, stating that:

“Worse is the nutrition of pregnant women and babies on everything in the dry season with heat outside and inside the house. Pregnant women always have a problem with a lack of adequate food for themselves and the baby and drinking water. When we are pregnant, we always face the problem of not getting enough food. We do not have enough power–energy–to go and labour for food.”

The participant additionally argued that:

“A belief exists amongst certain women that a baby's health is largely influenced by the season. Specifically, it is believed that babies born during the rainy season are born with robust health because their mothers can provide them with sufficient food. One of the key factors that has been identified to influence the health of new-borns at delivery is the mother's access to an adequate supply of food throughout her pregnancy.”

“If the mother consistently has access to an adequate food supply during pregnancy, the likelihood of delivering a healthy baby is increased. Conversely, if the mother has not had access to an adequate supply of food during pregnancy, the probability of delivering an unhealthy baby increase.”

Numerous scholars have claimed that climate change is having a meaningful impact on pregnant women's and new-borns' diets (Agostoni *et al.*, 2022; Fan and Zlatnik, 2023; Ramírez *et al.*, 2023). Changes in temperature and weather patterns affect the availability and quality of food crops, leading to potential nutrient deficiencies for expectant mothers and their babies (Hadley *et al.*, 2023; Joseph and Doon, 2023; Amondo, Rukundo and Mirzabaev, 2023). Nutrition during pregnancy and lactation can affect the microbiome of breast milk as well as the formation of the infant gut microbiome (Taylor *et al.*, 2023). The microbiome of breast milk is also affected by the mother's diet during this time (Mady *et al.*, 2023). Pregnant women and new mothers need to be aware of these potential impacts and work with their healthcare providers to ensure they are getting the nutrients they need for a healthy pregnancy and postpartum period.

Climate change in the department of Koung Khi led to an increase in food insecurity, a long-term consequence for maternal and child health. Limited access to nutritious foods will further increase the risk of maternal malnutrition and low birth weight, which in turn will lead to a range of health problems for the new-born. Additionally, efforts to address climate change and promote sustainable food production can help ensure a healthier future for all, which aligns with SDG 2, which is about creating a world free of hunger by 2030 and SDG 3, which is about ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all at all ages.

The SDG 2 aims to end world hunger by 2030, achieve food security, improve nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture. It paints a picture of a world where all people, especially the most vulnerable, have access to adequate, safe, and nutritious food throughout the year. By addressing issues such as food waste, agricultural productivity and equitable distribution of resources, SDG 2 seeks to transform the food system and ensure a hunger-free future for future generations.

The SDG 3 seeks to promote well-being by addressing a wide range of health challenges around the world to ensure quality of life for all at all ages. It aims to reduce maternal and child mortality, fight infectious diseases such as HIV/AIDS, malaria, and tuberculosis, and promote mental health and wellbeing. SDG 3 recognizes that access to universal health care, improved access to quality health services, and addressing the social determinants of health are essential to building resilient and sustainable societies.

Therefore, it is essential to prioritize and maintain a nutritious diet to ensure the best possible outcome for the baby's future health. The impact of climate change on food provision in the local region has had a negative effect, resulting in significant implications for local traditions. During the discussion, the issue of food access and availability was addressed, with a particular emphasis on the critical role of transportation in overcoming this challenge. A lead farmer mentioned that:

“The quantity that is harvested, because of the poor condition of the roads, is also often complicated to transport from the harvest point in the field to the house. Moreover, often going to sell it in the city is also a huge deal because when the road is bad, the transport is high, and we are not the ones who set the prices, so we most often sell at a loss

. Moreover, it is with this money that we solve all the financial problems of the family, such as buying all the needs of the family, sending kids to school, ensuring the health of the family, and the development of the family. So, it is often challenging for us to meet our survivals”.

The weather variability is disturbing crop production for smallholder farmers, as the rain stopped after the seeds started to grow (Appiah and Guodaar, 2022; Kramer and Hackman, 2023). On those issues, Ochoa (2023) argues that an unpredicted stop or decrease in rain adversely jeopardises crop quality and quantity. Following the same line as Kukal *et al.* (2023), this is because crops need both water and sunlight to grow properly. Without enough of either, the crops may not reach their full potential, and their yield may suffer. When the maturity of food crops is affected by any climate variability, then the nutrient content of that crop is also affected (Demem, 2023). It is crucial to ensure that crops receive sufficient water and sunlight to grow to their fullest potential (Al-Hazmi *et al.*, 2023). Any shortage of these essential resources can have a detrimental impact on both the quality and quantity of the crops (Kukal *et al.*, 2023). From this observation, it can be concluded that staple crops in the Koung-Khi department are not appropriately watered and exposed to adequate sunlight throughout their growth cycle. Doing so will not only improve the yield of the crops but also enhance their overall quality. The continuously changing climate will still compromise the nutritional status of smallholder farmers in the Koung Khi department.

5.5. National and Community-Level Initiatives for Strategy Adaptation

Climate adaptation strategies at the rural community level are crucial to dealing with the challenges presented by climate change to food security in local settings. Communities work together to develop effective climate change adaptation strategies.

“Regarding the practice of adaptation strategies, the state has adopted adaptation and crop improvement policies to increase agricultural production. We are already doing awareness campaigns in rural areas, and we are informing rural farmers about the practice of agriculture, the variation of crops, the practice of agroforestry, and the conservation of mangroves because this is what retains the water that will help irrigate the fields” (GR, Interview, 2023).

The collaboration between the government and non-governmental organisations to develop and implement adaptation strategies was also raised. Collaboration could mitigate the negative impacts of climate change on the crops grown in the area and preserve local traditions.

During the group discussion, CL and LF expressed their engagement in coping with the threat posed by climate change and its negative impact on crop productivity in the local region. They recognised the significance of local traditions and the need to adapt traditional practices to cope with climate variability and ensure sustainable crop production.

“Regarding the methods and practices of adaptation, we have done what we can to another extent with the means we have. We have changed our way and the date of sowing. We try to leave the trees between the fields so that they stop the soil and the wind and make a little shadow in the fields so that the sun does not dry out our crops anymore. We also plant several types of crops together, such as corn, beans, and potatoes, and we plant all this on the same surface; there are also additional activities, such as raising chickens and pigs, growing carrots, and other condiments used to prepare at home. Occasionally, we receive training from NGOs and the church to learn how to make a garden at home” (CL, FGD, 2023).

It is interesting to note that some participants discussed having access to food from others and the importance of storing and preserving traditional foods for consumption in the future. These practices can help ensure food security in times of scarcity and uncertainty, which is becoming more critical due to the adverse effects of climate change on crop productivity in the local region.

“There are tubers like macobo, taro, and even potatoes that we store traditionally. We dig the soil even to a depth of 1 metre, and we keep it in. Then we close well, and it keeps well. We remove it in the dry season when there is a lack of food” (LF, in FGD, 2023).

“We also practice the sharing of food and land between families and communities. When a person has many crops, he can share a small quantity of that harvest with those with nothing.

Alternatively, we exchange the products, which means you give me the maize and I give you the potatoes. Sometimes a neighbour who has many fields can also share or rent to those who have fewer fields” (CL, FGD, 2023).

“The church is social, and we often meet with the village chief to get some news from them and to see to what extent we can help them diversify food sources. We often do training on how to make our grease from kitchen waste” (ChL, Interview, 2023)

“The church also trains women to make bleachers with the waste from the house next to their house to grow condiments and salad to vary their food” (ChL, Interview, 2023).

“We also help pregnant women eat better. We organise a meeting with nutrition specialists in the church, and women from the village come for advice. It usually happens after the mass. After childbirth, many women lack food for themselves and their babies. We help them with some baby milk received from other churches. So that is our role as a church: to help the poorest. It is not always, but we give when we have” (ChL, Interview, 2023).

The GR also mentioned this and said they often do these trainings together with the NGOs; they accompany the NGOs in their training, make the report, and send it to the ministry in Yaoundé. Awareness campaigns are often done, but as this locality is very far from the city, it is sometimes difficult to come here because the roads are long and challenging to drive on, in the rainy season. To maintain their food security status, smallholder farmers in rural settings should adapt properly to the impact of climate change on food crop production (Anyika, 2023). By adopting innovative and sustainable agricultural practices, farmers can mitigate the effects of climate change and continue to produce enough food to feed their families and communities (Gwambene, Liwenga and Mung’ong’o, 2022). For smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-khi, changing the planting date, intercropping practices, agroforestry practices, irrigation practices, and supplementing income are the most common adaptation strategies applied in many sub-Saharan countries (Anyika, 2023). Additionally, in the department of Koung-Khi, traditional food storage is used and could be modernised to be more sustainable.

5.6. Barriers to Coping Strategies

Barriers to implementing coping strategies in rural areas can be significant. For example, limited access to information and resources, a lack of infrastructure, and lower levels of awareness about climate change can all hinder the development and implementation of effective adaptation strategies (Bedeke, 2022). Moreover, the economic and social structures of rural communities, as well as the political and institutional frameworks, can pose additional challenges.

“The government agents suggested the modified seeds, but we do not have the money to buy the seeds. Moreover, it is often said that when you start with that, it is forever because you cannot plant what you have produced. We must buy the modified seeds again at the market to plant.

Moreover, this makes us worry because we are not used to this practice. We have always been able to harvest and keep a part for the next agricultural season. If we buy the modified seeds and they do not produce much, how will we buy them next time? That is why we ask ourselves many questions to which we cannot find answers” (CL, FGD, 2023).

“Even the way we are cultivating our farms, it is only with our hands and all these tires our body and diseases happen, with our all age we are all the time sick, and diseases like Typhoid are very often here because of dirty water we are drinking, and the hospital is fare, and we do not even have money to go to cure our self” (LF, FGD, 2023).

“We are old like that; we do not have the strength to work the field anymore. We did not have retirement money like those who work for the government.

Some children from the village have gone to the city because life is difficult in the village. We sometimes lack the human resources for those who need them in their fields” (CL, FGD, 2023).

“We sometimes feel that all the world has forgotten us because none is there for us when we need help” (CL, FGD, 2023).

During the discussion, a government representative also mentioned the challenges of developing and implementing adaptation strategies. These challenges can include limited funding and resources, conflicts of priorities, and collaboration problems across different sectors and levels of government.

“What makes the policies not apply in rural areas is, first and foremost, a lack of political will. When a decision or law is taken at the national level, it takes time for it to be implemented at the rural level. We have a national climate change adaptation plan presented at COP 25 in Paris. We have been told that the government has not received external support, so the government budget alone cannot help the whole country adapt” (GR, Interview, 2023).

“There is the absence of cooperation and coordination between the agriculture and forestry sectors at the regional and rural levels that need a more comprehensive landscape management approach to bridge sectoral progress” (GR, Interview, 2023).

“The biggest challenges we have in the rural sector are that there are many people in need of support, but we do not have many ways or resources to help them. For example, the starvation of women and babies, in their case, they need special support.

Even though they produce food, this food is not the quality they need. Moreover, sometimes, it cannot solve the family's problem. So, we always need help from others" (ChL, Interview, 2023).

Upon questioning lead farmers and community leaders about methods to improve food security for community members, the majority emphasised the significance of remaining apprised of weather changes, adjusting planting dates accordingly, and providing easy access to agricultural subsidies as practical approaches to supporting rural farmers. Furthermore, strengthening market connectivity can be accomplished through implementing infrastructure projects such as road construction or establishing a market site within the village. This initiative endeavours to establish a link between urban and rural areas, thereby enabling urban residents to visit and make purchases. The government should also consult the farmers in the remote villages to determine the price of crops like beans and maize.

The adaptation of smallholder farmers to climate variability in the department of Koung-Khi presents a significant challenge, primarily due to the limited availability of resources and materials. Addressing this challenge entails prioritising the provision of resources and assistance to these farmers, ensuring their livelihoods, and promoting food system stability. Achieving this objective will require concerted efforts from relevant stakeholders, including policymakers, non-governmental organisations, and the private sector, to develop and deploy sustainable solutions that enhance the resilience of smallholder farmers in the face of climate irregularity.

Adaptation measures		Mitigation measures
-Sustainable transportation	Climate change impact on agriculture	-Soil and water management
-Tree planting and greens areas		-Improve agro-climatic information and conservation of agro-biodiversity
-Clean food production		-Improve food and seed storage
-Agro-forestry practice		-Improve organic practice and conservation agriculture
-Capture and use of landfill and digester gas		Crop and life stock diversification
-Efficiency use of water		-Land restoration and rehabilitation
-Manage waste effectively and efficiently.		-Integrated Nutrients pest and weed management

Table 8b: Adaptation and mitigation measures to climate change impact on agriculture
Source: Author's computation

5.7. Discussion

The outcomes of this investigation offer essential insights into the intricate interplay between climate change and food security, rural livelihoods, and agricultural production in the department of Koung-Khi. As a general view, the participants acknowledge that the current climatic conditions in the local settings have become increasingly challenging over the last few years. This has also threatened the health of vulnerable groups, like new-borns, in the community. The findings demonstrate that changes in climatic variability have altered the patterns of land and water usage, thereby affecting the harvesting of local food sources.

Changing climate conditions have adversely affected the production of food crops, and the nutritional status of indigenous communities has become a matter of great concern in recent times (Asamoah *et al.*, 2023). Like Reza and Sabau (2022), Shivanna (2022), Standen *et al.* (2022), and Batal, Deaconu and Steinhouse (2023), this investigation revealed that changing weather patterns, prolonged droughts, and variable rainfall have led to a significant reduction in crop yields, thereby resulting in food insecurity and malnutrition amongst smallholder farmer communities. The situation has been further aggravated by the loss of traditional knowledge and practices that were once integral to crop production in the village. In the focus group discussions (FGDs) and interviews with key informants (KIIs), it was brought to attention that climate variability, manifesting in the form pests, and diseases, has significantly affected round potato, maize, and bean production. Some studies in other parts of Africa have the same results while investigating food crop production and invasive pests (Hadunka *et al.*, 2023; Tonnang *et al.*, 2022; Phophi, Mafongoya and Lottering, 2020). The result of the investigation is in line with Nsele, Dogot and Maréchal (2023), who also looked at food crop production under weather variability in rural areas and found that the involvement of churches and NGOs in promoting sustainable and resilient agriculture practices plays a critical role in minimising climate change's adverse effects on food crop production and improving the nutritional status of indigenous communities. In this regard, Wook and Hassan (2022) also stated that there is a need to develop and implement effective measures to ensure long-term sustainability practices and promote food security among indigenous communities. Indigenous knowledge is a valuable repository of information that has been transmitted through generations and often provides insights into environmental patterns that are accounted for in scientific forecasts (Finca *et al.*, 2023). Filho *et al.* (2022) argue that gender plays an instrumental role in indigenous knowledge, as men and women have different experiences and perspectives on weather variability. Spencer *et al.* (2022) support the notion that women often possess a more nuanced understanding of the local environment due to their daily activities, such as farming and gathering.

Moreover, Birdsall (2022) indicates that it is essential to acknowledge that indigenous knowledge is a vital tool. Yeleliere, Antwi-Agyei and Nyamekye (2023) emphasise that a collaborative approach that integrates indigenous knowledge and scientific expertise is necessary to comprehend weather variability and design robust strategies for climate resilience. The effectiveness of adaptation and mitigation strategies can be impacted by factors such as governance, policy, and institutional frameworks. Marome *et al.* (2022) also emphasise that collaborative efforts across different sectors can foster the creation of a more sustainable and resilient future for rural communities. There is a need for strong governance and policy frameworks to ensure that adaptation and mitigation strategies are implemented effectively and that they are in line with local priorities (Robinson *et al.*, 2022; Bonnett and Birchall, 2022). National and community-level initiatives for strategic adaptation to climate change are crucial to cope with the challenges of the changing climate.

The government and the community can collaborate to develop and implement effective strategies that promote sustainable development, reduce susceptibilities to the impacts of climate change, and enhance resilience. Such initiatives may include the development of climate-smart agricultural practices, the promotion of renewable energy technologies, the application of water accumulation methods, and the adoption of sustainable land use policies. By working together, national, and community-level initiatives can ensure a more sustainable future for all.

Climate change poses big challenges to food system, particularly in rural settings wherein communities often depend closely on agriculture for his or her livelihoods. As temperatures upward push, precipitation patterns end up more erratic, and extreme climate occasions become more common, the capacity of smallholder farmers to supply sufficient and dependable food delivery is increasingly threatened (IPCC, 2023). Changes in temperature and precipitation can influence crop yields, adjust the dissemination of pests and illnesses, and disrupt conventional farming practices, main to reduced agricultural productiveness and food insecurity (FAO, 2023). In rural areas, wherein access to resources and adaptive ability can be restrained, the impacts of weather change on food safety are exacerbated (IPCC, 2023). Vulnerable populations, such as smallholder farmers, women, and marginalized communities, are disproportionately affected, dealing with extended food insecurity, malnutrition, and poverty (FAO, 2023). Moreover, the interconnected nature of climate change and food protection highlights the need for included processes that cope with no longer the simplest agricultural production but additionally issues which include water management, land tenure, and market access (FAO, 2023).

Addressing the complex challenges of weather exchange and food security in rural settings calls for coordinated action at the coverage and tiers investment (Marome *et al.*, 2022). National and global regulations play an essential function in providing frameworks and incentives to guide model and resilience-building efforts in rural communities (IPCC, 2023).

Policy interventions might also consist of investments in agricultural research and extension services, the merchandising of climate-smart agricultural performs, and the development of social safety nets to guard susceptible populations (FAO, 2023).

Furthermore, adequate funding is vital to put into effect and scale up weather-resilient agricultural practices and packages in rural areas (FAO, 2023). International funding mechanisms, along with the Green Climate Fund and the Adaptation Fund, can offer monetary guidance for weather variation initiatives in growing countries, which include initiatives aimed at enhancing food security (UNFCCC, 2023). Additionally, partnerships among governments, NGOs, research establishments, and the non-public sector are important for leveraging resources, knowledge, and information to address the complex and multifaceted demanding situations of weather trade and food protection in rural settings (FAO, 2023).

In conclusion, climate exchange poses a full-size hazard to food security in rural settings, exacerbating present vulnerabilities and inequalities. Addressing this challenge calls for holistic techniques that integrate weather adaptation, agricultural development, and social safety measures. Policy frameworks and funding mechanisms play a critical function in helping variation and resilience-building efforts, making sure that rural communities are ready to deal with the effects of weather trade and stabilise their meals and livelihoods.

6. Chapter Six Results and Discussion of the Survey

6.0. Introduction

The focus of Chapter 6 is to give a comprehensive overview of the survey findings. This report highlights an important aspect: the socio-demographic profile and farming information. This chapter comprehensively analyses the awareness and perception of climate change among smallholder farmers, presenting detailed insights and promoting a deeper understanding of the topic. Furthermore, this chapter explores the effects of changes in weather patterns on food crop production in the study area. To summarise, the chapter enlightens readers on the deep comprehension of smallholders' approaches to adapting to climate change, offering valuable insights into their methods and techniques.

6.1. Sociodemographic Profile and Farming Information

6.1.1. Respondents' Sociodemographic

This part of the work presents the respondents' sociodemographic profile from the three districts and the total area of study. These data are used to discuss and explain some variables related to the results. Table 8 below shows the sociodemographic characteristics and profiles of the respondents.

District	Agricultural post	Number of Farmers	Total in District
District of Bayangam	Badrefam	32	Total in the District of Bayangam 82
	Batoufam	17	
	Bayangam	33	
District of Demdeng	Famla II	41	Total in the District of Demdeng 87
	Djebem	19	
	Fomayum	27	
District of Poumougne	Kango	14	Total in the District of Poumougne 83
	Cheferie Dja	30	
	Nkeng	27	
	Bandjoun	12	
		Total 252	Total 252

Table 9: Statistics of respondents
Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

The Researcher used survey to collect quantitative and qualitative data on a variety of factors related to climate change impacts, agricultural practices, food security indicators, and socio-economic factors affecting rural communities. The smallholder farmers survey in the District of Bandjoun was added to Pougoune because of weak participation in that area.

6.1.2. Gender Characteristics

Figure 31: Gender Characteristics
Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

Figure 31 shows the gender characteristics of the participants. Regarding the gender characteristics of the study, the data analysis revealed that 53.82 percent of all respondents were females and 46.18 percent were males. Considering the results in more detail, the District of Pougoune had the highest number of female respondents, with 74.39 percent, followed by the District of Demdeng, with 55.81 percent. In contrast, the District of Bayangam had the highest number of male respondents, with 69.14 percent, followed by the District of Demdeng, with 44.19 percent, and the District of Pougoune, with 25.61 percent. Of all three districts, Bayangam had fewer female participants, with 30.86 percent, and Pougoune had fewer males, with 25.61 percent.

6.1.3. Age Distribution

Age range	Demdeng	Bayangam	Poumougne	Total Sample
< 35 years	33.33	27.16	09.76	23.60 %
35 to 45 years	14.94	18.52	21.95	18.40%
46 to 55 years	18.39	22.22	18.29	19.60%
56 to 65 years	10.34	24.69	34.15	22.80%
>65 years	22.99	07.41	15.85	15.60%
Average	46.98	46.64	52.73	48.74
Min	17	19	17	17
Max	74	80	75	80

Table 10: Age distribution. Source: Fieldwork
Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

From Table 9, we can see the respondents' age distribution: 23.60 percent of all respondents were below 36 years old, and 15.60 percent were above 65 years old. Additionally, the second most representative age group was 56 to 65 years old, with 22.80 percent of all respondents. The oldest respondent, 80 years old, was registered in the District of Bayangam, and the youngest, 17 years old, was in the District of Demdeng and Poumougne. The District of Poumougne had the highest average age, 52.73 percent; the District of Demdeng, 46.98 percent; and Bayangam, 46.64 percent. At the district level, the age group 56 to 65 years old in Poumougne was highly represented with 34.15 percent, followed by the age group under 36 years old in Demdeng with 33.33 percent.

6.1.4. Academic Qualifications of Respondents

Figure 32: Academic qualification of respondents
Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

Figure 32 above shows the academic qualifications of the respondents in the study. In this study, college refers to an educational institution that offers specialised vocational or professional education at an advanced level. The study revealed that 57.89 percent of respondents have academic qualifications at the college level, while 23.89 percent of total respondents do not have any qualifications. Additionally, the District of Bayangam had the highest respondent rate, 81.01 percent, with college qualification, followed by Demdeng at 48.28 percent and Poumougne at 45.68 percent. The highest respondent rate with no qualification was in Poumougne with 40.74 percent, followed by Demdeng with 19.54 percent, and Bayangam with 11.39 percent. Of the total participants, 18.22 percent had other qualifications, with Demdeng representing 32.18 percent, the highest number.

6.1.5. Household Size

Number of household members	Demdeng	Bayangam	Poumougne	Total Sample
< 5 persons	40.23	40.74	29.27	36.80
5 to 10 persons	48.28	53.09	60.98	54.00
> 10 persons	11.49	06.17	09.76	09.20
Average	5.93	5.29	6.55	5.93 persons
Min	1	1	1	One person
Max	16	17	34	34 persons

Table 11: Household size
Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

The results in Table 10 showed that most respondents had a household size between 5 and 10 people, representing 54.00 percent of the total respondents. The household size of fewer than five persons was the second most representative, with 36.80 percent, while more than ten persons per household represented 9.20 percent of total respondents. From the district level, the most significant household size of 5 to 10 persons was registered in the District of Poumougne at 60.98 percent, followed by Bayangam at 53.09 percent and Demdeng at 48.28 percent. The average household size in this study was 5.93 people.

6.1.6. Farming Experience

Farming experience	Demdeng	Bayangam	Poumougne	Total Sample
<10 years	34.48	30.86	14.63	26.80
10 to 20 years	32.18	35.80	30.49	32.80
21 to 30 years	14.94	17.28	14.63	15.60
>30 years	18.39	16.05	40.24	24.80
Average	19,26	18.07	27.17	21.45
Min	1	1	1	1
Max	75	70	63	75

Table 12:Farming experience

Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

The results in Table 11 showed that most respondents had farming experience between 10 and 20 years, representing 32.80 percent of the total respondents. The farming experience under ten years was second most representative with 26.80 percent, while between 21 and 30 years of farming experience represented 15.60 percent of total respondents. Looking at the district level, 40.24 percent of respondents had 30 years of farming experience in the District of Poumougne, followed by Bayangam, with 35.80 percent of respondents having 10 to 20 years of farming experience, and Demdeng, with 34.48 percent having under ten years of farming experience.

6.1.7. Farm Size

Farm size	Demdeng	Bayangam	Poumougne	Total Sample
< 2 ha	52,87	56.79	73.17	60.80
2 to 5 ha	32.18	33.33	13.41	26.40
> 5 ha	14.94	09.88	13.41	12.80
Average	2.23	1.92	1.76	1.97ha
Min	0.024	0.04	0.05	0.024ha
Max	15	15	15	15ha

Table 13: Farm Size

Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

From the results in Table 12 above, most respondents had farm sizes less than 2ha, representing 60.80 percent of the total sample. The farm size of 2 to 5ha represented 26.40 percent, while over 5ha represented 12.80 percent. The average farm size of all respondents was 1.97ha.

Regarding the district level, 73.17 percent had less than 2ha in the District of Poumougne, followed by Bayangam with 56.79 percent and Demdeng with 52,87 percent of respondents having all less than 2ha. The District of Demdeng had the highest average farm size with 2.23ha, followed by Bayangam with 1.92ha and Poumougne with 1.72ha. The District of Bayangam registers the lowest farm size of 0.04ha, and all three districts have the highest farm size of 15ha.

6.1.8. Land Ownership Status

Figure 33: Land ownership status
 Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

The results in Figure 33 above revealed that 71.26 percent of respondents are owners, and 28.74 percent rent their farms. At the district level, 81.40 percent are owners in Demdeng and 72.84 percent in Poumougne, followed by 58.75 percent in Bayangam. From the three districts, 41.25 percent of respondents in Bayangam rent their land, followed by 27.16 and 18.60 percent, respectively, in Poumougne and Demdeng.

6.1.9 Number of Farm Workers

Number of workers	Demdeng	Bayangam	Poumougne	Total Sample
<4 workers	35.63	23.46	35.37	31.60
4 to 6 workers	36.78	50.62	43.90	43.60
Above six workers	27.59	25.93	20.73	24.80
Average	5.36	5.97	5.11	3.99
Min	1	1	1	1
Max	20	30	20	30

Table 14: Number of farm workers
 Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

Table 13 above shows that most respondents had between 4 and 6 farm workers, representing 43.60 percent of the total respondents.

The number of farm workers under 4 was the second most representative, with 31.60 percent of total respondents, while 24.80 percent employed more than six farm workers. Looking at the district level, 50.62 percent of respondents employ 4 to 6 farm workers in the District of Bayangam, followed by 43.90 and 36.78 percent, respectively, in Poumougne and Demdeng. The average number of farm workers among all respondents was 3.99. The respondents in the District of Bayangam had the highest number of farm workers, with 5.97; the Districts of Demdeng and Poumougne had 5.36 and 5.11 farm workers on average, respectively.

6.1.10 Seasonal Variation of Workers

Figure 34: Seasonal variation of workers
 Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

The results in Figure 34 above revealed that 78.90 percent of respondents have a seasonal variation of workers, while 21.10 percent have no variation. At the district level, 87.84 percent has variation in Bayangam and 81.61 percent in Demdeng, followed by 67.11 percent in Poumougne. From the three districts, 32.10 percent of respondents in Poumougne perceived no variation in workers, followed by 18.39 and 12.16 percent, respectively, in Demdeng and Bayangam.

6.1.11 Farming Purpose

Figure 35: Farming purpose

Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

The study revealed that 73.28 percent of respondents are farming for mixed objectives, 13.77 percent for family needs, 3.64 percent for commercial purposes, and 9.31 percent for other reasons, as shown in Figure 35. Regarding the local level, 82.76 percent of respondents in Demdeng are farming for mixed objectives, followed by 70.37 and 65.82 percent, respectively, in Bayangam and Poumougne. Farming for family needs is practised by up to 26.58 percent of the respondents in the District of Poumougne, 9.88 percent in Bayangam, and 5.75 percent in Demdeng. Farming for commercial purposes is practised by only 7.41 percent of respondents in Bayangam, 2.53 percent in Poumougne, and 1.15 percent in Demdeng. Looking at farming for other reasons, 12.34 percent of respondents in Bayangam agreed with it, followed by 10.34 percent in Demdeng and 5.06 percent in Poumougne.

6.1.12 Common Crop Varieties Cultivated

Crop variety	Bayangam	Demdeng	Poumougne	Grand Total
Solanum potatoes	49,38%	27,59%	37,04%	37,75%
Yam	48,15%	51,72%	55,56%	51,81%
Maize	90,12%	95,40%	88,89%	91,57%
Beans	83,95%	93,10%	91,36%	89,56%
Groundnut	39,51%	72,41%	61,73%	58,23%
Cassava (Manihot)	48,15%	70,11%	62,96%	60,64%

Table 15: Common crop varieties cultivated
Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

From Table 15 above, most respondents had a farm size of less than 2ha, representing 60.80 percent of the total sample. From the table above, most respondents cultivated maize, representing 91.57 percent of the total sample. The other most cultivated crop was beans at 89.56 percent, cassava at 60.64 percent, groundnut at 58.23 percent, yam at 51.81 percent, and potatoes at 37.75 percent of total respondents. Regarding the district level, maize was the most cultivated in Demdeng, representing 95.40 percent, followed by 90.12 percent in Bayangam. In the district of Poumougne, beans were the most produced, representing 91.36 percent of respondents. Potatoes were primarily cultivated in the District of Bayangam and represented 49.38 percent of respondents.

6.1.13 Discussion

All smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-khi who participated in the study were distributed across all three districts. Of the overall participants, the female gender was more representative than the male gender. The reason could be that, in rural households, farming is dominated by the female gender. A similar finding has been observed in many investigations (Masamha, Thebe and Uzokwe, 2018; Leavens, Gugerty and Anderson, 2019; Ngetich *et al.*, 2022; Ingutia, 2021; Mohammed *et al.*, 2022). Following the same vein, Teklewol (2023) stated that in sub-Saharan African countries, females in rural areas are much more involved in agricultural practices than males. The same observation is also brought to light in India (Vijayalakshmy *et al.*, 2023) and in Nepal (Balayar and Mazur, 2022). On the same matter, Thomas, and Aloysius (2023) emphasised gender equity in the distribution of land for productive activities in Cameroon households. They argued that policy measures should enhance women's roles as agricultural producers concerning land ownership for practical purposes.

Regarding participation at the district level, female genders were more represented in Poumougne. The reason for the massive participation of the female gender may be the fact that the capital of the department of Koung-Khi is situated in the District of Poumougne, and it is there that the administrative offices and marketplace are located. An explanation for that is that the male gender in rural areas operates those activities in administrative offices and market services, while the female gender does household activities. The District of Bayangam, in contrast, has more male respondents. An explanation for that is that, as Bayangam is in the heart of the rural setting of the Koung-Khi department, the male gender is more engaged in farming activities. In contrast, the female gender is involved in household activities. The number of female participants in the District of Demdeng was slightly different, with female participants marginally higher than male participants.

The results showed that in the department of Koung-khi, females are more engaged in farming than males. In this context, females actively participate in farming more than their male counterparts. The observation suggests that women are essential in agricultural production, managing farms, making farming-related decisions, and contributing substantively to the farming workforce.

Women often play a central role in producing food for their households, ensuring food security and nutrition for their families (Uddin *et al.*, 2023). Women are actively involved in various farming activities in Cameroon (Foleu, Menzepe and Priso, 2022; Suh, Nyiawung and Abay, 2023), in India (Parveen, 2023) and generally in developing countries (Nwali *et al.*, 2022; Owonikoko *et al.*, 2023). The statement implies that women are significant in the agricultural sector and that their contribution should be acknowledged and valued. It is imperative to note that gender roles and female engagement in farming can vary significantly based on cultural, social, economic, and geographical factors. Additionally, efforts to promote gender equality in agriculture and recognise women's and men's contributions are essential for sustainable and equitable development within the agricultural sector.

Furthermore, the issue of gender ownership of land is raised. The issue has been addressed by Essengue (2022), who mentioned that women do not own land in tradition. The only property of the female gender is the one possessed by the husband. But this is not always the case where matrilineality is practised (Kooria, 2023). The smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-Khi have witnessed an increase in temperature and extreme events. The respondents' perceptions have varied according to the locality, which may be crucial for understanding farmers' willingness to invest in the issue of climate change's impact on food security. Smallholder farmers in the District of Bayangam witnessed a greater reduction in precipitation than storms and erosion. A likely explanation for this observation could be that the geographic variation of a region plays a crucial role in climate distribution. Some areas might be more prone to erosion because of their topography and soil characteristics, even with reduced precipitation. A supplementary explanation could be that natural climate variability, unrelated to climate change, can also cause fluctuations in precipitation and storm patterns over short periods.

These variations may not align with long-term climate change trends. Also, the high literacy of participants in that district is considered regarding the impact of education on the understanding and perception of climate change.

In the preceding chapters, the author delved into the intricate courting between weather exchange and food safety, uncovering the multifaceted influences of environmental shifts on agricultural systems and worldwide food supply. As those pivotal findings are revisited, it illuminates the profound significance of understanding and addressing demanding situations inside the broader context of sustainability and human well-being. Exploration found out that weather alternate is not risk but an urgent reality reshaping the very foundations of our food structures. Rising temperatures, erratic climate patterns, and changing precipitation degrees disrupt agricultural manufacturing, leading to yield losses, crop failures, and dwindling food reserves. From smallholder farms to sizeable agribusinesses, no nook of the globe remains untouched by means of the ripple results of a warming planet.

In this study, 57.89 percent of respondents have an academic qualification at the college level, which can affect their access to local climate evidence and knowledge. Academic qualifications associated with climate change knowledge in rural areas can significantly impact how communities understand, adapt to, and mitigate climate change effects (Adusu *et al.*, 2023). In this regard, Regalado *et al.* (2023) point out that insufficient access to climate information and knowledge in rural areas can be attributed to the suboptimal education level of smallholder farmers. Similar findings were supported by Olumba *et al.* (2023), who investigated awareness and perception of climate change among smallholder farmers in Nigeria and found that insufficient education results in inadequate planning, which leads to crop failure and endangers food security. Nyambo *et al.* (2022) also note that smallholder farmers in sub-Saharan Africa's lack of education and financial means significantly impedes their ability to make informed decisions regarding their agricultural practices, leading to poor harvests that threaten their food security.

The authors then suggest providing smallholder farmers with the necessary climate information to help them construct knowledgeable resolutions about crop planting and to help them understand the principles of intercropping and other agricultural techniques.

Regarding the smallholder farmers' perception of climate change in the study area, the results found that educated farmers were more informed about the change. This observation justifies the fact that educated individuals are more confident and willing to be informed (Marron, 2014). The idea is also supported by Belay *et al.* (2017), who stated that individuals with higher education levels have more access to and consideration of weather information, which allows them to be well-prepared to apply the proper measures to mitigate the risks. This observation aligns with the finding of Chimi *et al.* (2022), who used a case study to investigate climate change perception and local adaptation in a farming community in Cameroon and found that farmers with a high level of instruction are more prone to understand weather change and have a willingness to adapt to the threat.

In the same sense, Kongnso, Kongla and Ngala (2020) added that farmers' educational levels affect their participation in and understanding climate change. In the far north of the country, a similar finding was observed by Koguia *et al.* (2021) while investigating the discernment of weather variation and farmers' decisions to adapt in the Sudano-Sahelian Zone in Cameroon. These observations address the issue of climate change literacy in Africa, where Simpson *et al.* (2021) indicated that education and mobility are strong positive predictors of climate change literacy.

Though in this study, 57% are educated to college level and are informed about climate change, there is still just under half of the population who are not educated to this level, which impacts their ability to understand climate change education. The observation shows that awareness of climate change is not understood by all farmers, as 23.4 percent of farmers in the District of Poumougne were unaware of the threat. An alternative explanation for this observation could be the qualification level of participants, as up to forty percent of small farmers in the District of Poumougne did not have academic qualifications (see section 6.1.4). The observation aligns with the finding from Malyse (2021), who stated that a low level of education limited tomato farmers' efforts to get informed and adapt to climate change in the locality of Santa in west Cameroon. Though the percentage of unawareness is lower, it is essential to encourage farmers to prepare better and implement significant mitigation plans to enhance food security at the local level. Farmers may become more adaptable and invest in long-term adaptations if they understand climate change perceptions and local experiences.

In the districts of Poumougne and Demdeng, smallholder farmers perceived increased heat and rising temperatures. Considerable investigations have revealed the same observation (Molua, 2009; Yengoh, Hickler and Tchuinte, 2011; Awazi and Tchamba, 2018; Ngoe *et al.*, 2019; Awazi *et al.*, 2021; Bomdzele and Molua, 2023). The perception of climate extremes by farmers is different from location. Farmers mentioned during the focus group discussion that in the Koung-Khi department, the Bayangam district has received less rain than the other districts, though they are closer geographically.

The participants added that in the whole department, climate extremes induced the late onset and early cessation of the rainy season. During the last few years, the rain stopped earlier in the District of Bayangam than in the District of Demdeng, leaving crops immature. The same observation was made by Chiankem (2022), who stated that in the other part of the western region, they received an unproportioned quantity of rain in the last decade, causing some areas to receive more rain than others, which was never the case before. Chiankem (2022) added that harvest decreased in areas with less rain, which has induced farmers to sell a significant quantity of products. Because of the unproportionate distribution of rain in the region, Chiankem (2022) additionally mentions that specific plants, like potatoes, beans, maize, tomatoes, carrots, and cabbage, did not grow properly in the area with less rain. The quality of the product has worsened because it lacks water to grow properly, and the quantity of harvest has drastically decreased.

The price of the affected product has risen in the market, favouring the farmers who have harvested the best product quality. This situation then compromises the food security status of the rural sector, which should feed itself and feed the rest of the country and neighbouring countries. The impact induced a harvest reduction or crop failure, negatively impacting food security in the local community. Climate extremes caused a reduction in the quantity of harvest and the quality of products, leading to increased food prices on the local market and decreased farmer income. This has significantly affected local-on-local subsistence and imported crops as the country and its neighbouring countries rely massively on the western region's food production. Diba *et al.* (2022) witnessed an unproportionate distribution of rain in West Africa while analysing changes in compound rainfall and temperature extremes. Previous investigations from Kamga (2022) and Chimi *et al.* (2022) also found that seasonal changes increase food insecurity in rural populations due to their incomplete adaptive competencies. An investigation by Sani and Scholz (2022) on similar impacts in western and eastern Nigeria has a similar outcome.

This study found that climate information was available and effectively utilised by even the youngest smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-Khi. Based on this observation, it can be concluded that a positive trend emerging in rural environments, demonstrating an enhanced understanding of climate issues. Additionally, the study found a strong correlation between the perception of older farmers and their ability to adapt through environmental conservation, with their extensive farming experience and indigenous knowledge playing a crucial role in shaping their views.

The same finding was also made by Etwire, Koomson and Martey (2022), who revealed that the oldest farmers were shown to interact more with the environment, which raised their understanding and perception of climate change and their willingness to adapt.

6.2 Smallholders' Farmer's Awareness and Perception of Climate Change

6.2.1 Awareness about the Existence of Climate Change

Figure 36: Awareness about the existence of climate change
Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

The results in Figure 36 above revealed that 89.20 percent of respondents are aware of climate change, while 10.80 percent are not. At the district level, 98.77 percent are aware of climate change in Bayangam, 91.95 percent in Demdeng, and 76.83 percent in Poumougne. Of the three districts, 23.17 percent of respondents in Poumougne are unaware of climate change, followed by 8.05 percent and 1.23 percent in Demdeng and Bayangam, respectively.

6.2.2. Source of Information on Climate Change

Information source	Bayangam	Demdeng	Poumougne	Grand Total	Chi2
Television	61.54	68.52	66.67	65.56	0.6062 (0.739)
Radio	46.15	55.56	55.56	52.32	1.208 (0.547)
Government agencies	23.08	20.37	22.22	21.85	0.1187 (0.942)
Environment protection groups	15.38	11.11	15.56	13.91	0.5495 (0.760)
Libraries	03.85	01.85	2.22	02.65	0.4538 (0.797)
Friends and colleagues	17.31	20.37	28.89	21.85	2.003 (0.367)
Others	01.92	07.41	02.22	03.97	2.603 (0.272)

Table 16: Source of information on climate change

Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

From Table 16 above, 65.56 percent, representing most respondents, use television as a source of information on climate change. The other most used source of information on climate change was radio at 52.32 percent, government agencies with friends and colleagues at 21.85 percent, environmental protection groups at 13.91 percent, libraries at 2.65 percent, and others at 3.97 percent. Regarding the district level, television was the most used in Demdeng, representing 68.52 percent, 66.67 percent in Poumougne, and 61.54 percent in Bayangam.

Radio was the second most used source of information, with 55.56 percent in Demdeng and Poumougne and 46.15 percent in Bayangam. In the District of Poumougne, beans were the most cultivated, representing 91.36 percent of Bayangam.

6.2.3. Relationship between Source of Information and Farmers' Socioeconomic Characteristics

Source of information on CC	Sociodemographic characteristics				
	Gender	Age	Household size	Qualification	Experience
Television	17.8894*** (0.000)	24,444*** (0.000)	6.5931** (0.037)	24.9741** (0.000)	25.9133*** (0.000)
Radio	6.8915*** (0.009)	10.9919** (0.027)	4.8465* (0.089)	5.3143* (0.070)	6.8230 * (0.078)
Government Agencies	4.1036** (0.043)	3.9753 (0.409)	0.9253 (0.630)	9.9484*** (0.007)	8.9456 * * (0.030)
Environmental Activists	1.1444 (0.285)	2.3199 (0.677)	1.4393 (0.487)	6.7946** (0.033)	13.5237*** (0.004)
Library	0.0321 (0.858)	3.1850 (0.527)	2.9959 (0.224)	2.5535 (0.279)	0.5595 (0.906)
Friends and Colleagues	2.5057 (0.113)	4.4085 (0.354)	0.0278 (0.986)	1.3134 (0.519)	9.6383** (0.022)
Others	2.7613 * (0.097)	3.9838 (0.408)	6.0108** (0.050)	0.6878 (0.709)	1.9798 (0.577)

NB: *, **, ***= significant at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively

Table 17: Relationship between Source of information and farmers' socioeconomic characteristics
Source: Author computation with Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

Table 17 above shows that the use of television is strongly influenced by gender, age, and agricultural experience. At the same time, the study showed that we have a predominantly female population of 54 percent, which is relatively young; 50 percent were at most 45 years old, and around 23,60 percent had at least 20 years of experience in agriculture. All these characteristics reveal that farmers are younger and use innovative instruments like television to get information about climate change. This finding aligns with Iwuchukwu et al. (2016), who investigated the source of climate information for farmers in Imo State, Nigeria, and found that television is the best source of agricultural information in melon production. Unlike television, radio use is weakly influenced by the sociodemographic characteristics of farmers. Indeed, gender and, to a lesser extent, age are the factors that influence radio use at 1 percent and 5 percent, respectively. Radio is positioned more as a direct alternative to television. Many opt for radio in the absence of television. Furthermore, the methods of popularising, raising awareness, or transmitting information are almost identical. Through educational broadcasts, techniques for adapting or mitigating climate change are communicated to farmers.

Agricultural producers' education level strongly influences the source of information provided by government agencies. Along these lines, the study showed that more than half of the study population (approximately 60 percent) have at least a secondary school education. State agencies, in formulating new agricultural policies, are more oriented towards collaboration with structured organisations of educated people. A minimum level of education is required to assimilate and integrate information provided by state agents.

6.2.4. Causes of Climate Change

Climate change causes	Bayangam	Demdeng	Poumougne	Grand Total	Chi2
Burning of fossil fuels	41.38	26.39	34.55	34.58	3.913 (0.141)
Deforestation	87.36	73.61	92.73	84.11	9.681*** (0.008)
Greenhouse gas emissions	43.68	31.94	40.00	38.79	2.331 (0.312)
Atmospheric concentration of CO ₂	28.74	22.22	21.82	24.77	1.242 (0.537)
No idea	08.05	08.33	01.82	06.54	2.707 (0.258)
Other causes	01.15	04.17	01.82	02.34	1.659 (0.436)

Table 18: Causes of climate change
Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

Table 18 above shows that 84.11 percent, representing most respondents, have mentioned deforestation as the cause of climate change. The other causes of climate change mentioned were greenhouse gas emissions at 38.79 percent, burning fossil fuels at 34.58 percent, and the atmospheric concentration of CO₂ at 24.77 percent of total respondents. Regarding the district level, deforestation was the most mentioned in Poumougne, representing 92.73 percent, 87.36 percent in Bayangam, and 73.61 percent in Demdeng. Greenhouse gas emissions were the second most cited cause of climate change, with 43.68 percent in Bayangam, 40.00 percent in Poumougne, and 31.94 percent in Demdeng.

Climate change manifestations	Bayangam	Demdeng	Poumougne	Grand Total	Chi2
Heat / Rising temperature	58.62	60.49	59.76	59.60	0.062 (0.969)
Reduction in precipitation	63.22	56.79	57.32	59.20	0.897 (0.639)
Episodic precipitation	16.09	18.52	17.07	17.20	0.175 (0.916)
Changing in seasons	01.15	02.47	0.00	01.20	2.098 (0.350)
Erosion	08.05	09.88	07.32	08.40	0.368 (0.832)
Drought	0.00	0.00	01.22	00.40	2.057 (0.358)
Storms	06.90	13.58	17.07	12.40	4.178 (0.124)

Table 19: Climate change events witnessed
Source: Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

From Table 19 above, 59.60 percent represent most respondents who have witnessed heat or rising temperatures as manifestations of climate change. The other manifestations of climate change seen were a reduction in precipitation by 59.20 percent, storms by 12.40 percent, and erosion by 8.40 percent of total respondents. Regarding the district level, a reduction in precipitation was the most witnessed in Bayangam, representing 63.22 percent. Demdeng represented 68.52 percent, followed by 57.32 percent in Poumougne and 56.79 percent in Demdeng. Heat and rising temperatures were significantly witnessed at the commune level, with 60.49 percent in Demdeng, 59.76 percent in Poumougne, and 58.62 percent in Bayangam.

6.2.6. Perceived Effects of Climate Changes

The views of farmers concerning the influence of climate change on agriculture in rural locations are diverse and vary depending on the context.

Perceived effects	Bayangam	Demdeng	Poumougne	Grand Total
Prevalence of communicable diseases	31.03	50.62	37.80	39.60
Rising precipitation	47.13	41.98	30.49	40.00
Prevalence of diseases	45.98	59.26	41.46	48.80
Prevalence of Storms	49.43	54.32	36.59	46.80

Rising Temperature	58.62	61.73	58.54	59.69
Prevalence of soil erosion	39.08	40.74	30.49	36.80
Reduction in precipitation	58.62	56.79	43.90	53.20
Other effects	13.79	09.88	07.32	10.40

Table 20: Distribution of effects perceived by farmers

Source: Author computation with Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

Table 20 above shows that 59.69 percent, representing most smallholders, perceived rising temperatures as the effect of climate change. The observation also indicates that 53.20 percent mentioned a reduction in precipitation, 48.80 percent a prevalence of diseases, 46.80 percent a prevalence of storms, 40.00 percent rising precipitation, and 36.80 percent a prevalence of soil erosion. At the district level, the rising temperature of 61.73 percent was the most perceived in Demdeng, followed by 58.62 percent in Bayangam and 58.54 percent in Poumougne. Additionally, the reduction in precipitation was also pointed out as a perceived effect by 58.62 percent in Bayangam, 56.79 percent in Demdeng, and 43.90 percent in Poumougne.

6.2.7. Raising Sensitisation about Climate Change

Figure 37: Sensitisation of climate change

Source: Author computation with Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

Faced with the increasingly present phenomenon of climate change, all stakeholders are developing strategies to overcome the threat, either through adaptation or mitigation. From the results of this study, Figure 37 above reveals that 64.68 percent of smallholder farmers are not sensitised about climate change, and 35.32 are sensitised. That means most smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-Khi still need to be sensitised about the risks and impact of climate change. Regarding the district level, Poumougne and Demdeng reflect the general reality of the low sensitisation rate at 76.79 percent and 71.23 percent, respectively. The locality of Bayangam is an exception, with a high proportion of sensitised smallholder farmers at 51.33 percent.

The factor that can be explained is that there is a substantial presence of agricultural extension and promotion structures. It could also relate to the high educational level of smallholder farmers, as the study revealed that smallholder farmers in Bayangam were more educated.

6.2.8. Topic of Climate Change Sensitization

The topic of Climate Change sensitisation	Bayangam	Demdeng	Poumougne	Grand Total
Awareness on Climate change and food security	60.00	64.00	64.00	62.50
Conservation of mangroves	20.00	48.00	28.00	31.25
Household Waste management	66.67	60.00	68.00	65.00
Reforestation	86.67	80.00	80.00	82.50
Disaster risk management	13.33	16.00	24.00	17.50
Forest conservation	30.00	32.00	20.00	27.50
Climate change knowledge	33.33	44.00	24.00	33.75
Adaptation strategies	33.33	36.00	28.00	32.50

Table 21: Topic of Climate Change Sensitization

Source: Author Computation with Data collected through a survey during Fieldwork in districts

From Table 21 above, 82.50, representing the most investigated, have attended climate change sensitisation on reforestation, 65.00 percent on waste management, 62.50 percent on climate change and food security, 33.75 percent on climate change knowledge, 32.50 percent on adaptation strategies, 31.25 percent on conservation of mangroves, 27.50 percent on forest conservation, and 17.50 percent on disaster risk management. Regarding the district level, 86.67 percent of smallholder farmers were most sensitised to reforestation in Bayangam, followed by 64.00 percent in Poumougne and Demdeng. Sensitisation on reforestation and waste management was also considerable in Poumougne at 68.00 percent, Bayangam at 66.67 percent, and Demdeng at 60.00 percent. Additionally, the results at the district level show that 64.00 percent of smallholder farmers in Demdeng and Poumougne were sensitised to climate change and food security, followed by 60.00 percent in Bayangam. Among the diversity of topics related to climate change sensitisation, disaster risk management was the least requested topic, representing only 17.50 percent.

6.2.9. Discussion

6.2.9.1 Source of Climate Information in the Koung-Khi Department

From this study, we observe that television and radio are significant sources of climate information for smallholder farmers. This observation aligns with Nain *et al.* (2015) who mentioned that media is essential for transmitting climate information to rural agricultural partitioners. The authors also point out that the population cannot disseminate certain information, thus the media's appropriate role in promoting information.

According to several authors, the media occupies a preeminent position in fostering communication in rural areas by acting as an interface to disseminate knowledge, provide a platform for debates, introduce new ideas, and equip individuals with skills necessary for fostering a better living environment (Abubakar, Ango and Buhari, 2010; Choudhury, 2011; Kapoor, 2011; Obidike, 2011).

Also, Ango *et al.* (2013) argue that the media were essential precursors to the rapid rise in the development of agricultural programmes in developed countries. They are "therefore important elements in agricultural and rural development" (Mugwisi, 2015), just as they constitute an essential component of climate information sources. The result of this study reveals that it is evident that smallholder farmers no longer request books or any other physical written document to get informed about climate change, as only 2.65 percent of total respondents used the library.

6.2.9.2 Source of Information and Farmers' Socioeconomic Characteristics

Based on the hypothesis that the sources used by farmers are different in the study area, it is evident that there is a diversity of factors likely to influence the source of information. These factors may be linked to sociodemographic characteristics.

Fongang *et al.* (2019) noted that the potential of radio is that it draws still-isolated farmers to specialists and encourages them to participate in radio programmes.

Moreover, Fouepe *et al.* (2019) added that the Western region of Cameroon is covered by 24 radio channels, four of which broadcast from the Menoua department. All participate daily in promoting agricultural information, extension, and advice, underscoring the authors. Based on the general population census in 2008 in Malawi, Chapota *et al.* (2014) state that the proportion of households with a radio at their disposal is 64.1 percent on average. According to Iwuchukwu *et al.* (2016), in terms of melon production, their work reveals that radio is the second-best source of information for farmers in Enugu State, Nigeria, with an average annual proportion of 46.7 percent. Anseur (2009) points out that radio is regularly used in Algeria only during agricultural seasons. This author underlines that the action of national radios and 32 local channels is carried out monthly through a broadcast when it is necessary to initiate debates around an essential development subject. Also, four to five-minute spots or flashes are broadcast to provide technical advice and inform producers about "incentive measures and epizootic problems."

From this investigation, about 75 percent of farmers cite the staff of state agricultural extension services as the most important source of information.

Opara (2008) and Vidanapathirana (2012) note that the results of their work highlight the desire of extension services to permanently identify the sources of agricultural information preferred or which are best used as what will enable them to equip the farmers with quality information. All the same, there is a mixed connotation in some instances.

Thus, in the rural Pakistani community, the action of state agencies is so poorly perceived due to their repeated absences on the ground that Yaseen et al. (2016) propose that the government redefine their tasks and set up a system of repression likely to force them to carry out the work assigned to them. Whether environmental activists or family and friends, the emphasis is on experience in farming. This demonstrates that they focus more on sharing experiences, endogenous initiatives, and the relationship between knowledge and trust.

6.2.9.3 Causes of Climate Change

Across the three localities investigated (Poumougne, Bayangam, Demdeng), deforestation constitutes the leading cause of climate change, 92.73, 87.36, and 73.61 percent, respectively. The thoughts of smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-Khi are in line with everyday observations relating to the cause of climate change. The destruction of flora through deforestation to make way for farms, pastures, or other reasons produces greenhouse gas emissions (Pearce and Brown, 2023). Indeed, trees, once cut, release the carbon they have stored. Every year, around 12 million hectares of forest are destroyed (Shebitz *et al.*, 2023). Because forests absorb carbon dioxide, their destruction also limits nature's ability to prevent atmospheric emissions (Pearce and Brown, 2023). Approximately one-quarter of global greenhouse gas emissions result from deforestation, agriculture, and other land-use alterations (Shebitz *et al.*, 2023). Burning fossil fuels to produce electricity and heat is a substantial source of global emissions (Algarni et al., 2023).

Globally, just over a quarter of electricity comes from renewable sources (wind, solar and others), which, unlike fossil fuels, emit little or no greenhouse gases or pollutants in the air (Algarni *et al.*, 2023). Most of this concentration is attributable to vehicles due to the combustion of petroleum-derived products, such as gasoline, in internal combustion engines (Chiavola, Palmieri and Cavallo, 2023). However, emissions from ships and aircraft continue to grow (Algarni *et al.*, 2023). The energy-related carbon dioxide emissions generated by transportation account for almost a quarter of the global total, and trends suggest that energy consumption in this sector will rise significantly in the years ahead (Chiavola, Palmieri and Cavallo, 2023).

The manifestation of climate change in rural areas can be observed through the disturbances it induces or its effects on agricultural practices (Djihouessi et al., 2022). This phenomenon harms agriculture, livestock breeding, and the environment in general. It originates from devastating floods in the rainy season, which contrasts with increasingly long and harsh dry seasons, with extreme temperatures leading to failure to control incidental bushfires or consciously initiated by certain breeders and farmers (Djihouessi *et al.*, 2022).

Beyond the usual considerations, this study explored farmers' perceptions of climate change events at the local scale. Like the finding of Klusak *et al.* (2023) while exploring rural farmers' perceptions of climate change, numerous farmers in the rural settings of Koung-Khi believe that climate change mainly results in higher temperatures. Indeed, the agricultural sector is particularly exposed to repeated droughts (Sawadogo, 2022). One of the most apparent consequences of the drought in the department of Koung-Khi is the topographical structure of the area, which is made of high and lowlands like other places in the western region. This causes the highlands to be more exposed to droughts during the dry season and erosion while receiving heavy rain. The lowlands, on the other hand, faced massive floods. Several authors worldwide have witnessed this phenomenon, for instance, in Somalia by Ahmed *et al.* (2022), Bangladesh by Cherinet, Tadesse and Abebe (2022), India by Nayak *et al.* (2023), and Northwest Italy by Cremonini *et al.* (2023). Ahmed *et al.* (2022) supports the notion that, in the highlands, soil becomes very sensitive to erosion, which leads to significant soil losses and accelerated loss of fertility. Cherinet, Tadesse and Abebe (2022) conclude from their investigation on drought and flood extreme events and management strategies in Ethiopia that farmers in the highlands are witnessing a significant drop in yield and biomass; the appearance of sterile soils and continued degradation of arable land through the highlands represent the main factors in production. Nseka *et al.* (2022) also indicate that farmers in the Highlands of Southwestern Uganda are more disposed to landslide occurrences.

6.3. Changes in Weather Patterns and Food Crop Production in the Study Area

6.3.1. Trend of Precipitation in the Study Area between 2005 and 2022

Figure 38 below shows the precipitation trends in the study area between 2005 and 2022. Understanding the precipitation trend is essential for managing water resources and predicting potential impacts on the environment and human activities, such as agriculture.

Figure 38: Trend of precipitation between 2005 and 2022 in mm/year
 Source: Author computation with Data collected at the regional delegation of

The precipitation trend refers to the overall tendency of time series data to increase (upward), decrease (downward), or remain stable (neutral) (Mersin *et al.*, 2022). Based on the figure 38 above, it is apparent that the amount of precipitation has varied significantly over the years. The rainfall has continuously decreased from 1800mm in 2006 to 1200mm in 2012. The figure 38 shows that rainfall patterns have witnessed severe fluctuations between 2005 and 2022, reaching their minimal point in 2015 (1123.8 mm/year). When they noticed a drastic increase to 1700mm in 2013, it dropped to 1100mm in 2015, increased again to 1800mm in 2019 and later dropped to 1700mm in 2021. Overall, the figure 38 shows that the study area experiences fluctuation in precipitation levels, and there is a need to monitor and manage water resources to ensure sustainability.

6.3.1.1. The Trend of the Length of the Rainy Season

Figure 39 below shows the trend in the length of the rainy season in the study area.

Figure 39: Trend of the length of rainy season between 2005 and 2022

Source: Author computation with Data collected at the regional delegation of MINADER

The figure 39 above shows that the length of the rainy season has decreased extensively across the years, from 150 days of rain in 2006 to 110 days in 2022. This result suggests that climate change is relevant to the length of the rainy season in the study area. The rainy season's length is considered a second indicator of changes in meteorological conditions in our study. Its evolution over time has been analysed, and the results are presented.

6.3.1.2. Changes in Meteorological Conditions and Production of Staple Foods

The aim of the study was also to reveal the effects of changes in meteorological conditions on the production of staple foods. To attain this objective, a log-log Cobb-Douglas production function was used, wherein the inputs were precipitation, length of rainy season, and surface area cultivated for the various staple crops identified (maize, beans, and potatoes), and parameters were estimated using the ordinary least squares method.

Table 21 below shows the results of the descriptive statistics of meteorological conditions and the investigated staple foods. The data used in Table 21 below were collected under the statistical direction of the ministry of agriculture and rural development (see Appendices).

Variable	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Precipitation (mm/year)	1558.402	223.903	1123.8	1838.2
Length of rainy season (days/year)	124.438	25.409	92	165
Potatoes production (tons/years)	5607.5	4840.694	920	12100
surface area for potato production (ha/year)	538.15	162.264	105.4	730
Beans production (tons/years)	3714.294	3903.919	310.7	15000
surface area for Beans production (ha/year)	2711.606	4983.115	289	17647
Maize production (tons/years)	26365.49	62251.11	2305	258654.8
surface area for maize production (ha/year)	5699.313	3809396	1250	16667

Table 22: Descriptive statistics of explanatory variables and staple food
Source: Author computation with Data collected at the regional delegation of MINADER

Based on the descriptive statistics in the table above, we notice that the mean precipitation is 1558.402 mm/year, with a standard deviation of 223.903 mm/year. This shows that there is some variation in annual precipitation levels. Higher precipitation levels can benefit crop growth, but extreme rainfall can lead to flooding and soil erosion. The mean length of the rainy season is 124.438 days/year, with a standard deviation of 25.409 days/year. This suggests some variability in the duration of the rainy season. A shorter rainy season may cause water stress for crops, while a more extended rainy season may increase the risk of diseases and pests. The mean potato production is 5607.5 tons/year, with a standard deviation of 4840.694 tons/year. A wide range of potato production levels shows potential challenges in maintaining consistent yields because of climate variability.

The mean surface area for potato production is 538.15 ha/year, with a standard deviation of 162.264 ha/year. This suggests variations in the land area dedicated to potato cultivation may be influenced by factors such as the availability of suitable land and market demand.

The mean bean production is 3714.294 tons/year, with a standard deviation of 3903.919 tons/year. Like potatoes, there is considerable variation in bean production levels, highlighting potential vulnerabilities to climate change impacts.

The mean surface area for bean production is 2711.606 ha/year, with a standard deviation of 4983.115 ha/year. This shows that there are variations in the land area dedicated to bean cultivation as well. Finally, for maize production, the mean maize production is 26365.49 tons/year, with a significant standard deviation of 62251.11 tons/year. This shows substantial variability in maize yields over time because of various factors, including climate change impacts. The mean surface area for maize production is 5699.313 ha/year, with a substantial standard deviation of 3809396 ha/year. This suggests significant variations in the land area used for maize cultivation.

6.3.1.3. Effect of Explanatory Variables on Beans Production

Table 23 below presents the effects of explanatory variables on bean production in the study area.

Dependent variable (ln beans production)		
Explanatory variables	Coefficient	P> z
Ln precipitation	-1.902* (1.098)	0.109
Ln length of rainy season (days/year)	4.482*** (0.547)	0.000
Ln surface cultivated (ha/years)	0.649*** (0.137)	0.000
Constant	-4.237 (9.819)	0.674
Number of Observations	16	
F (3, 12)	43,00	
Prob > F	0.0000	
R-Squared	0.7812	
Mean VIF	1.30	

NB: *. **. ***= significant at 10%. 5% and 1%, respectively.

F in Brackets = Robust Standard Error

Table 23: Changes in explanatory variables and beans production

Source: Author computation with Data collected at the regional delegation of MINADER

The results presented in Table 23 above show that three key factors influence the production of beans in the study area: the length of precipitation, the length of the rainy season, and the surface area cultivated.

To estimate the effects of meteorological conditions on bean production, the researcher used a log-log Cobb-Douglas production function, and parameters were estimated using the ordinary least squares (OLS) method. The results show that the variables fit the model adequately, given the f-statistic of 43, a Prob>F of 0.000 and the R-squared of 0.7812. The mean-variance inflation factor (VIF), which stands at 1.30, reveals no multicollinearity between the independent variables. Regarding the results presented in Table 22, a 1% increase in precipitation leads to a 1.9 percent reduction in bean production. Hence, there is an inverse relationship between precipitation rate and bean production. As for the length of the rainy season, the coefficient shows that a 1 percent increase in the length of the rainy season leads to a 4.48 percent increase in bean production. Likewise, the coefficient for surface cultivation shows that a 1 percent increase in surface cultivation leads to a 0.65 percent increase in bean production.

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

The variance inflation factor (VIF) measures the extent to which the variance of the estimated regression coefficients is increased because of multicollinearity among the independent variables. A VIF value of 1 shows no multicollinearity, while values above 3 suggest increasing levels of multicollinearity.

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
ln _{days_rain}	1.38	0.723646
ln _{Precip}	1.26	0.790713
ln _{SurfBns}	1.25	0.798008
Mean VIF	1.3	

Table 24: Caption of Variance Inflation Factor

Source: Author computation with Data collected at the regional delegation of MINADER

As shown in Table 24, all the VIF values are below 2, showing no significant multicollinearity between the independent variables in the model. This means that each independent variable uniquely contributes to the prediction of bean production in the study area. Overall, the results suggest the model is reliable and can predict potato production in the study area based on climate variables. However, it is essential to note that the model only explains 78.12 percent of the variation in bean production, leaving room for other factors to influence the outcome.

6.3.1.4. Effects of Explanatory Variables on maize Production

Table 25 below shows the relationship between maize production and meteorological conditions in the study area.

Dependent variable (ln maize production)		
Explanatory variables	Coefficient	P> z
Ln precipitation	-2.834 (0.198)	0.216
Ln length of rainy season (days/year)	-0.526 (2.191)	0.484
Ln surface cultivated (ha/years)	0.745*** (0.005)	0.003
Constant	26.373 (18.611)	0.182
Number of Observations	16	
F (3, 12)	11.36	
Prob > F	0.0008	
R-Squared	0.6616	
Mean VIF	1.28	

NB: *. **. ***= significant at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively. *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01
F in Brackets = Robust Standard Error

Table 25: Changes in explanatory variables and maize production

Source: Author computation with Data collected at the regional delegation of MINADER

Table 25 shows the effects of changes in explanatory variables on maize production.

The overall results are statistically significant given the Prob>F, which is 0.0008, which shows that the model is effective at a 1 percent level. The R-squared of 0.6616 shows that 66.16 percent of variations in maize production are caused by the variables in the model. The table above shows that the explanatory variables have distinct impacts on maize production based on the regression analysis results. The coefficient for length precipitation is -2.834, but the p-value (P>|z|) is 0.216, which suggests that the relationship between precipitation and maize production is not statistically significant. This means that changes in precipitation may not considerably impact maize production in the study area. Similarly, the coefficient for the length of the rainy season is -0.526, with a p-value of 0.484. Again, this shows that the relationship between the length of the rainy season and maize production is not statistically significant.

On the other hand, surface cultivation has a coefficient of 0.745 with a p-value of 0.003, showing a statistically significant positive relationship between surface cultivation and maize production. This suggests that increased surface area cultivated can lead to higher maize production. This relationship is meaningful at 1 percent.

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
ln _{days_rain}	1.16	0.861403
ln _{Precip}	1.37	0.731281
ln _{SurfMiaze}	1.31	0.762297
Mean VIF	1.28	

Table 26: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for Maize Production

Source: Author computation with Data collected at the regional delegation of MINADER

The VIF values in Table 26 above for the three independent variables (Precipitation, Surface cultivated, and days of rain) are below 2, showing no significant multicollinearity between them.

Each meteorological condition contributes unique information to the prediction of maize production in the study area. The mean VIF value (1.28) also shows that the model is reliable, as no evidence of high multicollinearity could lead to unstable or unreliable estimates of the coefficients.

6.3.1.5. Effects of Explanatory Variables on Potatoes Production

Dependent variable (ln potatoes production)		
Explanatory variables	Coefficient	P> z
Ln precipitation	-3.074** (1.395)	0.048
Ln length of rainy season (days/year)	-2.952*** (0.854)	0.005
Ln surface cultivated (ha/years)	0.595*** (0.163)	0.003
Constant	41.232*** (8.315)	0.000
Number of Observations	16	
F (3, 12)	17.78	
Prob > F	0.0001	
R-Squared	0.7499	
Mean VIF	1.23	

NB: *, **, ***= significant at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively.

F in Brackets = Robust Standard Error

Table 27: Changes in explanatory variables and Potato production

Source: Author computation with Data collected at the regional delegation of MINADER

The results presented in Table 27 highlight the effects of changes in meteorological conditions and potato production based on data obtained between 2006 and 2021.

With a Prob>F of 0.0001, the model's overall results are statistically significant, signifying its 1 percent level of significance. The R-squared of 0.7499 shows that 74.99 percent of variations in potato production are explained by the variables included in the model. The results obtained here show the changes in meteorological conditions are negatively linked to potato production, given the negative signs attached to their coefficients. The coefficient for precipitation shows that a 1 percent increase in precipitation rate leads to a 3.07 percent reduction in potato production. Likewise, the coefficient of the length of the rainy season suggests that a 1 percent increase in the length of the rainy season is associated with a 2.95 percent reduction in potato production. These results are both significant at a 1 percent level of significance. The results show that the surface area cultivated positively affects potato production. The coefficient indicates that a 1 percent increase in surface area increases potato production by 0.59 percent. Specifically, the length of the rainy season and precipitation have a negative effect on potato production, while the surface area cultivated has a positive effect, implying that an increase in the length of the rainy season and precipitation will lead to a decrease in potato production, while an increase in the surface area cultivated will lead to an increase in potato production. The R-squared value of 0.7499 shows that the model explains up to 74.99 percent of the variation in potato production.

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
ln _{days_rain}	1.32	0.757347
ln _{Precip}	1.20	0.836692
ln _{SurfMiaze}	1.17	0.852735
Mean VIF	1.23	

Table 28: Variance inflation factor (VIF) for Potato Production

Source: Author computation with Data collected at the regional delegation of MINADER

The VIF values for the three independent variables (days of rain, precipitation, and surface cultivated) are all below 2, ranging from 1.17 to 1.32, as shown in Table 28.

This suggests that there is minimal multicollinearity among these variables in the regression model, showing that there is no significant multicollinearity between them.

This means that each independent variable contributes unique information to predicting potato production in the study area based on meteorological conditions.

The low VIF (mean VIF 1.23) value also suggests that the model is reliable, as no evidence of high multicollinearity could lead to unstable or unreliable estimates of the coefficients. It suggests the model is a good starting point for predicting potato production in the study area.

6.4. Impact of Climate Change on Food Availability, Accessibility, and Utilisation

Climate change has far-reaching impacts on various aspects of life, including food security, and might interrupt progress toward a world without hunger (Zahoor and Mushtaq, 2023). The results below illustrate the impact of climate change on the different dimensions of food security (availability, accessibility, and utilisation). A multinomial logit regression was used to determine if climate change impacts food availability, access, and utilisation. Separate regression equations were estimated regarding the three independent variables (food availability, food accessibility and food utilisation index).

6.4.1. Impact of Climate Change on Food Availability for Smallholder Farmers

The average impact of climate change on food availability index (FAvI) = 3.44. Food security is a complex issue involving production, distribution, access, and utilisation. Figure 40 below shows the impact of climate change on food availability for smallholder farmers' households.

Figure 40: Impact of climate change on food availability
 Source: Author computation with Data collected at the regional delegation of MINADER

From Figure 40 presented above, most of the smallholder farmers surveyed, 62.45 percent, reported that climate change severely impacts their food availability. This result shows that the impact of climate change on food availability is significant. This could be due to rising temperatures, changes in precipitation patterns, and extreme weather events all affecting yield and food production in the study area, leading to food shortages and an increase in food prices, which affect disproportionately vulnerable populations such as smallholder farmers by reducing the food available for consumption.

The table 28 below presents the results of a logistic regression analysis model with several explanatory variables used to explain the impact of climate change on the food availability index.

Explanatory variables	Weak Impact		Moderate Impact		Severe Impact (ref)
	Rrr	P> z	Rrr	P> z	
Number of CC events witnessed	0.879 (0.186)	0.543	1.297 (0.249)	0.176	
Number of CC effects witnessed	0.908 (0.128)	0.494	0.807** (0.080)	0.031	
Number of adaptation strategies used	0.797*** (0.067)	0.008	1.452** (0.213)	0.011	
Experience in farming	0.999 (0.001)	0.168	0.999 (0.0003)	0.722	
Farm size	0.999 (0.101)	0.993	1.044 (0.071)	0.528	
Gender (0= female; 1=male)	7.725*** (4.372)	0.000	1.424 (0.602)	0.403	
Academic qualification	3.047*** (1.243)	0.006	1.265 (0.368)	0.418	
Varieties cultivated	0.249*** (0.122)	0.005	0.769 (0.273)	0.461	
Constant	1.224 (1.001)	0.806	0.016*** (0.022)	0.003	
Number of observations	242				
Wald chi2 (16)	41.35				
Prob > chi2	0.0005				
Pseudo R2	0.1094				
Log pseudo-likelihood	-189.59755				

Note: _cons estimate baseline relative risk for each outcome.

NB: *, **, ***= significant at 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively.

F in Brackets = Robust Standard Error.

Table 29: Climate change effects on food availability index

Source: Author computation with Data collected at the regional delegation of MINADER

Table 29 above shows the results of the analysis linking climate change and the food availability index. As mentioned earlier, a multinomial logit regression is used to estimate the effects of climate change on the food availability index.

The overall results are statistically significant at a 1 percent significance level with a Wald chi (2) of 41.35, a pseudo-R2 of 0.194, and a Prob>chi2 of 0.0005. The findings reveal that the number of climate change events witnessed has no significant effect on the food availability index.

Conversely, the quantity of climate change effects experienced by a farm household significantly impacts the food availability index. It can be deduced that a rise in the occurrence of climate change effects lowers the likelihood of experiencing a moderate impact as opposed to a severe one.

Also, the number of climate change adaptation strategies used significantly affects the food availability index. Specifically, increasing the number of adaptation strategies used reduces the chances of a relative risk ratio in favour of having a weak impact instead of a severe impact by 0.797. In contrast, a rise in the quantity of adaptation strategies will cause the relative risk ratio of experiencing a moderate impact, instead of a severe impact, to increase by 1.452. This result is significant at a 5 percent level. The results in the table also show that male-headed households are more likely to experience a weak impact relative to female-headed households. The relative risk ratio (rrr) for suffering a weak impact rather than a severe impact is 7.72 times greater for male than female-headed farmers. Likewise, the academic coefficient with a rr of 3.04 shows that the higher the educational qualification, the higher the chances of witnessing a weak impact rather than a severe impact.

Conversely, an increase in crop varieties cultivated reduces the relative risk ratio by 0.25, showing a lower susceptibility to weak impacts. Because of climate change, farmers cultivating a wider range of crops are more vulnerable to food availability challenges.

6.4.2. Impact of Climate Change on Food Access for Smallholder Households

The average impact of climate change on food accessibility index (FAI) = 3.46. Food access is one dimension of food security. It is the state where people have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and preferences for an active and healthy life (FAO, 1996). Figure 41 below illustrates the impact of climate change on food access for smallholder farmers in the study area.

Figure 41: Impact of climate change on food accessibility

Source: Author computation with Data collected through survey during fieldwork in districts.

From the results presented in Figure 41 above, it is noticed that only 1.22 percent of the farmers surveyed in the study area reported that climate change had no impact on food access in their households, and 62.04 percent of the total smallholder farmers surveyed reported climate change had a severe impact on food access in their households. One hanging revelation from our qualitative findings resonates profoundly with the statement that intense weather occasions should lead to crop screw-ups, decreased agricultural productivity, and accelerated food costs. Across diverse geographical contexts, from the department of koun-g-khi, the researchers encountered views of farmers grappling with the devastating aftermath of unrelenting droughts, torrential floods, and unpredictable storms.

In addition, climate change has the potential to disrupt conventional farming techniques and affect water availability, resulting in further consequences for farmers and their families' access to food.

Explanatory variables	Weak Impact		Moderate Impact		Severe Impact (ref)
	Rrr	P> z	Rrr	P> z	
Number of CC events witnessed	0.713 (0.168)	0.152	1.353* (0.253)	0.105	
Number of CC effects witnessed	0.955 (0.099)	0.701	0.897** (0.078)	0.027	
Number of adaptation strategies used	0.979 (0.993)	0.839	1.145* (0.089)	0.083	
Experience in farming	0.997 (0.011)	0.823	0.999 (0.0003)	0.771	
Farm size	0.904 (0.114)	0.425	1.016 (0.065)	0.802	
Gender (0= female; 1=male)	0.825 (0.467)	0.734	0.730 (0.283)	0.418	
Academic qualification	3.518*** (1.384)	0.001	0.747 (0.229)	0.340	
Varieties cultivated	0.401** (0.156)	0.019	1.186 (0.452)	0.655	
Constant	0.398 (0.405)	0.366	0.206** (0.150)	0.030	

Number of observations	242		
Wald chi2 (16)	24.20		
Prob > chi2	0.0853		
Pseudo R2	0.0639		
Log pseudo-likelihood	-200.29008		

Note: _cons estimate baseline relative risk for each outcome.

NB: * ** ***= significant at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively.

F in Brackets = Robust Standard Error.

Table 30: Climate change effects on food accessibility index

Source: Author computation with Data collected through survey during fieldwork in districts.

An analysis of the effects of climate change on food accessibility shown in Table 30 shows that the number of climate change events witnessed, the number of climate change effects witnessed, and the number of climate change adaptation strategies used all significantly affect food accessibility. The number of climate change events and the number of adaptation strategies used increase the likelihood of suffering a moderate impact of climate change on food accessibility, with relative risk ratios (rrr) of 1.35 and 1.14, respectively. Conversely, the outcomes show that reducing the number of climate change effects endured decreases the relative risk ratio, favouring the likelihood of moderate rather than severe impacts of climate change on food accessibility. Additional factors that influence the food accessibility index are academic qualification and the number of varieties of crops cultivated.

6.4.3. Impact of Climate Change on Food Utilisation by Smallholder Households

The average impact of climate change on food utilisation index (FUI) = 3.14. Figure 42 illustrates the impact of climate change on food utilisation by smallholder households in the study area.

Figure 42: Impact of climate change on food utilisation

Source: Author computation with Data collected through survey during fieldwork in districts.

From the results illustrated in Figure 42 above, most of the farmers surveyed (55.88 percent) reported that climate change had a severe impact on food utilisation. This could be because they have observed changes in their ability to access and use food because of climate-related factors. It is important to note here that, unlike the other dimensions of food security, some farmers, although very few, reported that climate change had no impact on the utilisation of food in their households, which could be because of specific adaptation strategies implemented by these farmers to help mitigate the effects of climate change.

Explanatory variables	Weak Impact		Moderate Impact		Severe impact (ref)
	Rrr	P> z	rrr	P> z	
Number of CC events witnessed	1.173 (0.308)	0.543	1.549* (0.362)	0.061	
Number of CC effects witnessed	0.709** (0.112)	0.030	0.722*** (0.081)	0.004	
Number of adaptation strategies used	0.765** (0.089)	0.023	1.308** (0.152)	0.021	
Experience in farming	0.999 (0.0003)	0.156	1.000 (0.0003)	0.980	
Farm size	1.003 (0.089)	0.972	0.888 (0.115)	0.362	
Gender (0= female; 1=male)	67.102*** (63.271)	0.000	0.202** (0.1302)	0.013	
Academic qualification	24.262*** (16.196)	0.000	0.494 (0.219)	0.112	
Varieties cultivated	0.0007*** (0.0007)	0.000	8.081*** (6.534)	0.010	
Constant	346.694*** (522.462)	0.000	0.011*** (0.015)	0.001	
Number of observations	242				
Wald chi2 (16)	91.65				
Prob > chi2	0.0000				
Pseudo R2	0.3932				
Log pseudo-likelihood	-148.39776				

Note: _cons estimate baseline relative risk for each outcome.

NB: *. **. ***= significant at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively.

F in Brackets = Robust Standard Error.

Table 31: Climate change effects of food utilisation index

Source: Author computation with Data collected through survey during fieldwork in districts

As presented in Table 31 above, analyses of the effects of climate change on the food utilisation index show that the number of climate change events witnessed, the number of climate change effects witnessed, and the number of climate change adaptation strategies used all significantly affect food utilisation. The number of climate change events and the number of adaptation strategies used increase the likelihood of suffering a moderate impact of climate change on food availability, with relative risk ratios of 1.54 and 1.308, respectively.

Conversely, the outcomes show that experiencing a more significant number of climate change effects lowers the relative risk ratio for experiencing a severe impact on food utilisation while elevating the relative risk ratio for encountering a moderate impact as opposed to a severe one.

An additional factor that influences the food utilisation index is the gender of the household head, the academic qualification, and the number of varieties of crops cultivated.

6.5. Adaptations and Challenges among Farmers

6.5.1. Smallholders' Adaptation Strategies to Climate Change

Table 31 below presents the efficiency of adaptation strategies used by smallholder farmers in the study area. The Adaptation Strategy Index (ASI) is calculated and ranked.

The following formula from Uddin et al. (2014) was applied to calculate the adaptation strategy index (ASI).

$$ASI = AS_n \times 0 + AS_l \times 1 + AS_m \times 2 + AS_h \times 3$$

where, ASI = Adaptation Strategy Index

AS_n = frequency of smallholder farmers that rate adaptation strategy as having no application.

AS_l = frequency of smallholder farmers that rate adaptation strategy as having a low application.

AS_m = frequency of smallholder farmers that rate adaptation strategy as having a moderate application.

AS_h = frequency of smallholder farmers that rate adaptation strategy as having a high application.

Adaptation Strategies	Bayangam N=82 (32.24)					Demdeng N=87 (34.8)					Poumougne N=83 (32.8)					Total sample N=252 (100)					Chi2 (p-value)				
	High	Medium	Low	No	ASI	ASI Ranking	High	Medium	Low	No	ASI	ASI Ranking	High	Medium	Low	No	ASI	ASI Ranking	High	Medium		Low	No	ASI	ASI Ranking
-Growing short-lived crops	41.56	38.36	06.49	15.58	207.89	5	30.49	50.00	10.98	08.54	202.45	9	44.44	30.56	05.56	19.44	111.12	10	38.53	39.39	07.79	14.29	202.16	8	11.187* (0.083)
-Practice crop rotation	52.62	24.64	13.04	08.70	220.18	2	46.15	21.79	20.51	11.54	202.48	8	63.08	20.00	10.77	06.15	240.01	5	53.77	22.17	15.09	08.96	220.53	5	5.891 (0.435)
-Soil conservation techniques	30.16	30.16	15.87	23.81	166.67	10	28.40	37.04	14.81	19.75	174.09	10	39.68	28.57	12.70	19.05	188.88	8	32.31	32.37	14.49	20.77	176.16	9	3.091 (0.797)
-Practice intercropping	37.68	39.13	04.35	18.84	195.65	8	46.25	37.50	10.00	06.25	223.75	6	65.08	20.63	11.11	03.17	247.61	3	49.06	33.02	08.49	09.43	221.71	4	21.505*** (0.001)
-Practicing livestock diversification	47.06	22.06	16.18	14.71	201.48	7	61.45	18.07	08.43	12.05	228.92	4	64.52	12.90	14.52	08.06	233.88	6	57.75	17.84	12.68	11.74	106.11	10	6.7930 (0.340)
-Increased use of irrigation	50.00	26.39	05.56	18.06	208.34	4	56.47	21.18	10.59	11.76	222.36	7	57.89	34.21	01.32	06.58	185.52	9	54.94	27.04	06.01	12.02	224.91	3	12.851** (0.045)
-Change of planting date	55.71	21.43	07.14	15.71	217.13	3	61.73	22.22	09.88	06.17	239.51	2	38.81	37.31	05.97	17.91	197.02	7	52.75	26.61	07.80	12.84	219.27	6	13.37** (0.038)
-Agroforestry practice	27.27	37.88	15.15	19.70	172.72	9	53.66	30.49	06.10	09.76	228.06	5	58.67	34.67	02.67	04.00	248.02	2	47.53	34.08	07.62	10.76	218.37	7	24.634*** (0.000)
-Income-generating activities	38.03	43.66	04.23	14.08	205.64	6	46.15	44.87	03.85	05.13	232.04	3	66.18	29.41	02.94	01.47	260.3	1	49.77	39.63	03.69	06.91	232.26	2	17.193*** (0.009)
-Agricultural diversification	53.52	30.99	09.86	05.63	232.4	1	60.49	28.40	04.94	06.17	243.21	1	60.29	29.41	05.88	04.41	245.57	4	58.18	29.55	06.82	05.45	240.46	1	2.165 (0.904)

Table 32: Efficiency of Adaptation Strategies Used Adaptation Strategies Index (ASI)

Source: Author computation with Data collected through survey during fieldwork in districts

From the table 32 above, the result revealed that though the effect of the threat is similar in the department of Koungh-Khi, the response to adapt differs from one district to another. The outcome from the table above shows that Bayangam and Demdeng are prioritising agriculture diversification as the foremost adaptation strategy. However, in the district of Poumougne, income-generating activities are prioritised as a preeminent adaptation strategy. As the second adaptation strategy in the district of Bayangam, smallholder farmers are practising crop rotation. However, changing the planting date is mentioned as the second adaptation approach in the district of Demdeng. In contrast, in the district of Poumougne, agroforestry practice is the second most adopted adaptation scheme.

There may be numerous reasons why adaptation strategies differ among farmers in a single locality. Regarding the participants of this study, 69.15 percent in Bayangam were male, and 74.39 percent in Poumougne were female. Based on this observation, we can assume that gender plays a substantial role in the choice of adaptation strategy. Also, academic qualification seems to play a meaningful role in the adaptation approach, as in the district of Bayangam, up to 81.14 percent have college qualifications, whereas only 48.64 and 45.68 percent have in Demdeng and Poumougne, respectively. Additionally, awareness and perception of climate change play a significant role in the adaptation strategy. Of the total participants, 98.77 percent in the district of Bayangam were aware, along with 91.95 percent and 76.83 percent in the districts of Demdeng and Poumougne, respectively. These observations line up with the finding of Marie *et al.* (2020) while investigating the factors of farmers' implementation of climate change adaptation plans in north-western Ethiopia, who found that age, gender, family size, and farm size meaningfully predisposed farmers' choice of acclimatisation approaches.

Moreover, while trying to know if weather change acclimatisation strategies improve farmers' food security in Tanzania, Gebre *et al.* (2023) mentioned that the supply of resources can vary from farm to farm, which could affect the form of adaptation strategy. Al-Addous *et al.* (2023) additionally declare that the supply of natural resources, which includes water and arable land, varies within a locality. Populations with enough sources might prioritise water conservation, while those going through scarcity might recognise drought-resistant crop types. Nevertheless, inside the district of Bayangam, extended use of irrigation became ranked as the fourth adaptation strategy, seventh for Demdeng, and ninth for Poumougne, indicating a lack of resources for smallholder farmers to manage water retention. Adaptation techniques are frequently driven by traditional know-how and cultural practices (Hagaria, 2022).

Communities could draw on indigenous wisdom to develop strategies deeply rooted in their history and environment (Turner, Cuerrier and Joseph, 2022; Singh, Tabe and Martin, 2022; Ciornei, 2023). In rural groups in Cameroon, indigenous understanding serves as a precious aid in growing techniques to cope with the demanding situations posed with the aid of climate change and food safety. One tangible instance of that is the conventional agroforestry practices within the rainforest regions of Cameroon. For generations, the Baka have thrived in concord with their forest environment, cultivating a deep information of the local ecology and its problematic dynamics. Drawing in this indigenous information, they have developed state-of-the-art agroforestry structures that combine diverse tree species with staple food crops which includes cassava, plantains, and yams. In those agroforestry structures, tall canopy bushes provide colouration and moisture regulation, developing microclimates conducive to crop boom, while nitrogen-fixing bushes enrich the soil and enhance fertility. Meanwhile, understory vegetation like cocoa, espresso, and medicinal plant life complements the staple food vegetation, diversifying earnings sources and ensuring resilience against environmental fluctuations. In the face of escalating weather-demanding situations, conventional practices offer treasured insights into sustainable agriculture and resilience-constructing techniques. By recognizing and respecting indigenous know-how structures, rural groups in Cameroon can harness the power of their cultural history to adapt and thrive in a hastily changing global. During the group discussion, farmers stated that some congenital practices to store tubercules like taro, yam, and potatoes are still effective. It allows them to store meals until the next agricultural season.

Furthermore, Tulbure *et al.* (2022) claim that weather trade impacts can occur in another way, even within a locality. For instance, Bedeke (2023) mentioned that growth temperatures can influence one part of the community more than any other. Changing precipitation styles might also impact exclusive styles of vegetation in varying ways. According to Feng *et al.* (2023), socioeconomic elements are essential in adaptation strategies. Low-income communities ought to lack the financial resources to implement certain adaptation measures, while more prosperous regions can spend money on technologies and infrastructure to mitigate weather risks (Glennerster and Jayachandran, 2023). The financial status of smallholder farmers in the study area was raised during the group discussion, and all farmers mentioned that their financial resources are highly related to farming as they sell only part of the harvest to cover their financial needs. Farmers added that they have a terrible financial situation because yield has reduced, and the harvest quality is unsuitable for the market.

The extent of know-how and consciousness of climate change and its effects can also differ amongst farmers, which may influence their ability to increase effective model strategies. (Ricart, Gandolfi and Castelletti, 2023). Other factors indicated by Khan *et al.* (2023), including the sort of vegetation grown, soil type, and weather styles, can also play a role in determining the most suitable adaptation techniques for character farmers. The diversity of the adaptation strategies in the study area is beneficial because it shows the different adaptation strategies of smallholder farmers from one locality to another in the same region. This information can be helpful for the state, researchers, policymakers, and governmental and non-governmental organisations.

6.5.2. Challenges of Adaptation Strategies

Table 32 below presents the computation and ranking of the Problem Confrontation Index (PCI). The researcher assessed the problems that constrain the application of the adaptation strategies through a ranking by using the problem confrontation index (PCI) (Ndamani and Watanabe, 2015). The researcher asked farmers to grade their perceptions of each challenge on a four-point Likert scale ranging from "no problem", "low", "moderate" and "high."

The researcher calculated the problem confrontation index (PCI) by using the following formula from (Ndamani and Watanabe, 2015):

$$PCI = P_n \times 0 + P_l \times 1 + P_m \times 2 + P_h \times 3$$

were,

PCI = Problem Confrontation Index.

P_n = number of smallholder farmers who graded the constraint as no problem.

P_l = number of smallholder farmers who graded the constraint as low.

P_m = number of smallholder farmers who graded the constraint as moderate.

P_h = number of smallholder farmers who graded the constraint as high.

Challenges	Bayangam N=82 (32.24)						Demdeng N=87 (34.8)						Poumougne N=83 (32.8)						Total sample N=252 (100)						Chi2 (p-value)
	High	Medium	Low	No	PCI	PCI Ranking	High	Medium	Low	No	PCI	PCI Ranking	High	Medium	Low	No	PCI	PCI Ranking	High	Medium	Low	No	PAI	PCI Ranking	
Lack of water availability	81.25	13.75	02.5	02.5	273.75	1	75.00	13.10	03.75	0833	254.95	4	85.53	06.58	05.26	02.63	275.01	1	80.42	11.25	03.75	04.58	267.51	1	07.504 (0.277)
High cost of farm inputs	49.32	31.51	17.81	01.37	228.79	6	67.90	17.28	04.94	09.88	243.2	5	57.14	32.47	03.90	06.49	240.22	4	58.44	26.84	08.66	06.06	237.66	5	21.55*** (0.001)
Unforeseen weather	58.44	23.38	15.59	02.60	237.67	5	45.78	37.35	06.02	10.84	218.06	6	63.01	31.51	01.37	04.11	127.4	8	55.36	30.90	07.73	06.01	235.61	6	20.258*** (0.002)
Lack of access to timely weather information	72.97	18.92	06.76	01.35	263.51	2	78.31	15.66	04.82	01.20	271.07	1	75.68	10.81	06.76	06.76	255.42	3	75.76	15.15	06.06	03.03	263.64	2	07.097 (0.312)
Lack of access to finance	68.92	20.27	08.11	02.70	255.41	3	73.17	14.63	08.54	03.66	257.31	2	79.41	08.82	04.41	07.35	101.46	9	73.66	14.73	07.14	04.46	257.58	4	6.621 (0.357)
Lack of access to agricultural subsidies	38.67	29.33	20.00	12.00	194.67	7	39.51	30.86	19.75	09.88	200	7	56.16	10.96	04.11	28.77	194.51	6	44.54	24.02	14.85	16.59	196.51	7	28.901*** (0.000)
Lack of market access	34.29	34.29	17.14	14.29	188.59	8	19.75	34.57	19.75	25.93	148.14	8	42.65	16.18	16.18	25.00	56.49	10	31.51	28.77	17.81	21.92	169.88	8	14.877** (0.021)
Limited access to an agricultural practice advisor	67.95	19.23	12.82	0.00	255.13	4	70.24	20.24	04.76	04.76	255.96	3	78.08	12.33	05.48	04.11	264.38	2	71.91	17.45	07.66	02.98	258.29	3	9.823 (0.132)
Low soil fertility	21.74	40.58	23.19	14.49	169.57	9	15.00	27.50	22.50	35.00	122.5	9	45.21	28.77	08.22	17.81	201.39	5	27.03	31.98	18.02	22.97	163.07	9	30.105*** (0.000)
Limited farm size	26.47	36.76	16.18	20.59	169.11	10	17.07	21.95	15.85	45.12	110.96	10	37.14	30.00	08.57	24.29	179.99	7	26.36	29.09	13.64	30.91	150.9	10	19.233*** (0.004)

Table 33:Challenges of Adaptation Strategies Used

Source: Author computation with Data collected through survey during fieldwork in districts

The table 33 above reveals that the challenges of adaptation strategies vary from one district to another. It shows that the districts of Bayangam and Poumougne lack water availability, which is the dominant challenge in adapting to the impact of climate change on food security. This difference could be explained by the geographic localization of the area. For example, this issue was raised during the group discussion, and farmers mentioned that those who have their farms on the upper land are threatened by drought, erosion, and low soil fertility. In contrast, excessive floods impact those on low land. Numerous authors made similar observations, for instance, Derbile, Bonye and Yiridomoh (2022) through mapping exposure evaluation of food crop farming and weather change acclimatisation in Ghana and Ruwanza, Thondhlana and Falayi (2022) while reviewing the progress and conceptual insights on drought impact and responses among smallholder farmers in South Africa, as well as Dadzie (2023) through investigation on maize farmers' adaptation to drought. Moreover, Marie *et al.* (2020) concluded that crop failure, soil erosion, and a shortage of water were the central climate-related adaptation problems among smallholder farmers in north-western Ethiopia.

Conversely, in the district of Demdeng, lack of access to timely weather information was the foremost challenge to adapting to the threat. However, this was the second in the district of Bayangam and the third in the district of Poumougne. Smallholder farmers in the group discussion also mentioned that they did not have any climate information, which endangered their efforts to adapt to threats. In the district of Demdeng, lack of access to finance was ranked as the second challenge, while this was the third in the district of Bayangam and ninth in the district of Poumougne. This observation gives rise to a significant difference in adaptation challenges among farmers in the same administrative locality.

6.6. Discussion

6.6.1. Changes in the Meteorological Conditions in the Study Area

Climate change is a global singularity causing significant effects on agriculture, particularly in rural areas (Raihan, 2023). Its influences are observable through the temperature rise, the alteration of precipitation patterns, and the emergence of extreme weather circumstances like droughts and floods (Wagner *et al.*, 2021; Afzal and Nishtar, 2023). These changes affect the output of crops and livestock and, hence, farmers' livelihoods. A trend line was used to analyse the evolution of precipitation over time in the study area. The finding shows a negative trend in the evolution of precipitation levels in the study area, as revealed by the trend line, which has a relatively negative slope. Climate change has significantly impacted the extent of the rainy period in the study area, either by increasing or decreasing the number of days of rain during a particular year. These changes could significantly impact human activities, such as agriculture, by altering the calendar for agricultural activities (Khan et al. (2023). The decrease in rainy days over the years shows that the area is becoming drier, which could have profound implications for agricultural production. This trend could lead to reduced crop yields due to water scarcity in the region.

These results generally agree with Ghanim *et al.* (2023) in assessing spatiotemporal trends of total and extreme precipitation in a subtropical highland region. Additional support for this explanation comes from Amosi and Anyah (2023).

The findings of the investigation from data collected at the MINADER suggest that there has been a gradual decline in the length of the rainy season between 2005 and 2022, with the lowest levels witnessed in 2017 and 2018 (92 days of rain in the year). The nature of the trend curve shows that the length of the rain has a negative slope, and therefore, farmers should expect shorter rainy seasons in the future. The outcome of the study by Animashaun *et al.* (2023) is close to this observation through an evaluation of weather change impacts on the hydrological retort of a watershed in the Savanna region of sub-Saharan Africa.

6.6.2. Changes in Meteorological Conditions and Production of Staple Foods

6.6.1.1. Effect of Meteorological Conditions on Beans Production

Overall, these statistics highlight the potential vulnerability and challenges agricultural systems face because of climate change impacts on meteorological conditions and subsequent staple food production levels and cultivated areas. The results show an inverse relationship between precipitation rate and bean production. This observation could be attributed to the adverse impact of excessive precipitation, which may lead to flooding and, subsequently, the drowning of bean plants. The negative correlation between the two variables underscores the importance of managing precipitation levels in bean production. Lugoi, Martinsen and Almås (2022) had the same results while evaluating the effect of climate change on different crop types in Uganda. In Bangladesh, Begum *et al.* (2023) obtained the same result while exploring bean cultivation's production risk and technical inefficiency. Lugoi, Martinsen and Almås (2022) suggest that optimising precipitation levels can minimise the risk of flooding and enhance bean production.

6.6.1.2. Effects of Meteorological Conditions and maize Production

The regression analysis shows that the maize production in the study area is not influenced by the precipitation rate or the duration of the rainy season. Therefore, changes in the length of the rainy season did not significantly affect maize production. Chekole and Ahmed (2023) reported similar findings while investigating future climate implications on maize productivity with adaptive options in Ethiopia. Chekole and Ahmed (2023) further argue that the absence of a significant impact of changes in the length of the rainy season on maize production can be attributed to the crop's high adaptability to varying environmental conditions. An alternative explanation from Kwawuvi *et al.* (2022) is that maize has been selectively bred over time to perform optimally across diverse climatic zones; hence, the perturbations in the length of rainy seasons do not have as pronounced an effect on maize production as anticipated. A more plausible explanation for this outcome would be that maize is a resilient crop that can tolerate fluctuations in precipitation levels, reducing susceptibility to the repercussions of changes in the length of rainy seasons (Niu *et al.*, 2020).

However, numerous authors have evidence that changes in the length of the rainy season significantly affect maize production (Adeagbo, Ojo and Adetoro, 2021; Li and Lei, 2022; Warsame *et al.*, 2023; Lacolla *et al.*, 2023).

On the other hand, surface cultivation shows a statistically significant positive relationship between surface cultivation and maize production. The results suggest that increasing the surface area cultivated can lead to higher maize production in the study area, which can help meet the increasing requirement for maize and sustain food security in rural settings. Erenstein *et al.* (2022) mentioned that it is essential to note that simply expanding the cultivated area is not enough to ensure higher maize production. In this regard, Nova (2023) additionally indicates that other factors, such as soil quality, access to water, and proper crop management practices, also play a serious role in defining crop yields. Therefore, it is fundamental to foster holistic agricultural policies that consider these factors and promote sustainable land-use practices.

6.6.1.3. Effects of Meteorological Conditions and Potatoes Production

The regression analysis shows that changes in meteorological conditions are negatively linked to potato production. The investigation reveals that the length of the rainy season and the amount of precipitation in the study area can significantly affect potato production. An alternative explanation from Wagg *et al.* (2021) is that excessive rainfall, especially during the planting or harvesting periods, can lead to waterlogging and the rotting of tubers, adversely impacting potato yields. It is well-established that an increase in the surface area cultivated positively affects agricultural production. Expanding the cultivated area leads to higher yields and increased production (Godfray *et al.*, 2010). This positive correlation is attributed to the potential for increased input, economies of scale, and a more significant labour force available for crop management and harvesting (Zhang *et al.*, 2022). The interaction between these climate factors and cultivated surface area is vital. A larger cultivated area can help mitigate the adverse effects of excessive rainfall by distributing the risks. For instance, if a region experiences a prolonged rainy season, having a larger surface area under cultivation allows farmers to shift their focus to less saturated areas. Crop diversification and staggered planting across a larger surface area can further reduce the vulnerability of potato crops to the negative impacts of excessive rainfall (Ngetich *et al.*, 2022). These strategies and well-planned drainage systems can help optimise potato production under variable climate conditions.

6.6.1.4. Impact of Climate Change on Food Availability among Smallholder Farmers

The logistic regression results present the influence of the severity of climate change on food availability in households. The significant positive effect of the number of climate change events witnessed suggests that individuals who have experienced more severe weather incidents are more likely to perceive climate change as a threat to food availability. This underlines the significance of addressing the influences of weather amendment on vulnerable populations, particularly in areas prone to extreme weather events.

Conversely, the substantial adverse impact of the number of climate change effects witnessed implies that those who have encountered more gradual shifts in their surroundings may show greater resilience or adaptability to the repercussions of weather alteration on food accessibility.

This highlights the need for interventions that support adaptation and mitigation approaches to address the impacts of weather variation on food security. The significant positive effect of the number of adaptation strategies on the severity of weather change on food availability suggests that individuals who have implemented more adaptation strategies may still experience negative impacts on food availability. This emphasises the need for a comprehensive approach to addressing the impacts of climate change on food security that includes adaptation and mitigation strategies. The weak impact of gender on the severity of weather change on food availability suggests that there may not be significant differences in how men and women perceive or respond to climate change concerning food availability. The significant positive effect of academic qualification on the harshness of climate change on food availability suggests that individuals with higher levels of education may perceive climate change as a more noteworthy threat to food security. This highlights the importance of education and awareness-raising campaigns to increase understanding of the impacts of climate change on food security.

6.6.1.5. Impact of Climate Change on Food Accessibility for Smallholder Households

The logistic regression results show that some explanatory variables have a moderate impact on the harshness of climate change on food accessibility, while others have a weak impact. This suggests that individuals who have experienced more climate change events are more likely to perceive climate change as a risk to food access. In contrast, those who have experienced more climate change effects may be more resilient or adaptive. The number of adaptation strategies used significantly affects the severity of climate change on food access, showing that individuals who have implemented more adaptation strategies may still experience positive impacts on food access. This highlights the importance of adapting to climate change and mitigating its effects. The weight of gender on the impact of climate change on food accessibility implies that there might not be substantial variations in the perception or response of men and women towards climate change and its effects on food access. Academic qualifications have a significant constructive effect on the severity of climate change on food accessibility for smallholder farmers, showing that individuals with higher levels of education may recognise weather change as a more significant threat to food access. This could be because they have more knowledge or awareness of the potential impacts of climate change.

6.6.1.6. Impact of climate change on food utilisation by smallholder households

The results show the impact of various explanatory variables on the severity of climate change on the utilisation of food by farmers. The number of climate change events witnessed, and the number of climate change effects witnessed both positively and significantly impact the severity of climate change on food utilisation.

This suggests that farmers who felt more weather change events and effects are more prone to report severe impacts on food utilisation. The number of adaptation strategies used also has a positive and significant impact on the harshness of climate change on food utilisation.

This shows that farmers who have implemented more adaptation strategies are better able to cope with the impacts of weather differences on their food production. Gender has a significant impact, with female farmers more likely to report moderate impacts on food utilisation than male farmers. This suggests that gender may play a role in how farmers recognise and respond to the impacts of weather change on their livelihoods. Gender norms and roles may influence the crops grown, the level of access to possessions and information, and the decision-making power within households, all of which can affect how farmers adapt to weather variation. Academic qualification does not significantly impact the strictness of weather change on food utilisation, while farm size has a negative but non-significant impact. The number of varieties cultivated has a significant impact, with farmers who produce more varieties being more likely to report severe impacts on food utilisation. This could be because crops' increased complexity and diversity make adapting to changing environmental conditions harder. Overall, these results suggest that experiencing more climate change events and effects, implementing more adaptation strategies, and cultivating fewer crop varieties could help farmers mitigate the impacts of climate change on their food production. Gender also appears essential in developing interventions and strategies to help farmers adapt to climate change.

7 Chapter Seven: Summary of Key Findings

7.1 Overview of the Research Objective

The motivation behind this study is agriculture's significant role in Cameroon's food security, especially in the Western region. Agriculture in the western region of Cameroon is heavily dependent on smallholder farming. Their efforts contribute to food security, economic growth, and employment. Due to the high dependency on rainfall, climate change adversely impacts farming activities. One of the critical challenges is the slow development of irrigation potential and restricted access to improved agricultural technologies, inputs, and finance. The researcher developed an investigation to address smallholder farmers' challenges in rural areas due to weather irregularity and alteration. The present study aims to comprehensively investigate the multifaceted impact of climate change on the food security of smallholder farmers in the Kong-Khi department. The purpose of this chapter is to utilise the outcomes from both the numerical and qualitative elements to address the study objectives.

7.2. How are the Changes in Weather Patterns occurring in the Study Area and their Influence on the Production of Staple Foods?

As in several countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, in Cameroon, smallholder farmers are heavily dependent on agriculture, particularly in rural settings where agriculture employs more than 80% of the rural population. Agriculture products usually serve many purposes; for instance, financial and food needs are covered by selling part of the product harvested. The quantity and quality of the products harvested by smallholder farmers play a significant role in their nutritional needs. For that purpose, this study aimed to establish if weather change has an adverse effect on smallholder farmers' food security in the rural settings of the Koung-Khi department.

Results from early investigations have shown that fluctuating weather configurations, comprising increased temperatures, unpredictable rainfall, and prolonged drought, have adversely affected agricultural production, resulting in reduced crop yields and diminished livestock productivity (Baumgard *et al.*, 2012; Bekele, 2017; Masinde, Mamboleo and Nyantika, 2023). This phenomenon has reduced food availability, accessibility, and utilisation, leading to an increase in the risk of hunger and malnutrition worldwide, specifically in rural areas in Africa (Domguia *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, many investigators assumed that climate change has exacerbated the spread of pests and diseases, further affecting agricultural production (Abbass *et al.*, 2022; Cao, Lee, and Lee, 2023; Kaur *et al.*, 2023).

Interestingly, many scholars adhere to the view that both direct and indirect climate change impacts have perpetuated poverty and limited resources for rural communities, thereby hindering their ability to generate sustainable livelihoods (Moyo, 2023; Duong and Flaherty, 2023; Fanzo and Miachon, 2023). Affoh *et al.*'s (2022) investigation of weather irregularity and food security in sub-Saharan Africa reveals that rising temperatures and altered precipitation patterns negatively affect crop yields. Similar results have been found by Asfew *et al.* (2023), supporting the idea that prolonged droughts, extreme heat, and irregular rainfall in sub-Saharan African countries have reduced harvests, affecting the availability of staple foods.

The outcomes of this study indicate that the average seasonal temperature in the study area is increasing (see results in Chapter 5 on FGD), while annual rainfall shows a decreasing trend for 17 years. The climate in Koung-Khi is changing, which is supported by four sources of data: questionnaires, focus group discussions, key informant interviews, and meteorological data. This change aligns with global climate change (IPCC, 2022). The investigation's result shows that the weather has been changing based on the comparison of rainfall data from the statistical department of the regional delegation of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. Rainfall showed a negative trend over an episodic yearly decrease and an increase in the quantity of rain throughout the period. This raises the issue of water availability for agriculture and livestock areas, as farming is heavily rainfed. A point addressed on this matter by Safari, Sebaziga and Siebert (2022) stated that a decrease in precipitation induces a decrease in agricultural output and reduces food availability. The outcomes from the focus group discussion and key informant interview line up with this statement in that all farmers agreed during the session that in their area, food availability had been seriously impacted by climate variability, leading to food shortage. Support for this interpretation comes from Amuji (2023) while looking at the future of rain-fed crop production in the West African climate. A drastic decrease of rain fall follows the decreasing precipitation trend in the study area in the average number of rain days throughout the study. This outcome aligns with the results of Mainuddin *et al.* (2022) in Bangladesh under investigation of rainfall and temperature extremes over the long term and their potential risk to rice planting.

Stakeholders' pictures of weather change in the study area are confirmed through surveys, focus group discussions, and key informant interviews with agricultural experts in the western region. For instance, the smallholder farmers' survey revealed that 89% of respondents are aware of climate change, while 10% are not. From this observation, at the district level, 98.77 percent are aware of climate change in Bayangam and 91 percent in Demdeng, followed by 76.83 percent in Poumougne. The district of Bayangam had the highest respondent rate, 81.01 percent, with college qualifications, while the total number of respondents was 57.89 percent. This observation shows that academic qualification plays a significant role in the study area's awareness and perception of climate change. Similar findings were reported by (Kousar *et al.*, 2022; Eilam, 2022; Leiva-Brondo *et al.*, 2022; Adusu *et al.*, 2022; Kumar *et al.*, 2023).

During the focus group discussion with lead farmers and community leaders, they all mentioned that they are facing a severe change in climate resulting in low rainfall, later onset and early stop of rainfall, and prolonged temperature. In eastern Ethiopia, Usmail, Maja and Lakew (2023) also reached the same outcome by investigating farmers' perceptions of weather variability and adaptation approaches in rural areas. Additional support for this outcome comes from the investigations of Obwocha *et al.* (2022), Awolala *et al.* (2022), and Akanwa *et al.* (2023) in Nigeria.

Picture 12: Focus group discussion 02 with Lead Farmers
Source: Fieldwork (Picture taken with participant consent during group discussion)

Additionally, it was found in the focus group discussions that the impact of the change in local climate is meaningfully felt in the valley zones related to the uplands because of reduced admittance to water for irrigation. This observation is generally in line with those obtained in Abazinab, Duguma and Muleta (2022), where further argument highlighted similar comments with lead farmers and community leaders in the way that highlands in the study are much more impacted by drought, soil erosion, poor fertility of the soil, and severe winds during heavy rain. Furthermore, certain lowland areas close to river streams have high humidity levels, which can promote the growing of crops such as tomatoes and maize even in the dry season. A key informant interview with an expert also identifies the same observation as a focus group discussion.

The statistical analysis results of climate change's impact on staple food production in the study area indicate significant findings. According to the findings, the production of beans in the study area was positively influenced by the length of the rainy season and the length of the cultivated surface. Conversely, the study reveals that precipitation negatively impacts the production of beans.

This may be discussed in terms of Losa *et al.* (2021), who claim that prolonged periods of rain can increase the risk of fungal infections, further impairing bean yields. Additionally, Odunga (2022) argues that the obvious consequences of excessive precipitation can harm bean production by inducing root rot and reducing nutrient uptake. As beans are among the most used staple crops for nutritional needs in the department of Koung-Khi, a point that can be made is that the smallholder farmers in the rural settings of the department of Koung-Khi are susceptible to eating beans with poor nutrients. Some confirmations were obtained during the focus group discussion with lead farmers and community leaders, and all the participants were interviewed during the key informant interview. Pregnant women and new-born babies were the most affected, though they received little assistance from other community members or the church leader in the area. This observation can guide the state and national government and international organisations in prioritising awareness or adaptation initiatives in the study area or the western region of Cameroon. Also, farmers and farming experts should consider the length of the rainy season and the cultivation practices while planning bean production.

Concerning maize production, the present study concludes that changes in precipitation and the length of the rainy season did not significantly impact maize production. In contrast, information from focus group discussions and interviews indicates that maize production has decreased in quantity and worsened the quality of the grain harvested. During the discussion, participants mentioned that maize is among the most cultivated in their area because it serves many purposes. For instance, to feed the family, the harvested crops are sold in the market to cover livelihood needs. The conclusion can be substantiated by the analysis of rainfall data, which indicates yearly episodic decreases in the quantity of rain. These variations in yearly rainfall compromise the growth and production of maize, a rainfed staple crop with a short growth period. As such, the fluctuations in rainfall pose a significant challenge to the cultivation of maize, and strategies should be developed to alleviate these impacts. However, it has been found that an increase in the cultivated surface positively influences maize production. These findings can be of great importance for policymakers and stakeholders in the agricultural sector. Policymakers on agricultural management consulted during this investigation encompass a diverse array of actors spanning governmental bodies and non-governmental organisations (NGOs). At the national level, government ministries and departments responsible for agriculture, rural development, and environmental affairs play a central role in formulating and instigating policies related to agricultural management. It is imperative to consider the length of the surface to be cultivated while formulating any policy related to maize production.

Regarding potato production, the present study provides evidence of the adversative impact of weather change on potato production in the Koung-khi department. Findings from the focus group discussion, coupled with the results from regression analysis, have exposed the highly negative impact of climate events on potato output in the area.

Potatoes are among the area's most used staple crops for nutritional needs. During the focus group discussion, small farmers reported that potatoes are cultivated more in the lowlands because they need more water to grow properly. Adversely, the bean does need water at the growing and maturing stage and sun rays at the end stage to dry up and get ready to be harvested. Sometimes, farmers in the highlands may make trucks with those in the lowlands to compensate for the crop needs of the community. The results suggest that farmers in this region may need to adapt their agricultural performance to account for the shifting weather patterns. As such, it is imperative to foster and implement approaches for climate-smart agriculture that can enhance the resilience of smallholder farmers in the face of changing climatic conditions.

The implications of climate change in rural areas are significant, and it is imperative to implement technical and policy measures to mitigate its impact on the food systems of smallholder farmers. Working on policy with smallholder farmers is beneficial because it ensures that agricultural policies address this vulnerable group's specific needs and challenges, contributing to more inclusive and equitable development outcomes. Moreover, involving smallholder farmers in policymaking fosters ownership, empowerment, and grassroots innovation, ultimately leading to more effective and sustainable agricultural policies. Given the significance of agriculture in the economic development of rural zones, it is crucial to address this issue and ensure sustainable food production. As such, it is fundamental to identify approaches that can heighten the resilience of smallholder farmers to the effects of climate change. Therefore, a comprehensive approach that includes both technical and policy interventions is essential to minimise the magnitudes of weather variation on the food systems of smallholder farmers, promote sustainable agriculture, and ensure food security in rural areas. The livelihoods of smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-khi are under dire threat due to shifting local climate patterns.

This ongoing transformation is expected to continue, exacerbating the situation. Urgent intervention is needed to mitigate the effects of these changes and support those most impacted. The implications of these climatic alterations are complex and multifaceted and require careful consideration by stakeholders across various sectors. The focus group discussion, key informant interview results, and survey findings support this observation.

7.3 What is the Impact of Climate Change on Food Availability, Accessibility, and Utilisation among Smallholder Farmers?

Changes in weather patterns seriously threaten food security, specifically in developing countries where agriculture is the social and economic backbone. Empirical studies have shown that extreme weather events such as droughts, floods and heat waves significantly hamper agricultural production.

For example, Fudjumdjum's (2019) research in Bafoussam, Cameroon, shows that climate change is directly linked to reduced productivity and increased insect diseases. These adverse conditions reduce food production and increase food instability, leading to periodic food shortages and food price increases that strain the wealth of vulnerable households. Further experimental research highlights the ongoing impact of climate-induced agricultural disturbances on food security. When agricultural production declines, smallholder farmers who rely heavily on subsistence agriculture face immediate threats to food security. This is due to loss of income from crop sales, which limits their ability to purchase food supplements or invest in quality. Studies across sub-Saharan Africa, including Ghana and Nigeria, support these conclusions, showing that reductions in agricultural productivity due to climate change generally reduce household food supplies, another lifestyle forces them to resort to coping strategies such as giving up food or moving to cities in search of it. Although necessary for immediate survival, these adaptive strategies can negatively affect nutritional status and overall well-being.

Furthermore, the case studies highlight the significance of integrating local knowledge and exchange practices into wider programs to enhance food security. For example, in rural Cameroon, traditional agricultural practices of crop diversification, soil conservation, and water use have been shown to promote resilience to climate shocks but require these indigenous approaches support through participatory programs that provide resources, education, and financial services. By bridging the gap between empirical evidence and policy action, stakeholders can create robust and sustainable food systems that are better equipped to withstand the impacts of climate change. This investigation found that food availability in a farm household is significantly influenced by the extent of climate change effects experienced and the number of climate change adaptation approaches implemented. Notably, the impact of weather change is more severe in female-headed households than in male-headed ones. Smallholder farmers also mentioned that food shortages highly threatened families headed by women. This observation was also made by Aiswarya et al. 2023 while investigating gender vulnerabilities in small-scale agricultural households in India.

The most common reason was that the husband had passed away, and the rest were due to an inability to take on familial responsibility. Moreover, individuals with higher academic qualifications tend to witness a weaker impact than a severe one. The results highlight the significance of climate change adaptation strategies in addressing food security challenges in agricultural households, particularly focusing on support and education for those with lower educational levels.

An investigation of the outcomes of weather change on food accessibility revealed that the frequency and intensity of climate change occurrences and the use of adaptation strategies are all substantial factors. As the number of climate change events and adaptation approaches employed increases, the likelihood of a moderate impact on food accessibility also increases.

Furthermore, like the findings of Bernzen et al. (2023), this investigation revealed that other factors affecting food accessibility include academic qualifications and the diversity of crop varieties cultivated. It is obvious that weather alteration substantially impacts global food security, so understanding the factors that contribute to this impact is critical. While the frequency of climate change events and the number of adaptation approaches used may mitigate weather change's impact on food accessibility, the cultivation of diverse crop varieties and academic qualifications also play significant roles. Thus, it is crucial to promote education and awareness of the impact of climate change on food accessibility and to develop strategies that address the multifaceted confronts postured by this issue.

According to the outcome of this research, the accessibility of food is affected by a range of causes, including the frequency and efficiency of adaptation strategies to climate change, as well as the step to which weather change impacts are experienced, which line with the results of Gebre et al., (2023). These factors can have a moderate impact on food availability. Additionally, in concordance with the findings of Amao et al. (2023) on factors affecting food security among households in Nigeria, the results of this research indicate that food accessibility can be influenced by variables such as the gender of the household head, educational attainment, and the diversity of crops grown. It is imperative to consider all these factors when addressing the critical issue of food security in the framework of weather alteration.

Insights obtained from focus group discussions and interviews with agricultural experts have highlighted the detrimental impact of climate change on food supply, accessibility, and consumption. Farmers have repeatedly expressed concern over the decline in meal frequency and the inferior quality of grains that result in less flavourful food. This was attributed to the stunted growth of certain crops due to insufficient rainfall. Climate change exerts multifaceted health and broader impacts on smallholder farmers, compelling them to confront many challenges, such as amplified incidence and harshness of intense weather occurrences, rising temperatures, and changing precipitation patterns. These environmental stresses jeopardise crop yields and agricultural productivity and exacerbate food insecurity, malnutrition, and waterborne diseases, placing additional strains on farmers' physical and mental well-being. In response to these escalating threats, many smallholder farmers are reluctantly considering abandoning farming altogether as the viability of traditional agricultural practices becomes increasingly uncertain in the face of climate-related disruptions. In addition, obtaining supplementary food items on the market has become a significant challenge due to their high cost and the need for additional financial resources. Due to the use of funds generated from the sale of a portion of their harvested products, the family's financial security has been compromised.

As a result, the family's overall financial resources have been significantly constrained, thereby impeding its ability to undertake critical business operations. Considering this, alternate sources of funding must be explored to mitigate the family's current financial risks.

7.4. How are Smallholder Farmers Responding to Changes in Climate Conditions, and which Challenges do they Currently Face in their Efforts to Adapt?

In this regard, participants asserted during the focus group discussion that there are ancestral practices that can stop or call the rain. Those practices are applied when significant events are occurring in the chiefdom. The present study has revealed that smallholder farmers have already implemented certain essential practices to adapt to and cope with changes in climate conditions. These practices include growing short-lived crops, intercropping, increasing irrigation, changing planting dates, and engaging in additional income-generating activities. During focus group discussions, the farmers reported learning how to create organic compost by combining kitchen waste with tree leaves. In addition, the implementation of supplementary activities that generate revenue was carried out with proficiency. Experts interviewed for this study recommended that smallholder farmers alter their planting schedules and diversify their income streams. However, variations were observed in the practices followed by farmers in different communes, which were attributable to various factors, such as water access for irrigation and geographical location within the valley or highlands.

7.5. Ranking of Efficiency of Adaptation Strategies Used

Adaptation Strategies	Total sample N=252 (100)					
	High	Medium	Low	No	ASI	ASI Ranking
-Agricultural diversification	58.18	29.55	06.82	05.45	240.46	1
-Income-generating activities	49.77	39.63	03.69	06.91	232.26	2
-Increased use of irrigation	54.94	27.04	06.01	12.02	224.91	3
-Practice intercropping	49.06	33.02	08.49	09.43	221.71	4
-Practice crop rotation	53.77	22.17	15.09	08.96	220.53	5
-Change of planting date	52.75	26.61	07.80	12.84	219.27	6
-Growing short-lived crops	38.53	39.39	07.79	14.29	202.16	7
-Agroforestry practice	47.53	34.08	07.62	10.76	218.37	8
-Soil conservation techniques	32.31	32.37	14.49	20.77	176.16	9
-Practicing livestock diversification	57.75	17.84	12.68	11.74	106.11	10

Table 34: Ranking of efficiency of adaptation strategies used
Source: Author computation

The adaptation strategy index is frequently used in research because it gives accurate outcomes that can be ranked to prioritise any adaptation action. Table 3 above shows the ranking of the efficiency of adaptation strategies used by smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-khi. From the table above, the adaptation strategies are ranked from the highest to the lowest number of ASI. The higher the index of adaptation strategies, the more strategies are applied among the smallholder farmer community. The ranking in the table of efficiency of adaptation strategies reflects a nuanced understanding of each strategy's effectiveness in mitigating the impacts of climate change on smallholder farmers.

Qualitative details accompanying the rankings provide insights into the contextual factors influencing the practicability and applicability of each strategy, considering variables such as local agroecological conditions, socio-economic constraints, and community resilience. Through in-depth interviews and participatory assessments, stakeholders contribute valuable perspectives on the strengths, limitations, and potential trade-offs associated with different adaptation approaches, enriching the interpretation of the rankings, and informing strategic decision-making for sustainable agricultural development.

7. 5.1. Agricultural Diversification

Table 33 above reveals that agricultural diversification is ranked as the first adaptation strategy that smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-Khi are applying. During the focus group discussion, the lead farmers and community leaders also referred to the diversification of cultivated crops to adapt to the impact of climate change on their local food crops. However, farmers were not asked to rank the adaptation strategy during the focus group discussion. Adopting agricultural diversification as a priority strategy to adapt to the threat of climate change on food security is reasonable since it is convenient with few resources or skills.

Numerous authors also found agricultural diversification a top-priority adaptation strategy for smallholder farmers. For instance, Nyahunda and Tirivangasi (2022) examined how rural women adapt to the impact of climate change in South Africa. They found that household-based adaptation strategies include the diversification of livelihoods and crops, the use of indigenous knowledge systems, and the harnessing of social capital.

Nevertheless, Zhang *et al.* (2022) claim that crop subsidies, agricultural equipment, and household size are key breakthrough points to improve crop diversification.

This assertion appears partially unattainable for smallholder farmers in Koung-Khi, as they mentioned during the group discussion that they need more financial resources to purchase processed seed and more human resources to cultivate as they are using only their hands to work on the farm.

However, Bulte *et al.* (2023) claim that the quality of the seeds should be appropriate to the soil to expect a good harvest. This may require assistance from an agronomist or expert in the agricultural field.

Similarly, Di Bene *et al.* (2022) examine the barriers to sustainable agriculture practices and the opportunities for diversifying crops. The results revealed that the strength was that the selected crop for diversification should acclimate to the local climate conditions. The major weakness was that few farmers were experts in crop diversification. This outcome can offer valuable insights to aid in developing agricultural diversification across various affected rural settings.

7.5.2. Income-Generating Activities

The second most essential adaptation strategy was income-generating activities. This was also mentioned during the group discussion, as farmers claimed they were being trained by the church and government representatives to raise chickens and goats. This initiative is in line with government policy to foster extra activities at the local level to help farmers multiply their sources of income. Following the same view, Chen, and Liu (2023) asserted that by adapting alternative income-generating activities, farmers could compensate for potential agricultural losses by earning alternative revenues. The crop diversification strategy provides a safety net, reducing the economic impact of unfavourable farming seasons (Bernzen *et al.*, 2023). Prince *et al.* (2023) claimed that income generated from supplement activities could be directed towards climate-resilient farming practices, such as cultivating drought-resistant crop varieties or implementing improved water management systems. This observation can benefit smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-Khi, as they mention a need for more financial resources to procure processed seed. Considering climate change, farmers are examining income-generating activities that exploit emerging markets and opportunities (Tualle *et al.*, 2023). In the same opinion, Melville, Kuznesof and Franks (2023) asserted that farmers may cultivate specialised crops or value-added products, recognising the increasing demand for locally sourced, sustainable, and climate-resilient goods.

7.5.3. Increased Use of Irrigation

The third most essential adaptation strategy was the increased use of irrigation. This adaptation practice is among the benefits. Nevertheless, it can only be applied to farms on low land. The geographic situation of the Koung-Khi department is represented by upper and low land. This representation threatens farmers located in the upper land to apply irrigation. Farmers increasingly recognise that increased irrigation provides greater control over crop production and harvest timing. On that matter, in Kenya, Kwambai *et al.* (2022) looked at the essential means to improve potato production and realised that irrigation was among the best practices to enhance production. Farmers raised this practice during the discussion, but complaints were about the material used to irrigate the farm. The same farmers mentioned renting the material from the urban area, but transportation to the farm was challenging. The integration of efficient irrigation technologies in rural settings is in line with the broader sustainability goals (Bibri *et al.*, 2023).

Reliable water access for agriculture empowers communities to maintain a consistent food supply, lessening families' vulnerability to food shortages that arise from climate-induced conditions. The surplus produce generated through irrigation can be sold to boost the household's income.

7.5.4. Practice Intercropping

The fourth most essential adaptation strategy was practice intercropping. Scholarly investigations have proven that numerous smallholder farmers practice intercropping to adapt to the threat caused by climate change to crop production (Rafflegeau *et al.*, 2023). Smallholder farmers in the Koung-Khi department have witnessed that intercropping is broadly used as an adaptation strategy in this locality and the region. During the key information with the government representative, it was mentioned that some state initiatives empower farmers to practice intercropping by helping them identify different crops that can be cultivated together to prevent one crop from inhibiting the growth of the other. On that matter, Kramer, and Hackman (2023) claim that the diverse nature of crops results in different responses to weather variations, thus minimising the chances of total crop failure in extreme conditions. The use of different crop combinations has the effect of disrupting the life cycles of specific pests and diseases, thus increasing the difficulty for them to establish, and spread (Daughtrey and Buitenhuis, 2020; Skendžić *et al.*, 2021; O'Callaghan, Ballard, and Wright, 2022; Costa *et al.*, 2023; Zhang, Zhang, and Xu, 2023). Moreover, Hartmann and Six (2023) added that incorporating crops with diverse root structures into the agricultural system can improve soil structure, prevent erosion, and stimulate beneficial microbial activity. Another essential aspect of intercropping is its contribution to sustainable agriculture, which includes reducing the need for chemical inputs and enhancing soil health (Fagodiya, Verma and Verma, 2023).

7.5.5. Practice Crop Rotation

The fifth most essential adaptation strategy was practising crop rotation. Smallholder farmers stated during the group discussion that this practice is applied by farmers in their locality. The practice of crop rotation empowers farmers to vary their crop selection, consequently reducing the potential hazards linked to fluctuating weather patterns (Terefe, 2023). Several scholarly investigations asserted that the integration of drought-resistant crops into the rotation could result in decreased irrigation requirements, especially in times of drought (Wang *et al.*, 2022; Mohammed *et al.*, 2022; Alkhalidi *et al.*, 2023). Considering the changing climate, it is crucial to recognise the importance of conserving water resources, which is an effective method for mitigating greenhouse gas emissions through the rotation of leguminous crops as they could capture and store atmospheric carbon in the soil (Holka, Kowalska and Jakubowska, 2022; Chataut *et al.*, 2023). Incorporating this practice into agricultural activities could reduce the environmental footprint associated with farming and contribute towards the larger goal of climate change mitigation (Chataut *et al.*, 2023).

7. 5.6. Change of Planting Date

The dependency on rain-fed agriculture by smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-Khi makes them need help choosing an appropriate date to sow their seeds. A new plant needs sufficient water to germinate, and at the growing stage, a threat to the wither pattern can easily jeopardise the flowering stage and the development of its harvests. All smallholder farmers and government representatives witnessed that changing planting dates are widely applied to adapt to the changing climate. Farmers added that a lack of climate information often endangers their decision on planting dates. By analysing smallholder farmers' adjustment approaches to diminish the influence of drought on maize production in South Africa, Muroyiwa, Masinda and Mushunje (2022) utilised adaptation strategy indexes to determine the link between adaptation strategies and maize production. Based on smallholder farmer's evaluations, the adaptation strategies were rated according to their usefulness in coping with and alleviating declines in maize production. According to the results, smallholder farmers identified various adaptation strategies as most beneficial. These strategies include shifting planting dates, reducing maize cultivation areas, utilising drought-resistant varieties, diversifying crops, and practising intercropping. Following the same line, Nciizah *et al.* (2022) also investigated the smallholder farmers' adaptation strategies for food security in Zimbabwe. They found that shifting the planting date is considered one of the prominent practices in adaptation strategy. By implementing practices that are in line with fluctuating weather patterns, farmers can decrease risk and increase crop yield.

7. 5.7. Growing Short-Lived Crops

Given the fast adjustments in climate, farmers are actively adopting progressive techniques to evolve and ensure the sustainability of their agricultural practices (Mensah *et al.*, 2023). The cultivation of quick-lived plants is an approach that is increasingly being adopted.

Growing short-lived crops was also an adaptation strategy applied by smallholder farmers in the Koung-khi department. Government representatives also assert that the state used to train farmers on the benefits of growing short-lived crops, but the challenge resumed with procuring the crop from farmers. According to Zigene (2023), crops with quick lifespans usually reach maturity rapidly, so allowing farmers to promote their produce earlier than in unfavourable climate situations can greatly influence crop yield. Simultaneously, Sims (2023) stated that rapid maturation of short-lived plants allows early harvest to avoid climate-associated yield loss. Frequent crop rotation allows farmers to conform to consumer options and doubtlessly earn better charges in dynamic markets (Ayamga *et al.*, 2023). Crops with quick lifespans provide numerous benefits, which include reduced threats, accelerated flexibility, efficient use of resources, and advanced food protection.

7.5.8. Affective Adaptation

On the historical concept of affective adaptation, elderly smallholder farmers mentioned during the group discussion that, at a young age, their parents used to say that humans and nature are similar.

Additionally, they stated that their grandparents and parents used to say that every tree represented human life. In the past, their father used to plant a tree in the village when a child was born, symbolising the connection between the new-born and the universe. When the child reaches the age of understanding the phenomenon, the father then shows the tree and advises him to take care of it. Due to this connection with nature, rural populations may express their emotional belonging to the environment more easily. The emotional connection that human beings have with the environment is a treasured component that should be recognised and taken into consideration while promoting sustainable development and conservation of the environment. This deep emotional connection surpasses physical desires and encompasses spiritual, cultural, and emotional well-being. It is evident in how human beings interact with the environment via cultural practices, traditional know-how systems, and natural aid management. Through acknowledging and valuing emotional belonging, it can work toward constructing positive and collaborative relationships among humans, community groups, and the environment. It will then instigate the development of sustainable policies and initiatives that benefit the environment and assist the general well-being of the humans that rely on it.

7. 6. Ranking of Challenges to Adaptation Strategies

Challenges	Total sample N=252 (100)					PCI	Ranking
	High	Medium	Low	No			
Lack of water availability	80.42	11.25	03.75	04.58	267.51	1	
Lack of access to timely weather information	75.76	15.15	06.06	03.03	263.64	2	
Limited access to an agricultural practice advisor	71.91	17.45	07.66	02.98	258.29	3	
Lack of access to finance	73.66	14.73	07.14	04.46	257.58	4	
High cost of farm inputs	58.44	26.84	08.66	06.06	237.66	5	
Unforeseen weather	55.36	30.90	07.73	06.01	235.61	6	
Lack of access to agricultural subsidies	44.54	24.02	14.85	16.59	196.51	7	
Lack of market access	31.51	28.77	17.81	21.92	169.88	8	
Low soil fertility	27.03	31.98	18.02	22.97	163.07	9	
Limited farm size	26.36	29.09	13.64	30.91	150.9	10	

Table 35: Ranking of challenges to adaptation strategies used
Source: Author computation

Despite farmers' diligent efforts to acclimatise to the threats posed by weather change, they face significant challenges. Table 34 above shows the ranking of adaptation challenges used by smallholder farmers in the Koung-Khi department. Table 34 above ranks the problem confrontation index from the highest to the lowest. The higher the number of problem confrontation indexes, the more the challenge or problem is expressed among the smallholder farmer community. The table above reveals that lack of water availability is ranked as the first challenge farmers face in applying adaptation strategies. The second most critical challenge is the need for more access to timely weather information, limited access to an agricultural practice advisor, and a lack of access to finance. Findings from a focus group discussion with farmers revealed that inadequate financial means hinder their ability to adapt effectively to climate change. Some factors preventing adaptation are a lack of awareness about the situation, a lack of access to information, and a lack of knowledge about coping. Furthermore, the state must provide more support, particularly subsidies, for certain agricultural products, such as fertilisers and drought-resistant seeds.

Experts acknowledge that the state's support for farmers in rural settings to adapt better to climate change needs to be improved. Addressing these issues promptly ensures that the agricultural sector can thrive despite the changing climate. Scholars have highlighted the poverty of small-scale farmers in rural sub-Saharan Africa, making them predisposed to the impacts of climate change (Donkor and Mearns, 2022; Wudil *et al.*, 2022; Critchley *et al.*, 2023; Omotoso *et al.*, 2023). Adaptation resources can alleviate or reduce climate change impacts (Farooq *et al.*, 2022). Nevertheless, Nor Diana *et al.* (2022) point out that with the updated adaptation material, farmers must also acquire the necessary skills to use them. Ahmad and Sharma (2023) support this by saying that technical skills are essential for manipulating or reading resources such as irrigation facilities and weather forecast technologies. Smallholder farmers or communities are burdened with these challenges, affecting their purchasing, or renting power. The state and community leaders are hampered by the responsibility of the growing population (Abenir, Manzanero and Bollettino, 2022). Governments with limited resources often prioritise social action. Focusing on disease reduction may be more important than climate change adaptation. In South Africa, Sibiya *et al.* (2023) point out that ineffective administration, inadequate accountability, and corruption hinder the government's efforts to support climate change adaptation. Effiong, Ngang and Ekott (2023) in Nigeria, Ibrahim, Bartsch and Sharifi (2023) in Ghana, Shrestha *et al.* (2023) in Nepal, and Ahmad, Ngang and Ekott (2023) in Pakistan also supported this argument. During the group discussion, it was raised that smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-Khi joined forces to minimise expenses, but mistrust and a lack of interaction among members failed. Lecoutere and Van Campenhout (2023) found this approach beneficial for farmers in Uganda and Tanzania while investigating the impact of intrahousehold cooperation on welfare in East African agricultural households.

Tchawa (2023) also observed positive feedback on farmers joining together to apply for financial support. Therefore, there is a need for extension workers in the study area to support the development of cooperatives. Additional challenges identified in the study area were the insecurity in the northwest and southwest, neighbouring the western region. The arrival of the internally displaced people caused an increase in food scarcity in the area. Furthermore, group discussion revealed that elderly farmers lack the energy to cultivate land. Also, the farmers' productivity is affected by illnesses and diseases, causing some to be too weak from hunger to work more than a few hours daily. Most farmers in the discussion mentioned that the youth's migration to urban areas for better opportunities has resulted in labour difficulties. Labour constraints among older farmers have limited some soil and water conservation practices.

7.7. Summary

Agricultural practice in rural areas of sub-Saharan Africa is mainly rain-fed. It generates staple food essential to maintaining the nutritional status of smallholder farmers in the region and countrywide. Livelihood maintenance and enhancement affected by poverty in rural settings are dependent on food crop production. The study observed that female participants were more represented in the sample than males. The age range was 17–80, with more than half having a college qualification. The average size of the household was more than five people. An explanation for the increase in household size was the insecurity in the neighbouring region, which favoured internal displacement of the population. The average farm size in the sample regions was between 15 and 0.02 hectares, with over seventy percent of smallholder farmers owning their land with farming experience between 1 and 75 years and having, on average, four farm workers (see section 6.1.7). The reason for farming was for both commercial and family needs. The study integrated different meteorological data with quantitative and qualitative perspectives to understand the complexity of the influence of climate change on smallholder farmers' food security in the Koung-Khi department. Integrating local insights and meteorological data using a mixed-methods approach revealed that smallholder farmers are experiencing the effects of weather variability in their locality.

The study integrated results from surveys of smallholder farmers, government representatives, community leaders, church leaders, and representatives of non-governmental organisations and 17 years of precipitation data to establish the climate variability in the investigated area.

The findings showed that smallholder farmers and stockholders experienced an increase in hot days, a decrease in rainy days, soil erosion, drought, and heavy rains. The precipitation data shows a reduction in the rainfall and duration of the number of rainy days. The precipitation patterns in the investigated area witnessed severe fluctuations between 2005 and 2022, reaching their minimal point in 2015 (1123.8 mm/year). The trend diagram indicates a reduction in precipitation for the upcoming years.

There has been a gradual decline in the length of the rainy season between 2005 and 2022, with the lowest levels witnessed in 2017 and 2018 (92 days of rain in the year). The trend suggests that farmers should expect shorter rainy seasons in the future.

The observed climate variability appears to vary from one district to another. Also, smallholder farmers witnessed more significant weather variability in the highland zone compared to the lowland, mainly experiencing water scarcity, which needs to be investigated further. The negative influence of weather variability has been on yield production through the decrease in quantity and the product's quality change. Variability in the climate in the study area has contributed to the changes in the yield trends for potatoes, beans, and maize. This observation emphasises that non-climatic variables influence staple crop production in the Koung-Khi department. Fluctuations in climatic and non-climatic patterns in the department of Koung-Khi led to an alteration in farming practices, which in turn had substantial socio-economic implications at both domestic and district levels.

Although these changes have brought challenges, such as severe impacts on food availability, accessibility, and utilisation and threats to human health, they also present opportunities for innovation and adaptation. As the world and the country's population rates are increasing, finding ways to optimise the use of farming land is essential. Implementing innovative solutions and sustainable practices can preserve land and improve fertility. With careful planning and thoughtful resource management, thriving communities can emerge, and people and the environment will benefit. Smallholder farmers in the Koung-Khi department are already applying a confident attitude to adapt and manage the impact of weather variability in their area. Using the adaptation strategy index permits the ranking of the adaptation approaches adopted by smallholder farmers to cope with the threat caused by climate change to staple crops in the Koung-Khi department.

The variety of adaptation strategies adopted in different districts underscores the impracticality of a one-size-fits-all approach to coping with climate variations due to variations in perception and available resources. However, a particular crop yield may experience the same effects from weather variability in one location as in another. Therefore, duplicating specific crop adaptation measures in other localities can be accomplished by considering all essential resources. Though numerous adaptation strategies are applied to handle the effects of climate change, implementing them appears to be costly. Numerous smallholder farmers in rural settings need support to adapt to climate change. Poverty is one of the most noteworthy obstacles that hinder smallholder farmers' ability to implement effective adaptation strategies.

To address this challenge, tackling the root cause of poverty and enabling subsistence farmers to take the steps necessary to adapt to climate change are essential. This assistance contributes to their resilience to future challenges and improves food security. With the right approach, sustainable application could lead smallholder farmers to lessen nutritional incongruence in the face of climate change.

The findings support the conclusion that food security in the Koung-Khi department is adversely impacted in all districts, but differently.

In the Poumougne district, smallholder farmers perceive a more severe impact of climate change on food availability and accessibility. However, in the district of Demdeng, severe impacts on food utilisation are more significant. The finding reveals that the district of Poumougne has the lowest awareness rate regarding climate change, indicating the need for sensitisation. Furthermore, the district of Poumougne has the highest proportion of smallholder farmers, who must be sensitised about climate change. Conversely, the number of climate change adaptation approaches used significantly affects the food availability index. Specifically, increasing the number of adaptation strategies used reduces the chances of a relative risk ratio in favour of having a weak impact instead of a severe impact by 0.797. In addition, increasing the number of adaptation strategies will increase the relative risk ratio of suffering a moderate impact instead of a severe impact by 1.452. Smallholder farmers in the Koung-Khi department face several limitations and unpredictable weather patterns, jeopardising their efforts to acquire and maintain good nutritional status.

Despite the challenges in dealing with the influences of climate variability on food security, smallholder farmers have the opportunity for improvement. Collaborative exchange with the state, NGOs, and stakeholders can set up regulations and initiatives supporting smallholder farmers in reaching food sovereignty. While food assistance can be required in certain conditions to deal with immediate needs, it is essential to prioritise long-lasting answers that empower smallholder farmers to obtain sustainable food security. The research findings indicate that interventions at the policy and strategic level could be adopted to heighten smallholder farmers' adaptive competence and long-standing toughness to climate change.

7.8. Testing of Research Hypothesis

This study assesses the hypothesis that climate change negatively influences food production in the Koung-Khi department and reduces food availability among smallholder farmers. In social science research, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches in research design enhances the validity and reliability of a study (Abowitz and Toole, 2010). Following the same idea, Onwuegbuzie and Leech (2004) argue that mixed methods research represents the absolute “gold standard” for studying phenomena because it enhances the interpretation of significant quantitative and qualitative evaluation findings. In mixed methods with sequential type, the formulation of hypotheses is very frequent (Fetters, Curry and Creswell, 2013). The existing variations in mixed methods research allow for the development, testing, or confirmation of hypotheses (Palinkas et al., 2015).

Robey (1994) states that hypothesis testing, and generation represent two distinct research objectives. In hypothesis testing research, the investigator specifies one or more hypotheses based on existing theory or data and then puts these hypotheses to an empirical test with a new data set.

Conversely, in hypothesis-generating research, the investigator explores a set of data, searching for relationships and patterns, and then proposes a hypothesis, which may be tested in some subsequent study.

However, Turner, Cardinal and Burton (2017) state that hypothesis testing is only sometimes necessary while using mixed-method triangulation because the approach strengthens the validity of the results. Moreover, Onwuegbuzie and Collins (2007) claim that hypothesis testing in a mixed-method approach can still occur to give more weight to the validity of the finding. Following the same vein, Angius (2014) emphasises that a hypothesis can be empirically tested for research to justify or confirm hypotheses instead of testing. Barr et al. (2013) assert that if research does not have to experiment with a hypothesis beforehand, there are still sufficient ways to test it empirically. For instance, surveys and questionnaires can collect data from individuals or groups about their experiences, attitudes, or behaviours. This approach can be helpful for testing or justifying hypotheses about people's beliefs, perceptions, understanding, or opinions. While these approaches may not provide the same level of control or precision as experimental studies, they can still provide valuable empirical evidence to test and refine hypotheses (Crano, Brewer and Lac, 2014; Kätsyri et al., 2015).

It is essential to choose the most appropriate method for the hypothesis being tested and to use rigorous methods to ensure the validity and reliability of the data collected (Ranney et al., 2015). In this study, the methodology used was mixed-method concurrent triangulation, where hypothesis testing can imply using ideas from Onwuegbuzie and Collins (2007). Consequently, based on the hypothesis that climate change negatively influences food production in the Koung-Khi department and reduces food availability among smallholder farmers, a comprehensive testing and validation of the hypothesis was based on observation of the findings from qualitative and quantitative findings. Meteorological data from the Koung-Khi department provided decreased precipitation trends in the locality from 2006 to 2022. Also, the computation of staple food production from 2006 to 2022 in the department of Koung-Khi revealed that the quantity of output of maize, beans, and potatoes has decreased over time. Regression analysis made it possible to correlate data from staple food production with meteorological data. Statistical methods are used to establish correlations between climatic variations and crop yields. According to the precipitation coefficient, a 1% rise in precipitation rate corresponds to a 3.07% decline in potato production (see section 6.3.1.5). Concerning the presented findings, a 1% rise in precipitation results in a 1.9% decrease in bean production (see section 6.3.1.3). The statistical analysis shows no significant correlation between precipitation and maize production.

Consequently, any fluctuations in rainfall are unlikely to considerably impact maize production in the designated region (see section 6.3.1.4). Additionally, a non-climatic variable like the surface cultivated presented a decreasing trend from 2006 to 2022. Regarding the impacts of climate change on food availability, the results revealed that from the total smallholder farmers surveyed, 62.45 percent reported that climate change severely impacts their food availability.

A logistic regression analysis model with several explanatory variables was used to explain the impact of climate change on the food availability index.

The average effect of climate change on the food availability index (FAvI) was 3.44, meaning that the availability of food is highly impacted by climate change. A multinomial logit regression was also used to estimate the effects of climate change on the food availability index.

The overall results were statistically significant at a 1 percent significance level. The findings revealed that the number of climate change events witnessed has no significant effect on the food availability index. Conversely, the quantity of climate change effects experienced by a farm household significantly impacts the food availability index. It can be deduced that a rise in the occurrence of climate change effects lowers the likelihood of experiencing a moderate impact as opposed to a severe one.

Due to changes in weather patterns, food production in the study area has decreased, leading to food shortages. The set of evidence mentioned above, resulting in the decrease in the quantity of staple food production and the excessive value of the food availability index added to the significant correlation between weather variation and decreased food production, has strengthened the hypothesis that weather modification is negatively affecting food production in the department Koungh Khi and reducing food availability among smallholder farmers. Moreover, projections of the results determined that a reduction in food production will still accrue and will continuously jeopardise food availability among smallholder farmers in the Koungh-Khi department. Global climate change is a substantial issue that significantly affects agricultural systems worldwide. The hypothesis formulated here specifically justifies that the department of Koungh-Khi is facing adverse impacts of climate change, resulting in reduced food production and decreased food availability for smallholder farmers. Several factors related to climate change can contribute to this situation. For example, the increase in average temperatures affects food crops by altering rainfall patterns, increasing evaporation, and inducing a greater frequency of droughts. Erratic rainfall and tremendous weather incidents like cyclones can damage crops and agricultural infrastructure. These climate changes also disrupt local farming systems, decreasing crop yields and food availability for smallholder farmers in the Koungh-Khi department. Smallholder farmers often depend on their production for their livelihoods and are vulnerable to disruptions caused by climate change. By providing a detailed and in-depth answer to this hypothesis, the study wants to highlight the importance of understanding the effects of climate change on the food security and well-being of smallholder farmers in the Koungh-Khi department. The results can inform policies and actions to mitigate the adverse effects of climate change on food production and build the toughness of smallholder farmers. I hope this study will contribute to raising awareness about the confronts faced by smallholder farmers and promoting adaptation and mitigation measures to ensure sustainable food production and food security in the Koungh-Khi department.

Chapter Eight: Conclusion, Policy Implications, and Recommendations

8.0 Introduction

This chapter summarises the key findings from the previous chapters, including smallholder farmers' perceptions of the impacts of climate change on staple crops, the adaptation strategies applied, and the challenges faced in the department of Koung-Khi. The chapter also presents the conclusion drawn from the study, the policy options available for adaptation, and the roles of various stockholders in applying these options. The chapter offers recommendations for adaptation strategies and outlines the way forward for future research. The objectives of this research were to:

- Q1 Investigate changes in weather patterns in the study area and their influence on staple food (maize, beans, and potatoes).
- Q2 Assess the current state of the impact of climate change on food availability, accessibility, and utilisation among smallholder farmers.
- Q3 Explore smallholder farmers' adaptation strategies and the challenges they face.

This research analysed the influence of weather alteration on smallholder farmers' food security in the department of Koung-Khi. The study adopted a mixed-methods approach comprised of key informant interviews with stakeholders, surveys, and focus group discussions with smallholder farmers. The research findings provide new insights into the subject and adaptations applied locally to address the threat. Furthermore, the findings shed light on smallholder farmers' challenges while implementing adaptation measures. The outcome of this investigation will enable policymakers and agricultural practitioners to implement effective measures to adapt to climate change and enhance food security.

8.1 Summary of the Work Performed: A Short Overview of the Work and its Scope

Chapter 1 serves as the foundation of the research by clearly explaining why the study is essential. The general introduction in this chapter included the subject matter, the key concepts, and an overview of climate change and food security. The chapter illustrated the gap it aims to fill and how it will fit into a broader academic or practical context. This chapter analyses concepts, reviews relevant literature, and considers the context to develop the research question. At the end of the chapter, the structure of the thesis is elaborated. Considering that this research is taking place in Cameroon, an African country, some facts in Chapter 2 are presented to allow the reader to know more about the country's demographic, geographic, and historical information.

Considering the investigation of the impact of climate change in Cameroon, it is essential to present the different climate zones of the country, which represent its climatological diversity. This diversity in the climate from inland is basically because of his geographical situation, which is sharing a border with the Atlantic Ocean. Interestingly, while the country's south part has significant rain, the north faces water scarcity. Nevertheless, the changing climate is threatening many sectors, for instance, water resources, human health, and livelihood. More precisely, the agricultural sector is affected as agriculture practices in Cameroon are highly rain-fed. Episodic drought and flood jeopardise agricultural practice, particularly in rural settings with poor and low adaptative resources, as agriculture is among the economic and job drivers in Cameroon. Also, infrastructure, which serves the best practices of agriculture, is not well considered by the state. Considering this, Chapter 2 exposed how climate change impacts roads, food storage, and other agricultural infrastructure. All this impact threatens the availability, accessibility, and utilisation of food in urban and rural areas. Climate change is an ongoing phenomenon; therefore, I have examined the future trend of climate change in Cameroon, which is how the climate will continue to increase. This is then called upon to urge policy implementation at all levels of society.

Chapter 3 presents the diversity of agriculture in Cameroon and the different agroecological zones. This is one of the country's riches, as it allows many crops to grow in the different agroecological zones, making the country the breadbasket of Central Africa. In each agroecological zone, the climates of Cameroon also give diversity to agriculture. Given that each type of climate in Cameroon is favourable for a specific crop type, a deep overview of the agriculture sector in Cameroon allows us to shed light on the status of food security in Cameroon through a review of existing literature. More comprehensively, in this chapter, the literature about the current state of food security is explored, and the influence of climate change on its stability is exposed. By applying this approach, Chapter 3 indicates to what extent the literature has investigated the impact of climate change on food security in Cameroon. It gives the researcher a significant guide to current statutes on climate change and food security. In Chapter 3, the main crop under investigation is also presented, as these are among the most cooked staple foods in Cameroon and in the neighbouring countries. As the investigation is taking place in the western region of Cameroon, Chapter 3 gives a comprehensive overview of climate and agriculture in the Western Region. This chapter has provided information on how climate change affects agriculture in the West. Through Chapter 3, a deep exploration of critical concepts of relevant scholarly work is explored to complete the research question.

Chapter 4 provides a broad picture of the mixed methods applied to the research. It was good to justify the choice of concurrent mixed-method triangulation for this research. The main reason was the massive complexity of the research team's challenge. The team had to survey at least ten farmer communities in different localities. Motivation was my first strength in facing these challenges. Because I was the team leader, I had to empower the rest of the team members to avoid any bias during the data collection on the field because a small mistake could jeopardise my academic journey.

I have learned a lot from this methodology and hope to use those skills to contribute to scientific knowledge, principally in data collection with indigenous groups, fieldwork in rural settings, and the best method to approach or contact rural communities. I gained part of these experiences from my master's thesis since it was also with smallholder farmers; working with this population group has allowed me to acquire specific practical field skills. As I mentioned earlier, there is a need to adopt new methods of catching the attention of the rural population and getting information from them, which will help them and others. Rural communities have a significant role in the research field because more attention needs to be given to them, and they can also be the source of or contribute to the scientific solution of a phenomenon. This chapter details the quantitative and qualitative approaches used to collect data. The procedure allows us to maximise our time and obtain valuable and vital information while working with a group. The success of this methodology is also due to the attributes of the government representative in the department of Koung-khi and the university lecturer who was among the research team. From participant selection to data collection, I must ensure the procedure is accurate and valid.

Chapters 5 and 6 present the study's main findings, and Chapter 7 discusses the findings and triangulates the results. Chapter 5 mainly provides the results from the qualitative approach with the focus group discussion and the key informant interview. Chapter 6 presents the results of the quantitative approach to the survey. The finding is based on the smallholder farmers' perceptions of the impact of climate variability on food security in their locality. Referring to Chapter 5 on the qualitative approach, it was quite an exciting experience working with diverse participants with different backgrounds and know-how. This diversity of participants is also what gives strong validity to the findings of the research. I was able to obtain information from diverse sources to find out how their intercorrelation can influence another variable. Most importantly, during the focus group and interview, participants were engaged in sharing their thoughts, hoping that their voices would be heard at the international level as I told them how they could contribute to or be part of the solution to the threat caused by climate change. Also, the enthusiasm during the survey was remarkable. And I learned a lot while working with those communities. For instance, the elderly farmer expressed their opinion with a profound feeling. The expression on their faces was like, finally, I found the possibility to tell or discuss this problem that has burdened me for a long time. During the group discussion, farmers mentioned that climate change is causing big trouble in their food systems. They talk about the decrease in food crop production. This information was confirmed by a decrease in the quantity of food crop production in the study area. Also, the statistical data show that climatic and non-climatic factors affect crop production.

Additionally, cultivating a larger surface area can increase maize production (see section 6.3.1.4). Based on the coefficient, potato production is projected to increase by 0.59% for every 1% increase in cultivated surface area (see section 6.3.1.5).

All these prove that climate change affects farmers' food security in the Koung-Khi department. There is a need to join hands and think of better adaptation strategies from which all community members should benefit. The research shows that the district of Bayangam has a higher education rate. And more aware of climate change. This is an essential indicator for policymakers to consider education in a rural setting because it will help farmers improve their perception and adapt. Smallholder farmers in the Koung-Khi department are already applying a confident attitude to adapt and manage the impact of weather variability in their area. Using the adaptation strategy index permits the ranking of the adaptation approaches adopted by smallholder farmers to cope with the threat caused by climate change to staple crops in the Koung-Khi department. The first adaptation strategy that smallholder farmers are applying is agricultural diversification. The literature revealed that smallholder farmers in rural settings in other African countries prioritise changing the planting date. Additionally, the method has given a clear picture of which adaptation activities are prioritised in the study area from one district to another. Adaptation practices are not uniform across all districts. For instance, in the districts of Bayangam and Demdeng, the leading adaptation practice was agricultural diversification. In the district of Poumougne, the first adaptation practice was income-generating activities.

Moreover, the ranking of challenges smallholder farmers face in applying adaptation strategies using the problem confrontation index (PCI) has given the lack of water availability as the top first challenge in the department of Koung-Khi. At the district level, the first challenge in Bayangam was the lack of water availability. In the district of Demdeng, there was a lack of access to timely weather information; in Poumougne, there was a lack of water availability. The variety of adaptation strategies adopted in different districts underscores the impracticality of a one-size-fits-all approach to coping with climate variations due to variations in perception and available resources. However, a particular crop yield may experience the same effects from weather variability in one location as in another. Therefore, duplicating specific crop adaptation measures in other localities can be accomplished by considering all essential resources.

I have also learnt about the problem-confrontation approach from the group's differences. For example, the approach of the district's smallholder farmers differed. In some groups, they were a standard problem-solving approach. Farmers expressed a similar approach to handle climate's impact on crop production. However, some participants did not collaborate to solve the issue. The stronger community willing to cope with the threat was in Bayangam. Agricultural posts and leaders are more in communion with the population in those areas because participants in that locality were proud of the support they received from the agricultural post. The church's local leader also participated in key informant interviews and mentioned the kindness among the population. He notes that this is making him do all he can to keep the joy in the community through the blessing from God. He says he supports pregnant women, new-borns, and older adults.

This shared living between the community members and its leaders can also be considered a strength to empower and allow the community to come together for one cause, like climate change, affecting the nutritional status of all. This observation shows that community leaders can majorly influence the climate change adaptation process and strategy.

Additionally, it strengthens the self-motivation adaptation approach, which boosts the Bottom-up adaptation approach. The bottom-up adaptation approach supports the process that the farmers themselves should initiate adaptation ideas and processes. It will be arranged in such a way the experts or agricultural agent will approach the farmer and ask what adaptation strategies they are applying which are proper to them and their locality and how they think these practices could be improved to give a better response to the adaptation and increase food crop production. The ideal will be to put the farmer on the panel to listen to what they are doing to support food production and empower them on their way forward to improve the practice. This will be done instead of inviting experts and scientists to come into the village and tell the farmer that this is your problem, and that is what you should do to solve it.

Also, this approach to addressing climate change involves climate justice, which intends to safeguard the rights of the most vulnerable individuals and promote a fair distribution of the burdens and benefits of climate change and its effects. Another practical aspect of climate justice would be to organise the Conference of Parties (CoP) in developing countries where the most vulnerable individuals live. A practical example would be to organise the CoP in the Bandjoun in Cameroon or Kumpur in Nepal. Indigenous peoples living there will then be invited to the panel to share their understanding, perceptions, and challenges. This will address the fairness in promoting and raising awareness about global warming. It answers the question raised at the end of Chapter 2: safeguarding vulnerable communities and fostering international cooperation to prioritise long-term sustainability over short-term gains. Conversely, a farmer in another locality was waiting for help and support from the government or an NGO, and they could not do anything without support from the external community. This idea cannot be criticised, as most of the farmers who had this idea were the least educated participants.

This study focused on the microcosmic that are the same all over sub-Saharan, Asia, Latin America, and some poor regions in developed countries. Agriculture contributes massively to the nutrition of smallholder farmers in the rural settings. This study revealed that decreased rainfall induced a weak harvest of staple food (see section). As the national population is increasing by 1.5 inhabitants per square kilometre (+2.68 percent) in 2021 (INS 2022), the country will have more people who will need food in the future, leading to more deforestation to increase the quantity of food. This now raises sustainable land management to increase production in the face of an increased population. This means the population's size is growing, but the size of the country still needs to grow. This makes me ask myself how the situation will be in 100 years or more. The rich nations could have made little progress in adaptation.

But what will the sort of population living in the rural setting be? So, caring about the future generation is our duty and responsibility because we will be the cause of their environmental problem. This study's finding shows a decrease in rainfall, which is like Bomdzele and Molua's (2023) study. However, the particularity of this research is the finding on ranking the adaptation strategy and problem confrontation in the same way as effective adaptation, which must be empowered.

Lastly, it aims to empower self-motivation and an affective adaptation approach to find the best method to alleviate them, starting from the bottom to the top to shed light on the challenges.

8.2 Limitations of the Study

Despite its significant contributions, the prevailing study has limitations that may impact the authenticity of its findings, particularly regarding data series and analysis. However, it is crucial to recognise that these boundaries are within the study's general significance and impact. Instead, these findings open possibilities for future studies to build upon and address the limitations to enhance our understanding of the issue. The investigation involved gathering primary facts through group discussions and interviews. While this approach was successful, it is essential to acknowledge that subjective biases and capacity inaccuracies may have influenced the collected responses. Adopting an optimistic approach and conducting a comprehensive analysis while accounting for biases and obstacles is essential for ensuring the highest level of validity in the results. Respondents may have encountered challenges with emphasis stages due to their reliance on previous studies and memories. This becomes clear when considering climate-related hazards and how they affect the local environment. However, it is essential to appreciate and consider their views and use them constructively to pick out capability areas for development. Implementing proactive measures to handle demanding situations can foster a resilient and sustainable future. The main objective of the survey was to collect respondents' opinions regarding changes in food security, and it did not involve any direct measurements of crop yields.

Despite the influence of subjective factors, the gathered records provide relevant and distinctive information. The significance of these details cannot be overstated in our efforts to gain a more profound understanding of how nearby farmers perceive essential climate changes. The statistics provided valuable information about farmers' attitudes toward climate change, including their concerns, challenges, and priorities. Furthermore, the facts highlighted farmers' ability to adapt to climate change and implement strategies to mitigate its effects. Understanding that participants may intentionally provide false demographic data is essential for the central body. Some respondents in the Koung-Khi department may have submitted incorrect statistics. Regardless of the capability issue, valuable insights can still be gained from the records by employing theoretical frameworks to identify potential relationships between variables. Nevertheless, it is crucial to be cautious when using independent variables to anticipate the outcomes of other structured variables, as this method can produce deceptive effects.

Despite this, this analysis can still help uncover potential connections between variables. When interpreting the study's results, it is crucial to consider these factors and approach them constructively for a deeper understanding of the data.

Furthermore, the study employed socio-demographic variables of smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-Khi to determine how they perceive weather variability in their area and how it influences food security.

The availability of information may have an impact on these relationships. Therefore, when analysing the results, it is essential to consider the predictors to understand the underlying elements comprehensively. The study utilised socio-demographic variables to assess farmers' understanding of climate variability in the department of Koung-Khi and related hazards to nutritional status. The effect of fact availability on those correlations was emphasised, highlighting the need to recollect all predictors while reading the findings to gain a comprehensive knowledge of the underlying factors. As such, when deciphering the outcomes, we must remember all the predictors to ensure an accurate comprehension of the relationships among the variables. Because of economic constraints, only one department had been selected from eight to represent the western region. However, the geographic, cultural, and socio-economic traits of smallholder farmers within the Western region are very similar; therefore, they are unlikely to be significantly different across the region. Although the analysis used four districts, records have been collected in ten localities within the Koung-Khi department. The data accumulated had been adequate to draw together essential generalisations to inform academics. The climate data were only precipitation records, given that Cameroon's agriculture is rain-fed. Moreover, Cameroon has only two seasons: rainy and dry seasons. This symbolises that the absence of rain symbolises the presence of sunlight. Nonetheless, combining qualitative and quantitative data provides a comprehensive validation of research findings, ensuring the results are robust and reliable with informative conclusions.

8.3 Contributions of the Research

8.3.1 Research Involvement in the Smallholder Farmers' Understanding of the Threat

Integrating agricultural and climate data in this study has significantly contributed to the consideration of smallholder farmers' insights into climate change. The findings reveal complex, unrelated impacts of climate change and changes in agricultural practices in three districts with similar agroecological characteristics. Chapter Five highlights the outcomes of focus group discussions and key informant interviews. This chapter shows that smallholder farmers have witnessed the rising temperature. The indication is the rise in the number of hot days. The reduction in the number of rainy days was also among the significant climate change effects witnessed by smallholder farmers. The computation of climate data justifies this statement made by the farmer.

Additionally, numerous climate events, such as soil erosion and heavy wind, were more recurrent in the highlands. In response to climate variability, the smallholder farmer prioritises specific adaptation practices like agricultural diversification, increased use of irrigation, and the practice of intercropping. Among the smallholder farmer community, pregnant women, newborn babies, and older people emerged as a vulnerable group. Their nutritional status was at risk due to the unpredictable weather patterns, necessitating special care. The districts were sharing common climate variability, though they are distant. Nevertheless, adaptation practices differed from one district to another.

Other stockholders, such as government representatives, church leaders, and NGO representatives, provided supplemental evidence and validation. In their adaptation efforts, smallholder farmers were primarily helped and supported by the practices and methods being used at the local level. Appreciations were commonly made for counselling on nutritional needs for the woman during and after pregnancy. Income-generation activity was also among the common adaptation strategies employed by stockholders.

8.3.2 Research Contribution to the Scholarly Literature

The research contributed to the scholarly literature by enlarging knowledge on climate change and food security in Sub-Saharan Africa, focusing on rural settings. The response to the research's first question shed light on the changes in weather patterns in the study area and their influence on staple foods (maize, beans, and potatoes). This has contributed to the present literature on the status of staple foods in the face of weather variability and its understanding from a rural farmer perspective, which are needed to comprehensively address climate change at the local and national levels. The second research question addresses the current state of the impact of climate change on food availability, accessibility, and utilisation among smallholder farmers. In achieving this, the study provides the literature and states evidence on the present food security status among smallholder farmers in the study area. This can be used to communicate facts about food security in rural settings. The third research question investigates smallholder farmers' adaptation strategies and challenges. This has added to the literature on the adaptation approach prioritised by smallholder farmers and the challenges faced. This has added to the literature on the adaptation approach prioritised by smallholder farmers and the challenges they face in implementing adaptation strategies. These findings safeguard future research on the topic or the same area of interest. In addition, the findings admitted variables on insights of climate change that can meaningfully help researchers breed new hypotheses and interrogations for advanced evaluation, predominantly in rural areas in Sub-Saharan African countries.

The results from this investigation can be generalised to other rural settings in Cameroon and Sub-Saharan Africa, facing similar agroecological characteristics and weather variabilities. Nevertheless, further research is needed to confirm the transferability of the other regions and countries. The investigation did not tackle the nutritional value consumed locally by the smallholder farmers. Therefore, this approach is an interesting topic for future exploration.

The study adopted a mixed-method concurrent triangulation design, including quantitative and qualitative data collected simultaneously. This approach is efficient in terms of time-saving, and concurrent triangulation designs use qualitative and quantitative data to define relationships more accurately among variables of interest. An integrated approach to comprehensively addressing the research objective is fundamental to enhancing the understanding of the outcomes. This method emerges among researchers as an essential tool for concomitant investigation while referring to rural settings. This research has added to fundamental thinking by bringing imperative experimental understandings to the literature.

The association of multiple scales to tackle climate change's impact on food security in the department of Koung-Khi gives rise to inclusive consideration of the local and regional threat of weather variability on staple foods. The ranking of the adaptation strategy index and problem confrontation index guides future researchers in prioritising the investigation topic or study area. This strategy encourages researchers to apply efficient and thriving design investigations to alleviate climate change and food security risks at various locality levels. The findings give rise to significant evidence for policymakers to adopt a reasonable approach to evaluating and handling climate change threats at all levels. This study provides an opening for government officials, policymakers, and development experts to collaborate and incorporate a variety of standpoints and comprehension systems into upcoming climate change and agricultural policies, as the current climate change and adaptation policies need to recognise knowledge integration sufficiently. As a result, smallholder farmers can establish resilience to changing and unpredictable weather conditions.

8.3.3 Theoretical and Practical Policy Implications of the Research

The concerns of this study have policy implications. Good social policies point towards benefit adaptation policies. Governments must recognise the importance of preventing weather change and promoting food safety at all stages. Policies and measures should be developed to mitigate the effects of climate change on agriculture and expand the resilience of the most vulnerable populations. Policies need to consider the correlation between weather irregularity, food security, and the social factors of health. To accomplish this, agriculture, health, and stakeholders interested in economic improvements need to collaborate. Moreover, policies must consider the unique desires of the most predisposed populations, and measures should be taken to reinforce the resilience of rural agencies and smallholder farmers. To provide specific food protection for the most affected populations, investments in sustainable agriculture are necessary, as are rights to water and infrastructure and social safety programmes.

The policy implication should consider that farmers are prioritising some adaptation strategies in one area rather than another. The research findings will give evidence to the state, national, and international organisations to prioritise actions and favour the sufficient use of resources. By considering prioritisation, the accomplishment will favour sufficient use of available material or resources.

The findings of this study add value to policy by enhancing the possibility of using climate variability and resource control strategies to increase farm productivity. The findings reveal that farmers in the Koung-Khi department need more government guidance in adjusting to weather variations. Ntali et al. (2023) have discovered similar observations in northern Cameroon, Fonjong and Zama et al. (2023) within the northwest and southwest of the neighbouring region. The survival of farmers in the face of climate variability commonly depends on their very own efforts, with only a minimum of help from an extension group of stakeholders and non-governmental actors. This observation outlines several coping and adaptation strategies to support farmers in adapting and attaining long-term resilience and food security.

Although future efforts may be made to enhance farmers' adaptive capability, combining these variation strategies and rules with ongoing and deliberate adaptation to increase farm production for smallholder farmers is crucial. It is essential to integrate these efforts with current coping strategies and resource management to ensure that practical assistance for smallholder farmers will be necessary. As a result, poverty reduction efforts can be supported while sustainability goals are achieved. These efforts include decreasing emissions, sustainably coping with natural resources, and growing farm yield. Ensuring sustainable control of water and forestry resources in changing weather is imperative. The study findings indicated that smallholder farmers in the three districts responded differently to adaptation strategies and confronted diverse challenges. Developing and implementing sustainable policies at the local, regional, and state levels can be accomplished through utilising the diversity challenges and coping strategies at the policy level. Policies should empower effective adaptation at the local level. This approach is beneficial for the present and future generations regarding ecosystem conservation.

During the group discussion, smallholder farmers expressed emotions about the environment. This practical expression could allow the state to develop and integrate different environmental or ecosystem conservation policy perspectives. Elderly smallholder farmers discussed the connection between humans and nature, emphasising that every tree represents life. They mentioned their father planted a tree in the village to symbolise the universal connection at childbirth. Rural populations may have a stronger connection to nature. Understanding the human-environmental emotional bond is vital for sustainability and ecosystem conservation. This connection encompasses overall well-being. Humans interact with the environment through culture and resource management. Emotional connection fosters positive relationships. This promotes sustainable policies for the environment and human well-being. This approach aligns with agroforestry applications, which policymakers should also consider. Integrating and developing agroforestry policies will incorporate enhanced agricultural landscapes to improve soil health, boost biodiversity, and provide additional sources of income for smallholder farmers. Empower smallholders to plant a diverse range of bushes alongside vegetation and livestock and create more resilient and sustainable farming systems to improve adaptation to weather change and variability. The approach additionally helps to sequester carbon in the soil and bushes, contributing to the effort to fight weather exchange.

To assist smallholder farmers in adopting agroforestry practices, governments, NGOs, and stakeholders can establish guidelines and tasks that promote sustainable farming practices, improve the right of credit entry, and provide training and schooling on climate-resilient agriculture.

8.3.4 State and International Policy Implications

As the climate is still changing, the real challenge today is finding ways and means to reverse the trend and improve this level of well-being. To this end, an environmental programme must be implemented to limit climate change in the worst possible scenario. It must then undergo a green revolution to breathe new life into preserving and regenerating the vegetation cover.

While safeguarding all citizens remains predominant, a state's foremost duty encompasses empowering communities through equitable access to education, healthcare, and regulations, ensuring welfare and security for everyone. Measures such as implementing policies or regulations to prevent or promote an emergency response in times of environmental disaster can be applied. Addressing challenges induced by ecological disasters in a locality requires a constructive approach toward strengthening local governance structures and institutions. Implementing this approach enhances local institutions' and infrastructure's capability to develop and implement policies that promote climate change adaptation and mitigation. Participation of the local community in policy decision-making processes increases the effectiveness of policies and programmes aimed at climate resilience. Consequently, local institutions also deserve empowerment by cultivating a promising environment where they may take preemptive initiatives to mitigate the community consequences of climate change. Applying climate change adaptation strategies should ensure that support is provided to those most in need. This involves targeting the most vulnerable individual group and prioritising the most affected localities, such as people living in extreme poverty, those who are disabled or elderly, or those who have been affected by specific crises or disasters. This could be effective in assisting those who are in the greatest need of support. This approach improves lives and promotes equality and social justice. It can include training and education on climate-resilient agriculture, enhancing agricultural diversification practices, improving access to credit or agricultural subsidies and weather forecasts, and crop-related insurance.

On the other hand, targeting the most affected locality addresses broader issues for the entire community. This approach should consider areas experiencing a higher impact of environmental degradation in the form of challenges. Also, the initiative can build more resilient and sustainable communities that can withstand future shocks or crises. Working collaboratively holistically creates a more just and equitable society that supports the most vulnerable individuals and communities. It can include making a collective irrigation system to benefit all or most of the community. Effective climate risk management ensures the country's continued economic growth and development through proactive steps at the national and sub-national levels. It embraces leveraging international financial markets and structure interactions with the monetary facilities to gather and transfer know-how and risks.

Promoting climate change adaptation is essential, but it should engage all core ministries and relevant stakeholders to facilitate effective planning and implementation of policy and regulation. Cameroon's agricultural infrastructure should be equipped to cope with the challenge of a changing climate. Consideration should be oriented toward the road to accessing agricultural products in remote areas. Access to the marketplace should also be considered. Up-to-date technology for weather broadcasts should be at the disposal of smallholder farmers in the rural sector. Irrigation systems should also be improved at the local level. National and international cooperation on policy implementation plays a crucial role in successfully planning and implementing climate change adaptation. Collaborative work with subsistent farmers and policymakers could establish a constructive policy that empowers smallholder farmers to better cope with threats. Policies can include providing access to accurate climate information, promoting sustainable water availability, improving access to finance, and improving farmer training and education on farming practices and weather data availability. Reinforcing existing policies should be prioritised to ensure adequate implementation in rural areas. The various treaties ratified by African countries to protect the environment must be respected in their application.

Policy implications

Strong policies are needed to establish an agricultural livelihood. It outlines measures to help smallholder farmers cope with climate change and food security.

National Adjustment Programs (NAPs).

The NAP integrates climate adaptation into national development policies. Specific add-ons, including NAPs, should prioritise promoting climate-sensitive agriculture (CSA). CSA incorporates sustainable agricultural practices to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and increase productivity and resilience. Examples include agroforestry, conservation agriculture, and integrated pest management. Planning should support water management practices such as rainwater harvesting, irrigation, and small catchment storage. These measures help smallholder farmers deal with irregular rainfall and prolonged droughts.

Early warning systems and weather services help farmers make important decisions. Systems should support and disseminate ongoing local weather forecasts and weather advisories.

Financial and technical assistance

Small farmers need financial and technical support to adapt to climate change. Key policy interventions include Governments supporting anti-climate technologies and practices. Financial incentives encourage farmers to invest in improved yields, soil conservation, and renewable energy.

Access to microfinance and credit facilities can finance adjustments for smallholder farmers. The policies should facilitate the establishment of rural credit cooperatives and low-interest loans by financial institutions.

Capacity building and education

Education and training are critical to the adaptive capacity of smallholder farmers. Programs in this area include Improving agricultural extension services for climate resilience.

Extension services: Strengthening agricultural extension services through ongoing training and support on climate resilience practices. Extension workers should be equipped with the latest knowledge and equipment to better support farmers.

Farmer Field Schools (FFS): Establish farmer field schools to facilitate peer learning and knowledge exchange among farmers. FFS can serve as a platform to showcase new technologies, share best practices, and promote adaptive community-based approaches.

Education policy: Integrating climate change education into formal and non-formal education programs. Planning should support curriculum design for modules on sustainable agriculture, weather change effects and acclimatisation approaches.

Research and Development

Agricultural research institutes: Strengthen national and regional agricultural research institutes to focus on developing climate-resistant crop varieties and agricultural strategies. Collaborative research with international organisations can increase the scope and impact of these efforts.

Field trials and demonstrations: Support field trials and demonstration projects to test and demonstrate new technologies and practices. These programs can provide empirical evidence of effectiveness and increase farmers' adoption.

Data collection and analysis: Effective adaptation strategies to enhance data collection and analysis capacity to assess climate change impacts. Programs should support the establishment of an agricultural data centre and the use of remote sensing technology.

Infrastructure development

Improving rural infrastructure is essential to increase the resilience of smallholder farmers. Key policy interventions include transportation Network: Invest in rural transport infrastructure to facilitate market access, reduce post-harvest losses, and ensure timely delivery of investment and inputs.

Irrigation: Establishment and expansion of irrigation systems to reduce reliance on unpredictable rainfall. The policy should prioritise the expansion of affordable and manageable small-scale irrigation systems for smallholder farmers.

Storage and Processing: Developing storage and processing facilities to reduce post-harvest losses and add value to agricultural production. Policies should support the development of community-based conservation solutions and encourage the private sector to invest in agricultural production.

Governmental and institutional support

Active governance and established support are crucial for the successful implementation of climate adaptation policies. Key measures include:

Policy Coordination and Coordination: To ensure coordination and synergies across various policies and programs related to agriculture, climate change and rural development. The formation of inter-member committees can facilitate coordinated planning and implementation.

Stakeholder engagement: To actively involve smallholder farmers, civil society organisations and individual stakeholders in policy formulation and decision-making. Inclusive policies can ensure that the needs and perspectives of all stakeholders are considered.

Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E): Establish a robust M&E program to control the progress and impact of change strategies and interventions. Regular reviews can identify policy changes and ensure continuous improvement.

Addressing the influences of weather change on smallholder food security in rural areas requires a comprehensive and multi-faceted strategy. By prioritising climate-sensitive agriculture, financial and practical support, capacity building, research development, infrastructure development, and effective governance, policymakers can provide resilience to smallholder farmers. This will safeguard food security and contribute to the broader sustainable development goals.

8.4 Recommendations

Better support for producers and integrating relevant adaptation measures into combating the effects of climate change will require strategic decision-making by public authorities, rural intervention structures, research, and local populations. Extending appropriate support to producers and integrating accurate adaptation strategies is essential to address climate change impacts effectively. This requires informed decision-making by public authorities, rural intervention programmes, research, and communities. By working strategically and effectively together, we can identify and implement effective solutions to mitigate the impacts of climate change and pave the way for a more sustainable future. The fate of food security rests on our actions today to safeguard the environment. We must acknowledge and take responsibility for our environmental impact to create a sustainable future for ourselves and future generations.

8.4.1 To the Public Authorities

Agriculture in Cameroon and sub-Saharan Africa is vulnerable to multiple shocks (in prices and land) mainly due to the weaknesses of household farms. Indeed, they are poor populations that need the means to increase their production or adapt to economic changes. As a result, in formulating its policies, the state must support rural people in managing their land through subsidies and training sessions. This is to allow the main stakeholders to be less vulnerable. In addition, soil rotation must be a significant prerequisite, as soils tend to see their yields decrease as their use intensity increases. While the consequences of climate change on food security are visible, their causes and origins are diverse.

Today, industries' release of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere and water pollution amplifies weather variation and its consequences. Strategies to reduce these products must be operational to mitigate the impacts of climate change. More practically, this could involve:

- I. Providing meteorological information in a form that producers can understand would signal the progress of agricultural activities such as sowing. Community media could be involved in implementing this recommendation, especially in disseminating weather information.
- II. Acquire more meteorological stations in different rural localities to provide real-time climate information.
- III. Build skilled personnel for meteorological service to deliver the meaning of meteorological data and information understandably and truthfully to the producers. Also, strengthen the capabilities of producer support agents, including Community Education and Action Centres (CEACs) and other local resource persons, on adaptation strategies to respond to producers' concerns on climate change adaptation issues.

8.4.1.1 Acknowledging Indigenous Understanding

Acknowledging and appreciating Indigenous understanding is crucial for promoting inclusive and effective decision-making processes. Collaborating with indigenous authorities will involve and attract nearby communities to decision-making. Including local knowledge in policymaking allows for a more comprehensive understanding of farmers' values and viewpoints, leading to carefully developed projects catering to specific requirements and situations. Closer collaboration with indigenous authorities enables decision-makers to craft policies and packages that serve all community members, aligning more closely with local realities. Incorporating local know-how and willpower paves the way for a revolutionary and participatory approach to policy and programme formation firmly rooted in the experiences and opinions of local communities. Sustainable and fair effects are ultimately achieved by fostering stakeholder belief and collaboration.

8.4.1.2 Research and Agriculture Practice

Prioritising sustainable and regenerative practices is a positive recommendation for agricultural studies and farming training. Promoting organic farming and reducing chemical inputs, along with practices like crop rotation and cover cropping to improve soil health, can help achieve this. Given their unique challenges, education and schooling applications are crucial for supporting small-scale and family farmers in accessing markets and financing. Furthermore, encouraging cooperation among researchers, farmers, and local communities can ensure that agricultural practices are impactful and socially conscious, leading to a more substantial and sustainable food system.

8.4.1.3 Rainwater Harvesting

Rainwater harvesting is a highly beneficial solution for maintaining water in rural areas. It is an easy and cost-effective technique that may offer a dependable water supply for various uses, including irrigation, cattle, and domestic purposes. For effective implementation, picking out the first-rate region, which can be the roof of a house, barn, or shed, is vital. The catchment area must be fabricated from a durable and non-toxic cloth, including metal or plastic, to ensure the best water harvest. After setting up the catchment area, gutters and downspouts should be hooked to gather and direct the water into a garage tank. The garage tank needs to be massive enough to hold sufficient water for the intended use and needs to be located close to the catchment location for better admission. Ensuring the garage tank is effectively sealed is fundamental to saving it from infection and evaporation.

To ensure optimal rainwater harvesting device capability, it is necessary to control it frequently, including cleaning the catchment area, gutters, and downspouts to remove blockages and debris that could have occurred in the garage tank.

Additionally, a primary flush diverter, which diverts the preliminary runoff from the catchment region to prevent debris or contaminants from entering the storage tank, is highly endorsed. Overall, rainwater harvesting is a sustainable answer to water conservation. It can help rural groups become more self-sufficient and reduce their reliance on luxurious and unreliable district water resources.

Enforcing this technique can ensure communities have the right to access a reliable water supply, which is essential for their survival and prosperity.

8.4.1.4 Empower Indigenous Storage Practice

Encouraging indigenous underground storage practices aids in fostering sustainable progress while preserving cultural heritage. These practices can be empowered by providing technical and economic support for conventional storage techniques. Also, promote using locally sourced substances and methods and collaborate with local communities and traditional holders to ensure cultural values and practices are respected. In addition, formal partnerships should be established among indigenous groups, relevant stakeholders, authority groups, and NGOs to facilitate information transfer and potential construction. The goal is to empower indigenous storage practices and promote sustainable improvement in the system, achieved through a collaborative and culturally sensitive approach.

8.4.2 Recommendations to Producers

Transparent collaboration between producers and the intervention structures is essential in implementing climate change adaptation actions. Producers must be available and receptive to better support and organise themselves as groups to facilitate the action of intervention structures, which will reduce their access to technical and financial support in terms of adaptation to climate change.

8.4.2.1 Empower Gardening Near Houses

Gardening near homes is a great way to enhance the beauty of the surroundings and promote a healthy lifestyle. It offers the opportunity to produce clean and organic food, which benefits health and reduces carbon emissions. Furthermore, gardening provides an enjoyable and appealing way to stay active outdoors. It can also bring the family closer and create a sense of belonging. Promoting nearby gardening enhances sustainability and joy in everyday life.

8.4.2.2 Empower Coming Together to Buy Adaptation Resources in Rural Settings

It is often said, “*When you are alone, you go faster, but when we are many, we go very far.*” For rural farmers, staying updated with technology and adapting to changing situations can be challenging. Collaborating with other farmers can overcome these limitations.

It lowers the costs of buying adaptation resources and encourages a sense of camaraderie and mutual support, which is valuable during times of need. Therefore, connecting with other farmers and discussing the chance to collaborate and improve farming operations is essential. Participating and sharing resources help build a more robust agricultural network that can overcome future challenges.

8.4.2.3 Having Agricultural Advisors

The smallholder farmers in the district of Poumougne mentioned the lack of agricultural advisors as the first challenge to adjusting to the impact of weather change on food security. Having a farming consultant can be beneficial for rural farmers.

These specialists could guide measures ranging from crop choice and soil control to advertising, marketing techniques, and economic planning. Farmers could optimise their yields and enhance outcomes by working with an advisor. Additionally, advisors could help farmers stay updated on trendy technology and techniques for sustainable farming.

8.4.2.4 Participation in the Pricing of the Product

During the group discussion, all smallholder farmers mentioned that pricing is made without their opinion, obstructing their efforts to gain from farming. Smallholder farmers said that when they arrive at the market, they do not know how much the price per unit of the product costs. Sometimes, the buyer tells them that the price per unit decreased an hour ago. Farmers do not have anything to check if it is true or false. The involvement of smallholder farmers in pricing enables them to receive accurate reimbursement for their labour. One way to try this is through collective trading, where farmers negotiate costs with buyers collectively. Cooperatives or various farmer corporations can facilitate this. Another method involves implicating farmers in the price chain, giving them a role in pricing, advertising, and marketing. This may be performed by offering statistics about market tendencies, charges, and those related to farmers improving marketing techniques. Finally, involving smallholder farmers in pricing their merchandise could help them promote sustainable and fair food security.

8.5 Contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Agenda 2030

Climate change has become a significant alarm for smallholder farmers due to its direct impact on food security. Due to climate change, unpredictable rainfall, and extreme weather, smallholder farmers find it difficult to grow crops and raise livestock, affecting their income, livelihood, and overall well-being. Smallholder farmers' vulnerability to climate change potentially undermines the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Agenda 2030. The SDGs aim to eradicate poverty, ensure zero hunger, and promote sustainable agriculture, among other things. However, these goals will be challenging to achieve if the impact of climate change on smallholder farmers is not addressed.

By addressing the influence of weather variation on smallholder farmers' food security in the Koung-Khi department, this study provides a clear picture of climate change in rural settings in most sub-Saharan countries. This information can contribute to the decision-making of experts who supervise SDG actions on the state of climate change. This investigation provides evidence that could help to plan and investigate "SDGs 1 eradicate poverty." By addressing the impact of climate change on the food security of smallholder farmers in the department of Koung-Khi, this study delivers a perfect representation and current picture of the nutritional statute in rural settings, which can serve as a resource to shape any SDGs 2 awareness to achieve zero hunger in rural settings of developing countries. The findings expose different environmental and non-environmental variables threatening food availability, accessibility, and utilisation in the study area or rural settings. Also, it gives a clear picture of the most affected social group and their degree of impact.

This investigation sheds light on climate change's impact on smallholder farmers' food security and gives insight into the "SDG 3 good health and well-being" because having sufficient and nutritious food is shared or results in good health and well-being. The well-defined climate change perception of smallholder farmers presented in this study can guide prioritising adaptation strategies in affected rural settings. The ranking of the adaptation strategies index provides significant information on what type of adaptation strategy smallholder farmers are already applying to alter the threat of climate change and which practices or measures they prioritise according to the threat and the knowledge they process.

Additionally, the ranking of the problem confrontation index provides significant evidence on what type of problems or challenges smallholder farmers are currently experiencing and which difficulties they are facing or sharing the most according to the threat and the knowledge they possess. This evidence can play a crucial role in the decision-making of experts that administer "SDGs 13 climate action" engagements on adaptation to climate change in rural settings and its challenges.

This indication can play a vital role in the decision-making of experts that administer "SDGs 13 climate action" engagements on adaptation to climate change in rural settings and its challenges. The investigation provides a social characteristic variable that can be used to prioritise adaptation action and conduct awareness campaigns. It also indicates the more appropriate channel to inform smallholder farmers in rural settings about climate change. It is, therefore, essential to support and respond to smallholder farmers to help them adapt to a changing climate. This can be done in various ways by penetrating climate-smart agricultural practices, improving access to markets, and ensuring access to financial services.

8.6 Future Research

More practical investigations are needed to shed light on smallholder farmers' food security status in the Koung-Khi department. One helpful approach to food security is considering BMI and calorie intake. These metrics can provide valuable insights into the complex relationship between food access and health effects. This information can enhance targeted interventions that address the specific needs of communities struggling with food insecurity. Additionally, BMI and calorie intake measurements can provide valuable insights into one's fitness and nutritional needs, helping them make informed choices about their diets and lifestyles. More investigation is required to apprehend how climate change affects food security and health and assess the value of measures to mitigate these effects. Among this research, agricultural research should be directed towards making new crops more resilient and adaptive to recent climate changes. Research centres or universities should be involved. In addition, irrigated crops must be promoted to reduce dependence on ever-decreasing rainfall.

- Explore specific adaptation and mitigation solutions to strengthen communities' resilience to climate change's food security and health impacts.
- Review strategies to promote sustainable agriculture, reduce the impact of climate change on food production, and ensure adequate food availability.
- Assess the impact of social protection policies on preventing food insecurity and its effects on the health of vulnerable populations.
- Analyse the relationships between food insecurity, malnutrition, and non-communicable diseases to understand better climate change's long-term effects on people's health.

The journey embarked upon in this thesis has explored the intricate intersection of weather variability, agriculture, and food security in rural landscapes. Qualitative and quantitative investigations revealed the intensity and nuances of the challenges posed by a changing climate to the livelihoods of rural communities. Changes in climatic and non-climatic patterns have exposed vulnerabilities in food security. Food security within climate exchange requires interdisciplinary and holistic approaches that consider not only meteorological changes but also poverty, inequality, and access to resources. The results provide a clear designation for integrating weather-resilient practices into agricultural regulations.

They highlight the urgency of supporting rural groups striving to strengthen and innovate. This thesis presents a significant contribution to evidence-based decision-making, providing policymakers with valuable insights to inform strategies that seek to improve food security while mitigating the adverse effects of climate change. Finally, as we progress in this thesis, it becomes evident that the imperative is to convert knowledge into action. The impact of weather variability on food safety is a pressing issue. The insights acquired from this study serve as a guiding light, illuminating a route towards sustainable, resilient, and equitable food structures in the face of an uncertain future. The insights disseminated here catalyse fruitful exchanges, motivating future research, policy reform, and transformative actions that preserve the basic entitlement to food for all.

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GLOSSARY AND KEY CONCEPTUAL TERMS

Adaptation

In human systems, the process of adjustment to actual or expected climate and its effects to moderate harm or exploit beneficial opportunities. In natural systems, the process of adjustment to actual climate and its effects; human intervention may facilitate adjustment to expected climate and its effects.

2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development

A UN resolution in September 2015 adopting a plan of action for people, planet, and prosperity in a new global development framework anchored in 17 Sustainable Development Goals (U.N., 2015; Möller et al., 2023, p. 2898).

Adaptation options

The array of strategies and measures that are available and appropriate for addressing adaptation. They include a wide range of actions that can be categorised as structural, institutional, ecological, or behavioural (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2898).

Community-based adaptation

Local, community-driven adaptation. Community-based adaptation focuses attention on empowering and promoting the adaptive capacity of communities. It is an approach that takes context, culture, knowledge, agency, and preferences of communities as strengths (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2898).

Ecosystem-based adaptation (EBA)

The use of ecosystem management activities to increase resilience and reduce the vulnerability of people and ecosystems to climate change (Campbell et al., 2009). See also Nature-based solution (NBS) (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2898).

Climate change

A change in the state of the climate that can be identified (for example, by using statistical tests) by changes in the mean and/or the variability of its properties and that persists for an extended period, typically decades or longer (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2902).

Climate extreme (extreme weather or climate event)

The occurrence of a value of a weather or climate variable above (or below) a threshold value near the upper (or lower) ends of the range of observed values of the variable (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2902).

Extreme weather event

An event that is rare at a particular place and time of year. Definitions of ‘rare’ vary, but an extreme weather event would normally be as rare as or rarer than the 10th or 90th percentile of a probability density function estimated from observations. The characteristics of extreme weather may vary from place to place in an absolute sense (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2908).

Food system

All the elements (environment, people, inputs, processes, infrastructures, institutions, and others) and activities that relate to the production, processing, distribution, preparation and consumption of food and the output of these activities, including socioeconomic and environmental outcomes (HLPE, 2017; Möller et al., 2023, p. 2909).

Food security

A situation exists when all people, always, have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life. The four pillars of food security are availability, access, utilisation, and stability. The nutritional dimension is integral to the concept of food security (FAO, 2018/ 2009; Möller et al., 2023, p. 2909).

Food Availability

Physical availability of food. Food availability addresses the supply side of food security and is determined by the levels of food production, stocks, and net trade (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2909).

Food Access

Economic and/or physical access to food. Economic access is determined by disposable income, food prices, and the provision of and access to social support. Physical access is determined by the availability and quality of land and other infrastructure, property rights, or the functioning of markets (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2909).

Food Utilisation

The way in which the body uses the various nutrients in food. Individuals achieve sufficient energy and nutrient intake through good care and feeding practices, food preparation, diet diversity, and intrahousehold food distribution. Combined with biological utilisation of the food consumed, energy and nutrient intake determine the nutrition status of individuals (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2909).

Food Stability

The stability of the other three dimensions over time. Even if individuals' food intake is adequate today, they are still considered food insecure if they periodically have inadequate access to food, risking the deterioration of their nutrition status. Adverse weather conditions, political instability, or economic factors (unemployment, rising food prices) may have an impact on individuals' food security status (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2909).

Global warming

Global warming refers to the increase in global surface temperature relative to a baseline reference period, averaging over a period sufficient to remove interannual variations (for example, 20 or 30 years). A common choice for the baseline is 1850–1900 (the earliest period of reliable observations with sufficient geographic coverage), with more modern baselines used depending on the application (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2910).

Climate justice

A just approach to addressing climate change involves linking development and human rights, intending to safeguard the rights of the most vulnerable individuals and promote a fair distribution of the burdens and benefits of climate change and its effects (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2909).

Global Food Security Index

Considers affordability, availability, and quality across 113 countries, based on a definition derived from the 1996 World Food Summit. The index is a comprehensive scoring model incorporating 28 distinct indicators to evaluate the drivers of food security in developing and developed countries. It employs a combination of quantitative and qualitative measures for a comprehensive analysis (UNCDD, 2022).

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The 17 global goals for development for all countries established by the United Nations through a participatory process and elaborated in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, including

ending poverty and hunger; ensuring health and well-being, education, gender equality, clean water and energy, and decent work; building and ensuring resilient and sustainable infrastructure, cities and consumption; reducing inequalities; protecting land and water ecosystems; promoting peace, justice and partnerships; and taking urgent action on climate change (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2924).

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)

The UNFCCC was adopted in May 1992 and opened for signature at the 1992 Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro. It entered into force in March 1994 and, as of May 2018, had 197 Parties (196 States and the European Union). The Convention's ultimate objective is the 'stabilisation of greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system.' The provisions of the Convention are pursued and implemented by two treaties: the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2926).

Vulnerability

The propensity or predisposition to be adversely affected. Vulnerability encompasses a variety of concepts and elements, including sensitivity or susceptibility to harm and lack of capacity to cope and adapt. See also Exposure, Hazard, and Risk (Möller et al., 2023, p. 2928).

KEYWORDS

Climate change

Food security

Smallholder farmers

Staple crops

Food production

Food availability

Food utilisation

Food accessibility

Rural Areas

Adaptation

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APPENDIX 1 University of the west of Scotland Ethical Approval Letter

09/01/2023

Dear RESCHET Hubert Fudjumdjum,

Your application 19521: Climate change and health: An analysis of the impact of climate change on smallholder farmers' food security in western Cameroon in the department of Kong-khi., submission 16171, has been approved by the Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Hughes

APPENDIX 2 Ministry's Research Authorisation letter 01 from the State Ministry

REPUBLIQUE DU CAMEROUN
Paix – Travail – Patrie

MINISTERE DE L'AGRICULTURE
ET DU DEVELOPPEMENT RURAL

SECRETARIAT GENERAL

DIRECTION DES ENQUETES ET
DES STATISTIQUES AGRICOLES

CELLULE DES INFORMATIONS ET
DE L'ALERTE RAPIDE

REPUBLIC OF CAMEROON
Peace – Work – Fatherland

MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE
AND RURAL DEVELOPEMENT

GENERAL SECRETARIAT

DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURAL
SURVEYS AND STATISTICS

INFORMATIONS AND EARLY
WARNING UNIT

N° 00301 / MINADER/SG/DESA/CIAR/CEA/dtm

Yaoundé, le

17 MAR 2023

LE MINISTRE

À

MONSIEUR FUDJUMDJUM Hubert
Doctorant à l'Université de l'Ecosse de l'Ouest et
l'Université des sciences appliquées de Hambourg
21033 Hambourg Allemagne

Réf: Votre lettre du 14 février 2023.

Objet: Demande d'autorisation pour mener des interviews auprès des agriculteurs et recueillir des données annuaires météorologiques et les productions agricoles dans la région de l'Ouest.

Monsieur,

Faisant suite à votre correspondance de référence et d'objet repris ci-dessus,

J'ai l'honneur de marquer mon accord afin que vous recueilliez les informations relatives à l'impact des changements climatiques sur la sécurité alimentaire des petits exploitants agricoles ; à la disponibilité, l'accès et l'utilisation des aliments par les ménages ; et aux stratégies d'adaptation desdits ménages dans le département du Koung-Khi, région de l'Ouest Cameroun.

A l'issue de votre étude, bien vouloir mettre à notre disposition les résultats de vos recherches.

Veillez agréer, **monsieur**, ma considération distinguée.

Personal details withheld.

APPENDIX 3 Ministry's Research Authorisation letter 02 From the departmental Delegate

REPUBLIQUE DU CAMEROUN
Paix-Travail-Patrie

MINISTERE DE L'AGRICULTURE
ET DU DEVELOPPEMENT RURAL

REPUBLIC OF CAMEROON
Peace-Work-Fatherland

MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE AND RURAL
DEVELOPMENT

DELEGATION REGIONALE DE L'OUEST

DELEGATION DEPARTEMENTALE DU KOUNG-KHI

WEST REGIONAL DELEGATION

KOUNG-KHI DIVISIONAL DELEGATION

BUREAU DES AFFAIRES ADMINISTRATIVES
ET FINANCIERES

ADMINISTRATIVES AND FINANCIALS AFFAIRS
OFFICE

AUTORISATION D'INTERVIEW SUR LE TERRAIN

Dans l'optique de mener des interviews auprès des agriculteurs et recueillir des données annuaires météorologiques et les productions agricoles, Monsieur **FUDJUMDJUM Hubert**, Doctorant à l'Université de l'Ecosse de l'Ouest et l'Université des Sciences Appliquées de Hambourg est autorisé à se rendre sur le terrain pour effectuer son travail d'interview dans tout le Département du Koung-Khi.

Nous comptons sur votre entière collaboration, pour faciliter la faisabilité de ce travail.

Personal details withheld.

APPENDIX 4 Participants' information sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Researcher:

Hubert FUDJUMDJUM, a Doctorat Student at the University of West of Scotland and Hamburg University of Applied Sciences in Germany, is undertaking the research.

1. Research Project Title

The PhD research title is:

Climate change and Health: An analysis of the impact of climate change on smallholder farmers' food security in the department of koung-khi in western Cameroon.

2. Invitation

Dear Participants, you are invited to participate in the PhD research mentioned above.

Before you decide, you must understand the purpose of the PhD research and its involvement. Please read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask the researcher if there is anything unclear or if you want more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this.

3. What is the project's purpose?

This PhD research aims to explore the impact of long-term shifts in temperatures and weather patterns on smallholder farmers' food security in western Cameroon in the department of kong-khi and how they respond to ensure food scarcity. In a comprehensive approach with minimum 200 or maximum 300 smallholders farmers, the researcher will :

- - Investigate the occurrence of changes in weather patterns in the study area and its influence on staple food.
- -assess the current state of the impact of climate change on food availability, accessibility, and utilisation among smallholder farmers.
- -explore smallholder farmers' adaptation strategies and the faced challenges.

Consent to Participate in the research

You are invited to participate in the research of Hubert Fudjumdjum, Doctorant at the University of West of Scotland and Hamburg University of Applied Sciences. The purpose of the research is to identify and analyse the impact of climate change on smallholder farmers' food security in western Cameroon, more particularly in the department of Kong-Khi. The participation should take approximately 20 to 30 minutes to complete.

PARTICIPATION

Your participation in this survey is voluntary. You may refuse to participate in the research or exit the survey without penalty. In addition, you may skip any question you do not wish to answer for any reason.

BENEFITS AND RISKS

You will receive no direct benefits from participating in this research. However, your responses may help us learn more about the impact of climate change on the food security of smallholder farmers in western Cameroon, more particularly in the department of Koung-Khi. Therefore, there are no foreseeable risks involved in participating in this research.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your survey answers will be for academic purposes only. Any information received from you will remain confidential. At the end of the survey, you will be asked if you are interested in the results. If you provide contact information such as your phone number or email address, your survey responses may no longer be anonymous to the Researcher. However, no names or identifying information would be included in any publications or presentations based on these data, and your responses to this survey will remain confidential.

CONTACT

If you have further questions or concerns about your rights as a participant in this study, contact the Researcher at B00362457@studentmail.uws.ac.uk

If you have questions or concerns regarding the Ethical Approval Processes of the Study, contact the Research Ethics Board of the School of Computing, Engineering & Physical Sciences at: CEPSEthics@uws.ac.uk.

Please put your initials in the boxes below to confirm your wish to participate:

- I have read the Participant Information Sheet.
- I voluntarily agree to participate.
- I am 18 years of age or older.
- I agree to participate in this study

Signature of participant Date.....

APPENDIX 6 Format of Focus Group Discussion

Format of Focus Group Discussion

Title of the Project: Climate change and food security: An analysis of the impact of climate change on smallholder farmers' food security in the department of koung-khi in western Cameroon.

During the survey, the researcher will select eight stallholder farmers composed of four men and four women. The Participants in the group will be proportionately represented. During the discussion, participants should not speak only on their behalf but reflect on the situation of most households in the area as they know it. The discussion should last 45mins to 1 hour.

- a) Word of Welcome from the researcher (2 min)
 - Explain the purpose and process of the focus group discussion.

- b) Introduction by all participants (8 min)
 - Ask each person to present himself.

- d) Ask the questions (30 min)
 - Ask questions, then go around the table and have each person speak.

- e) Summarize the discussion by the Researcher (3 min)
 - Give a short summary of the main themes you heard.
 - Ask participants if researcher correctly describe what was said.

- f) Thanks, and closing (2 min)
 - Thank everyone for participating.
 - Explain how researcher plan to use the information and what to do next.

APPENDIX 7 Questionnaire for Focus Group Discussion

PhD research title:

Climate change and food security: An analysis of the impact of climate change on smallholder farmers' food security in the department of koung-khi in western Cameroon

Questions for Focus Group Discussion

1- How many meals on average, do you consume in a day in you community? Explain how and why climate change influence on this number over the past years?

2-How change in temperature and precipitation have influenced the main food crops cultivated and consumed in your area during the last thirty years? (Please explain more about the quality and quantity of food crops)

3-How extreme weather has impacted the availability, accessibility, and utilisation of food in you region and your family? (Please explain more about transportation, storage, and consumption)

4- What measures are you applying in your area to address and cope with climate change impacts on food security? (Please explain more about active and passive measures)

5-What are the challenges that constrain the application of the adaptation strategies and what do you do to overcome the threat?

APPENDIX 8 Questionnaire for Key Informant Interview

PhD Question for Key Informant Interview

Interview with agricultural experts and Churches leaders in west Cameroon

- 1- How does climate change affect smallholders' food security in the western region?
- 2- How are Cameroonian states supporting smallholder farmers in adapting and mitigating the impact of climate change on food security in Cameroon and at the rural level?
- 3- What are the policies you are implementing at the local level to support smallholder farmers in adapting and mitigating the impact of climate change on food security?
- 4-What challenges limit the application of adaptation and mitigation policies, and what are you doing to overcome the threat?

APPENDIX 9 Questionnaire for Survey

Title of doctoral research:

Climate Change and Health: An Analysis of the Impact of Climate Change on Smallholder Farmers' Food Security in the Department of Koung-Khi in Western Cameroon.

Section I: Information and experience of smallholder farmers on understanding climate change

Q1. What is your gender? Men Women

Q2. How old are you? _____

Q3. What is your highest qualification?

Graduate

of the college

Postgraduate PhD

No qualification

Other (please specify) _____

Q4. How many people make up your household? _____

Q5. How long have you been working as a farmer? _____

Q6. How big is your farm/field? _____ ha

Q7. Do you own the land?

No. Yes

Q8. Do you rent the land?

No. Yes

Q9. How many people are working on your farm/field today? _____

Q9a. Does it change with the seasons? Yes, No Other (please specify) _____

Q10. What is your main objective for agriculture?

Family needs Business purpose Mixed Other (please specify) _____

Q 11. What type of crop do you usually grow?

Potatoes Ignams maize Beans Peanuts Casava Other crops: (please specify) _____

Q12. Have you ever heard of climate change?

Yes, quite (Please go to Q 13) Yes, moderate (Please go to Q1 3)

Yes, a bit (Please go to Q 13) No (Please go to Q1 9)

Q 13. If so, could you tick off the effects of climate change you've already heard?

Increase in communicable and non-communicable diseases Sea level rise

More rain

More diseases can emerge

- More storms
- Increased warmer temperatures Increased soil erosion Less rain Other (please specify)

Q14. From the list above, please name the effects observed in your area over the past thirty years.

- 1 _____
- 2 _____
- 3 _____

Q15. On which of the following platforms have you heard about climate change?

- Television Government agencies Libraries
- Radio Environmental Groups Friends or colleagues
- Journal Academic Journal/Special Publication Other (please specify) _____

Q 16. What do you think are the causes of climate change?

- Combustion of fossil fuels (coal, oil, gas, gasoline) Deforestation Greenhouse gas emissions
- Atmospheric concentration of CO2 I don't know Others (please write down all ideas) _ _ _

Q17. Have you attended a consultation or workshop on the impacts of climate change and food security in previous years? Yes (please go to question 18) No (Please go ask 20)

Q18. What did you discuss at the event?

- Raising awareness about climate change and food security
- Mangrove conservation to increase food production
- Reuse and recycle household waste
- Reforestation (tree planting)
- Household information on disaster management plans
- Do not cut down trees/forests
- Household information on farm dependency and types of crops produced
- The state of knowledge of subsistence farmers on climate change
- Current adaptation practices
- Other (please specify) _____

Q19. What is the level of confidence in climate change information if you were to receive it from?

	A lot	A little	Not much	Not at all
Family members				
Colleagues				
Scientific				
Government Agencies				
Environmental organizations				
Media (TV, radio, newspapers, etc.)				

Section II: Climate change and food availability, accessibility, and use.

Q20 How strong is the impact of climate change on the availability of sufficient quantities of food of appropriate quality, supplied by domestic production over the last thirty years?

High incidence Medium impact Low impact No impact

Q21 How strong is the impact of climate change on having sufficient resources to obtain appropriate food for a nutritious diet over the past thirty years?

High incidence Medium impact Low impact No impact

Q22 How strong is the impact of climate change on food use through adequate food, clean water, sanitation, and health care to achieve nutritional well-being over the past thirty years?

High incidence Medium impact Low impact No impact

Section III: Strategies and challenges of adaptation

Q23 Rate different coping strategies using the same four-point rating scale and check off the strategies that are most effective for you.

Coping strategies	High	Moyenne	Low	No
Growing short-lived crops				
Practice crop rotation				
Soil conservation techniques				
Practice intercropping				
Practicing crop diversification				
Increased use of irrigation				
Change of planting date				
Agroforestry practice				
Income-generating activities				
Agricultural diversification				
Integrated Agricultural System				

Q24 Rate the different challenges of coping strategies using the same four-point rating scale and check mark you encounter.

Trouble	High	Moyenne	Low	No problem
Lack of water availability				
High cost of farm inputs				
Unforeseen weather				
Lack of access to timely weather information				
Lack of access to finance				

Lack of access to agricultural subsidies				
Lack of market access				
Limited access to an agricultural practice advisor				
Low soil fertility				
Limited farm size				
Inadequate farm size				

Thank you for your answers!

APPENDIX 10 Pictures of Fieldwork

Fieldwork in Poumougne

Departmental Delegation of Koung Khi

Fielwork in Batoufan

Fielwork in Batoufan

Fieldwork in Poumougne

Fieldwork in Badrefam

The images have been taken and published with consent.

Fieldwork in Batoufan

Fieldwork in Batoufan

Fieldwork in Badrefam

Fieldwork in Fomayum

Fieldwork in Batoufan

Fieldwork in Fomayum

The images have been taken and published with consent.

Fieldwork in Bayangam

Fieldwork in Badrafam

Fieldwork Logistics in Batoufam

Fieldwork Logistics in Demdeng

The images have been taken and published with consent.

APPENDIX 11 Statistics of Crop production in West Cameroon used to produce the work

